

**Exploring the Image of
Chinese Temples as a Cultural Tourist Attraction in Phuket, Thailand:
Using Projective Questions and Drawing Techniques**

Inderpal Singh Virdee

**A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the Degree of Master of
Business Administration in Hospitality and Tourism Management**

(International Program)

Prince of Songkla University

2016

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Thesis Title Exploring the Image of Chinese Temples as a Cultural Tourist Attraction in Phuket, Thailand: Using Projective Questions and Drawing Techniques Factors Enhancing Brand Awareness of Design Hotels on Thailand's Andaman Coastline

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ABSTRACT

Chinese (Taoist) temples and shrines in Phuket, Thailand have a long and unique history. Although Phuket remains primarily a sun, sea and sand destination, Phuket's specific cultural tourist attractions such as Chinese temples and shrines lay dormant. Meanwhile, only Phuket's religious Vegetarian Festival is promoted for tourist's consumption. This study explores the image of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket as cultural tourist attractions based on the perspectives of international tourists. The research employed a qualitative approach using open-ended questions, projective questions and projective drawing techniques to capture the image of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket from 153 international tourists visiting Chinese temples and shrines around Phuket. The data was then analysed using content analysis. The results were triangulated to increase the reliability and validity. The overall results revealed the image of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket as having statues, figures and gods, while being religious, traditional, fascinating, attractive, mysterious, peaceful and unique. The projective drawings identified the unique features of the Chinese temples and shrines as the altar, calligraphy, columns, the ding, pot or cauldron, objects of divination, the donation safe or box, the firecracker room, lanterns, nature, outside walls, placards, plates and signs, the roof and statues, figures and gods. In addition, Asian and European tourists were found to have different perceptions towards Chinese temples. Asian tourists related to more religious and traditional imagery than European tourists, who experienced greater feelings of peace and fascination. In conclusion, Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket are seen as being unique cultural and heritage attractions. However, the feasibility and profitability needs to be further assessed before the future development of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket. The managerial implications of this study are also discussed.

Keywords: Phuket Chinese Temples, Projective Techniques, Qualitative Triangulation, Destination Image, Cultural Tourism

ชื่อเรื่อง	การสำรวจภาพลักษณ์ความเป็นแหล่งท่องเที่ยวทางวัฒนธรรมของศาลเจ้าเงินในจังหวัดภูเก็ต:เทคนิคการใช้ภาพเพื่อฉายความคิดเห็น
ผู้วิจัย	นายอินเดอร่ปอล ชิงห์ เเวอร์ดี
สาขาวิชา	บริหารธุรกิจมหาบัณฑิต สาขาการจัดการบริการและการท่องเที่ยว (หลักสูตรนานาชาติ)
ปีการศึกษา	2560

บทคัดย่อ

ศาลเจ้าเงินในจังหวัดภูเก็ตมีประวัติความเป็นมาอันยาวนานและโดดเด่น ถึงแม้จังหวัดภูเก็ตจะเป็นแหล่งท่องเที่ยวทางทะเล แต่ศาลเจ้าเงินซึ่งถือเป็นที่ยึดเหนี่ยวทางวัฒนธรรมก็ได้รับความสนใจตลอดทั้งปี สืบเนื่องจากการรณรงค์ให้เทศกาลถือศีลกินผักเป็นเทศกาลท่องเที่ยวประจำปี งานวิจัยนี้มุ่งศึกษามุมมองความคิดเห็นของนักท่องเที่ยวต่างชาติที่มีต่อภาพลักษณ์ความเป็นแหล่งท่องเที่ยวทางวัฒนธรรมของศาลเจ้าเงินในจังหวัดภูเก็ต โดยเป็นการศึกษาวิจัยเชิงคุณภาพ อาศัยเครื่องมือในการวิจัย อันได้แก่ คำถามปลายเปิด คำถามและการใช้ภาพฉายความคิดเห็น เพื่อแสดงให้เห็นถึงภาพลักษณ์ของศาลเจ้าเงินในจังหวัดภูเก็ต ในความคิดเห็นของนักท่องเที่ยวต่างชาติ จำนวน 153 คน จากศาลเจ้าเงินจำนวน 7 แห่งในจังหวัดภูเก็ต และวิเคราะห์ข้อมูลโดยวิธีการวิเคราะห์ที่แก่นสาระ (Content Analysis) และสถิติค่าเฉลี่ย จากนั้นจึงนำข้อมูลที่ได้มาตรวจสอบแบบสามเส้า (Triangulation) เพื่อเพิ่มค่าความเชื่อมั่นและความเที่ยงตรงของข้อมูล ผลการวิจัยแสดงให้เห็นว่าภาพลักษณ์ของศาลเจ้าเงินในจังหวัดภูเก็ต คือ สถานที่ที่ประกอบไปด้วย ประติมากรรม รูปเคารพของเทพเจ้า และเป็นสถานที่ทางศาสนาเก่าแก่ดั้งเดิม มีความน่าดึงดูดใจ มีเสน่ห์ ลึกลับ สงบ และโดดเด่นมีเอกลักษณ์เป็นของตนเอง การใช้ภาพเพื่อฉายความคิดเห็นเชื่อมโยงลักษณะสำคัญของศาลเจ้าเงินกับ โต๊ะหมู่บูชา ลายพู่กันจีน เส้า กระจาดรูป หรือกระจาดสำหรับประกอบพิธีกรรม วัตถุเกี่ยวกับเทพเจ้า ถังรับบริจาค ห้อยจุดประทัด ตะเกียง ธรรมชาติ กำแพงชั้นนอก แผ่นประกาศ ป้ายสัญลักษณ์ หลังคาประดับรูปปั้น รูปปั้นและเทพเจ้า นักท่องเที่ยวชาวเอเชียและชาวยุโรปมีความคิดเห็นแตกต่างกัน โดยนักท่องเที่ยวชาวเอเชียมีมุมมองว่าศาลเจ้าเงินเป็นแหล่งท่องเที่ยวดั้งเดิมทางศาสนา ในขณะที่นักท่องเที่ยวชาวยุโรปจะเกิดความรู้สึกสงบและความประทับใจมากกว่า กล่าวโดยสรุปได้ว่า ศาลเจ้าเงินในจังหวัดภูเก็ตได้รับการยอมรับว่าเป็นสถานที่ท่องเที่ยวที่เป็นมรดกทางวัฒนธรรมอันโดดเด่นมีเอกลักษณ์ อย่างไรก็ตามก็มีความจำเป็นที่จะต้องศึกษาเพิ่มเติมเพื่อทราบถึงคุณค่าในแง่การสร้างรายได้ งานวิจัยนี้ยังได้ให้ข้อเสนอแนะต่อการนำผลวิจัยไปใช้ประโยชน์ในแง่การจัดการอีกด้วย

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Inderpal Singh Virdee

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTERS

ABSTRACT	1
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	3
1 INTRODUCTION	14
1.1 Research Background.....	14
1.2 The Importance of Cultural Tourism	15
1.3 Destination Image	17
1.4 Research Aims & Objectives	20
1.4.1 Research Aim	20
1.4.2 Research Question.	20
1.4.3 Research Objectives.....	20
1.5 Research Benefits.....	20
1.6 Scope of the Research	21
1.6.1 Scope of Time	21
1.6.2 Scope of Demographics	21
1.6.3 Scope of Geographical Locations	21
1.7 Definition of Terms	21
2 LITERATURE REVIEW	23
2.1 Cultural Tourism in Thailand.....	23
2.2 Chinese Taoist/Daoist Temples in Phuket as Tourist Attractions.....	23
2.2.1 Taoist/Daoist Philosophy	23
2.2.2 Taoist/Daoist temples.....	24
2.2.3 Taoist/Daoist temples in Phuket	24
2.3 Destination Image within Cultural Tourism.....	28
2.4 Tourists' Cultural Perceptions.....	30
2.5 Definition of Destination Image.....	31
2.6 Destination Selection: The Influence of Tourism Destination Image.....	31
2.7 Destination Image Formation.....	32
2.8. The Components of Destination Image.....	34
2.9 Measuring Destination Image	36

2.10 Projective Tests	38
2.10.1 Projective Questions	39
2.10.2 Projective Drawing	39
2.10.3 Drawing Analysis.....	40
2.10.4 Drawing in Colour	41
2.11 Content Analysis	42
2.12 Triangulation Methods.....	43
3 METHODOLOGY	45
3.1 Population and Sample.....	46
3.2 Data Collection.....	46
3.3 Research Instruments	48
3.4 Interview Materials	57
3.5 Interview Process	57
3.6 Pilot Test	58
3.7 Data Analysis	59
3.8 Reliability and Validity	64
3.9 Triangulation Analysis	64
3.10 Research Limitations.....	65
3.11 Research Ethics	65
4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.....	67
4.1 Respondents	67
4.1.1 Response Rate.....	67
4.1.2 Respondent's Profile.....	67
4.2 Objective 1: To Explore the Image of Chinese temples as a Visitor's attraction in Phuket	71
4.2.1 Holistic Tangible Image of Chinese Temples/Shrines in Phuket	72
4.2.2 Statues, Figures and Gods.....	72
4.2.2.1 Open-ended Results.....	72
4.2.2.2 Projective Results	72
4.2.2.3 Drawing Results	73
4.2.2.4 The Impact of Statues, Figures and Gods Images on Tourism.....	73
4.2.3 Holistic Intangible Image of Chinese Temples/Shrines in Phuket	73

4.2.4 Religious/Traditional	74
4.2.4.1 Open-ended Results	74
4.2.4.2 Projective Results	74
4.2.4.3. Drawings Results	75
4.2.4.4 The Impact of Religious and Traditional Images on Tourism	75
4.2.5 Fascinating	76
4.2.5.1 Open-ended Results	76
4.2.5.2 Projective Results	76
4.2.5.3 Drawings Results	76
4.2.5.4 The Impact of Fascinating Images on Tourism	77
4.2.6 Attractive	77
4.2.6.1 Open-ended Results	77
4.2.6.2 Projective Results	78
4.2.6.3 Drawings Results	78
4.2.6.4 The Impact of Attractive Images on Tourism	80
4.2.7 Mysterious	80
4.2.7.1 Open-ended Results	80
4.2.7.2 Projective Results	80
4.2.7.3 Drawings Results	81
4.2.7.4 The Impact of Mysterious Images on Tourism	81
4.2.8 Peaceful	82
4.2.8.1 Open-ended Results	82
4.2.8.2 Projective Results	82
4.2.8.3 Drawings Results	82
4.2.7.4 The Impact of Peaceful Images on Tourism	83
4.2.8 Unique	83
4.3 Objective 2: To Identify the Uniqueness of Chinese Temples in Phuket	83
4.3.1 Open-ended Results	84
4.3.2 Projective Results	84
4.3.4 Drawing Results	84
4.3.4 The Impact of Unique Images on Tourism	89

4.4 Objective 3: To Examine the Differences in Perception Between Asian and European	90
4.4.1 Open-ended Questions by Asians and Europeans	90
4.4.1.1 First Images that Come to Mind for Asians and Europeans.....	90
4.4.1.2 Distinctive Features for Asians and Europeans.....	91
4.4.1.3 First impressions upon entering a Chinese Temple for Asians and Europeans	93
4.4.5 Projective Questions: Asian and European Image.....	94
4.4.6 Projective Drawings by Asian Respondents	95
4.4.7 Projective Drawings by European Respondents	97
4.5 Respondent Recommendations	98
4.5.1 Possibility to Recommend	98
4.5.2 Reasons for Recommendations.....	100
4.5.3 Future Admission Fee	100
4.5.4 Recommendations for Promotional Images and Pictures	101
4.5.5 Recommendations for Promotional Activities.....	102
4.5.6 Recommendations for Management	102
5 CONCLUSION	105
5.1 Review.....	105
5.2 Summary of Findings	106
5.3 Assessment of Research Methodology Used	107
5.4 Promoting Chinese Temples and Shrines in Phuket	109
6 LIMITATIONS.....	110
7 FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS.....	110
REFERENCES	111
TABLES & FIGURES	140
Table 9.1.1 Chinese (Taoist/Daoist) temple and shrine studies from 1898 to 2015	140
Table 9.1.2 Religious temples and shrine studies concentrating on temple tourism, temple image, temple attraction, temple attitudes and temple behaviour	144
Figure 9.2.1 McKercher & Du Cros, (2002). A Cultural Tourist Typology.....	148
Table 9.3.1 Themes used for thematic analysis including references	149
Table 9.4.1 Number of respondents at Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket	154
Table 9.4.2 Respondent's socio-demographic profile.....	155

Table 9.4.2 Respondents' nationalities and regional classifications	157
Table 9.4.3 Travel behaviour of tourists who visit Chinese temples in Phuket	158
Table 9.4.2.1 Details of respondent's experience at Chinese temples in Phuket	159
Table 9.4.5 Factors affecting a Chinese Temple visitation in Phuket	161
Table 9.4.6 Respondents' expectations before visiting a Chinese temple in Phuket	161
Table 9.4.7 Provision of information at Chinese temples in Phuket	161
Table 9.4.8 Level of visitor satisfaction at Chinese temples in Phuket	162
Table 9.4.9 Activities engaged at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket	162
Table 9.4.10 Respondents spending behaviour at Chinese temples in Phuket	163
Table 9.4.11 The reasons that international tourists visited Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket....	163
Table 9.4.12 First images that come to mind when thinking of a Chinese temple overall	164
Table 9.4.13 First images that came to mind when thinking of a Chinese temple for Asians	165
Table 9.4.14 First images that came to mind when thinking of a Chinese temple for Europeans ..	165
Table 9.4.15 The distinctive features of Chinese temple in Phuket overall	166
Table 9.4.16 The distinctive features of Chinese temple in Phuket for Asian	167
Table 9.4.17 The distinctive features of Chinese temple in Phuket for Europeans	167
Table 9.4.18 Overall respondents first impressions when entering a Chinese temple in Phuket....	168
Table 9.4.19 Asian tourist's first impressions when entering a Chinese temple in Phuket	169
Table 9.4.20 European tourist's first impression when entering a Chinese temple in Phuket	170
Table 9.4.21 Frequency of responses for projective questions	171
Table 9.4.22 The overall image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using projective questions	172
Table 9.4.23 Top 6 overall themes of Chinese temples in Phuket using projective questions	173
Figure 9.4.1 The overall image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using Echtner and Ritchie (2003) Components of Destination Image Model.	173
Table 9.4.23 Comparison of Asian and European image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using projective questions	174
Figure 9.4.2 The Asian respondents image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using Echtner and Ritchie (2003) Components of Destination Image Model.	175
Figure 9.4.3 The European respondents image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using Echtner and Ritchie (2003) Components of Destination Image Model.	176
Table 9.4.24 The drawn categories and elements of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket	177

Table 9.4.25 The drawn descriptive themes of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket	180
Table 9.4.26 The overall results of the drawn elements and themes by respondents	182
Table 9.4.27 The results of the drawn elements and themes by Asian and European respondents	184
Table 9.4.28 The results of drawing numbers, completion and dimensions	186
Table 9.4.29 The results of drawing size, proportion and impression	186
Table 9.4.30 The results of cropped images and use of calligraphic impressions	187
Fig. 9.4.4 Results of object's drawn a with non-directional perspective	188
Fig. 9.4.5 Results of object's drawn a with directional perspective.....	188
Figure 9.4.6 Drawn results of the nine grid locations	189
Figure 9.4.7 Drawn results of the three horizontal locations	189
Figure 9.4.8 Drawn results of the three vertical locations	189
Table 9.4.31 The results of pencil usage in chinese temple/shrine drawings	190
Table 9.4.32 The results of colour pencil usage in Chinese temple/shrine drawings	192
Table 9.4.33 The results of colours used in Chinese temple/shrine drawings	194
Figure 9.4.9a The image results for the altar at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	195
Figure 9.4.9b Drawn examples of the altar image at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	196
Figure 9.4.10a The image results for calligraphy at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	197
Figure 9.4.10b Drawn examples of calligraphy at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	198
Figure 9.4.11a The image results for the columns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	199
Figure 9.4.11b Drawn examples of columns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	200
Figure 9.4.12a The image results for the ding/pot/cauldron at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	201
Figure 9.4.12b Drawn examples of the ding/pot/cauldron at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	202
Figure 9.4.13a The image results for the objects of divination at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket	

by overall respondents.....	203
Figure 9.4.13b Drawn examples of objects of divination at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	204
Figure 9.4.14a The image results for the donation safe/box at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	205
Figure 9.4.14b Drawn examples of donation safe/box at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	206
Figure 9.4.15a The image results for the firecracker room at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	207
Figure 9.4.15b Drawn examples of the firecracker room at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	208
Figure 9.4.16a The image results for the lanterns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	209
Figure 9.4.16b Drawn examples of lanterns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	210
Figure 9.4.17a The image results for nature around the Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	211
Figure 9.4.17b Drawn examples of nature around the Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	212
Figure 9.4.18a The image results for the outside wall at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	213
Figure 9.4.18a Drawn examples of the outside wall at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	214
Figure 9.4.19a The image results for the placards/plates/signs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	215
Figure 9.4.19b Drawn examples of placards/plates/signs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	216
Figure 9.4.20a The image results for the roof at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	217
Figure 9.4.20b Drawn examples of the roof at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	218

Figure 9.4.21a The image results for the statues/figures/gods at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	219
Figure 9.4.21b Drawn examples of statues/figures/gods at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents.....	220
Figure 9.4.22a The image results for the Chinese temples and shrines architecture in Phuket by Asian respondents.....	221
Figure 9.4.22b Drawn examples of chinese temples/shrines architecture in Phuket by Asian respondents.....	222
Figure 9.4.23a The image results for the banners at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents.....	223
Figure 9.4.23b Drawn examples of banners at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents.....	224
Figure 9.4.24a The image results for the ding/pot/cauldron at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents	225
Figure 9.4.24b Drawn examples of ding/pot/cauldron at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents	226
Figure 9.4.25a The image results for the objects of divination at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents	227
Figure 9.4.25b Drawn examples of objects of divination at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents	228
Figure 9.4.26a The image results for the placards/plates/signs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents	229
Figure 9.4.26b Drawn examples of placards/plates/signs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents	230
Figure 9.4.27a The image results for the roof at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents.....	231
Figure 9.4.27b Drawn examples of roofs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents.....	232
Figure 9.4.28a The image results for the statues/figures/gods at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents	233
Figure 9.4.28b Drawn Examples of Statues/Figures/Gods at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by	

Asian respondents	234
Figure 9.4.29a The image results for the chimney at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents	235
Figure 9.4.29b Drawn examples of chimneys at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents.....	236
Figure 9.4.30a The image results for the donation safe/box at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents	237
Figure 9.4.30b. Drawn examples of donation safe/box at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents	238
Figure 9.4.31a The image results for the firecracker room at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents	239
Figure 9.4.31b Drawn examples of the firecracker room at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents	240
Figure 9.4.32a The image results for the lanterns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents	241
Figure 9.4.32b Drawn examples of lanterns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents.....	242
Figure 9.4.33a The image results for the offerings at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents	243
Figure 9.4.33b Drawn examples of offerings at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents.....	244
Figure 9.4.34a The image results for the outside wall at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents	245
Figure 9.4.34b Drawn examples of outside wall at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents.....	246
Figure 9.4.35a The image results for the roof at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents.....	247
Figure 9.4.35b Drawn examples of roofs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents.....	248
Table 9.4.34 Recommending Chinese temples in Phuket to others	249
Table 9.4.35 Reasons for recommending Chinese temples in Phuket	250

Table 9.4.36 Future admission fee at Chinese temples in Phuket.....	251
Table 9.4.37. Recommendations for promotional images of Chinese temples in Phuket.....	252
Table 9.4.38. Recommendations for promotional activities at Chinese temples in Phuket.....	252
Table 9.4.39. Recommendations for temple managers at Chinese temples in Phuket.....	253
APPENDIX.....	254
9.5 Interview Questions.....	254
Interview Questions 1 – Local Expert	254
Interview Questions 2 – Tour Guides	255
Interview Questions 3 – Tourists	256
9.6 (306) Projective Drawings of Chinese Temples and Shrine in Phuket	263
VITAE.....	303

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

Thailand is ranked 10th in the world's top tourist destinations (UNWTO, 2016), with Phuket as one of the leading tourist destinations of choice in Thailand (TripAdvisor, 2015a). Phuket welcomed 18,977,912 foreign tourists and generated 272 billion Thai Baht (THB) in 2015 (Thailand's Department of Tourism, 2015) and continues to be one of the major economic contributors to Thailand's tourism industry attracting the majority of international tourists through its idyllic destination image of sun, sea and sand (Kontogeorgopoulos, 1998). Yet, with Phuket's long history, rich cultural and unique heritage, most cultural tourism resources in Phuket remain underdeveloped, in particular Chinese (Taoist/Daoist) temples and shrines. One local temple manager estimated that about one thousand international tourists visit their site per year.

Chinese temples and shrines in Thailand face an exceptional problem in that the Thai government sees Chinese temples/shrines as non-religious places. Lacking legal religious status, many Chinese temples/shrines remain unregistered and receive very little to no government intervention (Kataoka, 2012), leaving Chinese temples/shrines struggling to manage their own finances, operations and advertising. Nevertheless, Chinese temples/shrines have many unique cultural aspects, for example their long cultural history, distinctive architecture, cosmological and numerical symbolic design (such as Feng Shui (Johnson, 1989)), bright colours, religious artefacts like the Taoist cauldron (Ding/Ting), mythological dragons and creatures, statues of deities, religious rites and festivals such as the Vegetarian Festival, and divination, as well as functioning as community centres for traditional medical, psychological and spiritual advice.

Wat Mangkon Kamalawat, also known as Wat Leng Noei Yi (Dragon Lotus Temple) is a Taoist, Confucian and Buddhist temple in the Chinatown area of Yaowarat, Bangkok and is one of the most sacred temples in Bangkok. Wat Mangkon Kamalawat is a successful example of a cultural tourism attraction (Choeichuenjit & Sapsanguanboon, 2014) that is promoted on TripAdvisor (2015b), Lonely Planet (2015) and Bangkok.com (2015), and attracts many tourists through its temple images; however, very little research has been done on Chinese temples in Phuket. Considering that Phuket has a large Hokkien Chinese community, and attracts some international tourists, Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket still lack popularity as cultural destinations. This might be linked to the unclear image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket, as international tourists may still predominantly perceive Phuket as a sun, sea

and sand destination. This raises the question: how can Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket can be promoted as a cultural attraction to international tourists?

The international image associated with Chinese temples in Phuket is that of the intangible cultural event known as the Phuket Vegetarian Festival. The Vegetarian Festival or Nine Emperor Gods Festival is a purification ritual festival that is held on the ninth lunar month (Hamilton, 2003; Cohen, 2001, p.83). The images marketed by Phuket's Chinese temples and the international mass media (NY Daily News, 2015; The Independent, 2014, International Business Times, 2013) of Phuket's Vegetarian Festival are ones of spiritual mediums shockingly piercing parts of their bodies with a vast array of dangerous objects (Phuket Vegetarian Festival, 2015; Maud, 2007). These powerful induced images attracted 258,000 tourists over the nine-day period of the Vegetarian Festival in 2014 (Kasikorn, 2014). All the same, Chinese temples/shrines fail to attract tourists all year round due to the festival's brevity and the underdeveloped image of the temples/shrines. However, the tangible cultural uniqueness of the Chinese temples/shrines may have the potential to be an all year-round cultural tourist attraction. If the Chinese temple/shrine image is managed as well as the Phuket Vegetarian Festival image, Chinese temples/shrines could become a successful cultural attraction in Phuket, thus diversifying the tourism products in Phuket to include cultural tourism along with the established seasonal sun, sea and sand tourism. As a result, this would attract income to the local community directly through Chinese temple/shrine visitations; but before an asset can be developed, an assessment of the image, perception and attraction potential of the visitors needs to be taken. This research aims to provide a valuable insight into that.

1.2 The Importance of Cultural Tourism

In 2013, recreation and leisure travel reported 568 million or 52% of all international tourist arrivals, with the Asia and the Pacific region growing the fastest at 6% (UNWTO, 2014). Richards (2011, 2014) estimated that 430 million international cultural trips were taken in 2013 and indicates the link between the increase in cultural tourism products and their consumption (OECD, 2009). Similarly, in 2013 China welcomed over 10 million foreign sightseeing and leisure tourists (China National Tourism Administration, 2013) out of which 4.5 million international tourists visited Beijing tourist attractions (Beijing Market Profile, 2014).

One of the most renowned Chinese temples, the Temple of Heaven (2016) in Tiantan Park, Beijing, is an example of a successful all year-round cultural heritage site (UNESCO, 2015a) that

preserves its cultural and tradition while managing its site capacity of 100,000 visitors per day through ticket sales (Beijing Temple of Heaven, 2015). However, environmental concerns remain (Li, Wu, & Cai, 2008). Its unique cultural image attracts tens of thousands of tourists on a daily basis and is regarded as one of the main sightseeing spots when visiting Beijing (TripAdvisor, 2015c; Beijing Parks, 2014). The Temple of Heaven, with its unique temple shape and identity, has been well publicised through its own website, destination management organisations, tour operators and local businesses. A study exploring the cultural image factors across 168 hotel websites in Beijing found that the Temple of Heaven was one of the best-represented images (Law & Chen, 2012) of Chinese culture, which added the perception of Chinese temples to international tourists' minds. Furthermore, the creative marketing positioning of the image, showing the shape of the Temple of Heaven, as an award at the ceremony of the fifth Beijing International Film Festival (2015) in Beijing is another example of the power of image association and a well-managed brand identity to attract future tourists (Qu, Kim, & Im, 2011). This successful cultural tourism product contributed to Beijing's US\$4.8 billion tourism industry (Beijing Market Profile, 2014) through its image, which has made it an important cultural attraction.

Chinese temples in Phuket also have the potential to join the cultural tourism market share, as they possess many unique cultural aspects (Sánchez-Rivero & Pulido-Fernández, 2011). This would be beneficial to Phuket's tourism industry, as it would develop an all year-round attraction in addition to the sun, sea and sand tourism (Tomljenovic & Kunst, 2014). Developing the Chinese temples/shrines image would add a new dimension to Phuket's overall destination image and attract new market segments of cultural travellers to Phuket. Chinese temples/shrines are important cultural tourism points (Henkel, Henkel, Agrusa, Agrusa, & Tanner, 2006) that have the potential to enhance cultural understanding (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002), tourist numbers and revenue for local businesses in Phuket. However, a Thailand tourism report by Business Monitor International (2012) raised concerns over tourism's effect on the environmental and cultural heritage sites (Kesmanee & Charoensri, 1995), and another study identified the cultural tourism management aspect as being an important factor that affects the sustainability and conservation of tourism in Phuket (Sakolnakorn, Naipinit, & Kroeksakul, 2013). Therefore, as a first step, it is necessary to study the effects of Chinese temples/shrines on tourists' perceptions in order to develop a successful destination.

1.3 Destination Image

In the late 1970's Crompton (1979, p.18) described image to be "*the sum of beliefs, ideas and impressions that a person has of a destination*". These images can be formed organically through friends, colleagues, relatives, word of mouth personal travel experience and/or induced through advertising, promotions, celebrity and spokesperson's recommendation, stories, articles and reports about a destination (Sonmez & Sirakaya, 2002; Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972, p.120). Numerous studies thereafter on destination image have strongly suggested that the creation and appeal of a unique destination image have a strong and positive effect on tourists' decisions to visit a destination (Matlovičová & Kolesárová, 2012; Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011; Phakdee-auksorn, 2009; Echtner & Ritchie, 2003; Jenkins, 1999; Chon, 1990; Pearce, 1982; Dann, 1977; Hunt, 1975).

With the emergence of developing economies as major tourist destinations and increasing tourist numbers (UNWTO, 2014), competition has increased among established tourism destinations and the need to further define unique aspects of an image destination has become critical to remain competitive as a tourist destination. Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket as cultural attractions offer one such unique image aspect. However, the image of Chinese temples/shrines from a tourist's perspective remains relatively unknown resulting in irregular visitor numbers to Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket. This was identified in the case of Pud Jor Chinese temple and Jui Tui Shrine in Old Phuket Town, where occasional international tourists visited during the weekdays. Due to the low population size at these sites, a qualitative method is used to gain a rich insight into international tourists' perception of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket.

In addition, a review of the destination image literature also revealed that less than half of studies have used qualitative methods (Pike, 2002). Echtner & Ritchie (2003) have pointed out that qualitative techniques identify more salient attributes and Nghiêm-Phú (2014) stated that "*images perceived by the audiences*" and the "*images created by the destination*" are rarely examined together. Furthermore, most qualitative and quantitative articles only focus on the text-based responses from respondents without examining the visual images aspect (Nghiêm-Phú, 2014; Pike, 2002; Echtner & Ritchie, 2003). Consequently, the application of the word-elicited findings for promotional destination images may be difficult for managers to produce.

Therefore, unlike other destination image studies which have mainly focused on qualitative methods using text only to identify the destination image, this study integrates the use of both text ("*images perceived by the audiences*") and image ("*images created by the destination*") in its methods to

examine the image of Chinese temples in Phuket as cultural heritage assets (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002). The first component uses open-ended questions (Echtner & Ritchie 2003; Jenkins, 1999). The second component uses projective questions (Westwood, 2007; Loevinger, 1976) and examines the functional characteristics and psychological characteristics, the common and unique dimension of an image and attributes and holistic imagery of the destination site (Echtner & Ritchie 2003). The third component uses projective drawing (Riley, 2001) to explore the image from a non-linear (Zweifel & Wezemaël, 2012; Riley, 2001) and culturally inclusive (Bagnoli, 2009) view point, which may reveal the “*images created by the destination*”. After, the three components are triangulated (Fig. 1.1) to increase the reliability and validity of the results (Decrop, 1999; Burns & Lennon, 1993; Jick, 1979; Denzin, 1970; Campbell & Fiske, 1959) and finally examined in a cultural tourism context (Table 2.2) for tourists’ consumption (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002).

The academic benefit of this technique allows both text and image data sets to be assimilated so researchers may consider the visual aspect of a destination’s image with enhanced reliability and validity of their findings. This is method also endeavours to expands the current body of knowledge on the assessment of destination image. The additional advantage of this tool is its practical application for destination image organisers as it is more intuitive to understand the nature of image in a visual way. Therefore, creating marketing imagery for attractions is easier, with the added benefit of identifying specific social and cultural differences among tourists.

Figure 1.1 Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image.

Lastly, 42 studies on Chinese (Taoist/Daoist) temples/shrines from 1898 to 2015 examined aspects of the Chinese temple/shrine (Table 9.1.1), but very few examined the image of the Chinese temple. Similarly, there are a minimum of twenty-nine studies examining temple tourism based on other religious temples and shrines (Table 9.1.2), thus exposing the examination of temple image as a largely unexplored field. Therefore, this study aims to fill the tourism literature gap by investigating the image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using a unique combination of open-ended questions, projective questions and projective drawing.

1.4 Research Aims & Objectives

1.4.1 Research Aim.

To investigate the image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket based on the perspective of international tourists.

1.4.2 Research Question.

What are the perceived images of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket held by international tourists?

1.4.3 Research Objectives

1. To explore the image of Chinese temple as a visitor's attraction in Phuket.
2. To identify the uniqueness of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket.
3. To compare the perception of Asian and European tourists.

1.5 Research Benefits

This study will expand the existing body of knowledge about destination image analysis and provide a practical method for promoting a destination such as Chinese temples and shrines as cultural attractions. The academic contribution of this research is its unique method, triangulating the combination of open-ended questions, projective questions and projective drawings methods to provide insight into the tangible and intangible images that international tourists hold. Furthermore, this method specifically identifies the tangible images for promotion that are linked to intangible feelings caused by the destination's image that are captured by projective drawings. This technique supersedes the word-based-only studies that are incapable of connecting a definite image to a particular feeling. In addition, the visual interpretation of the same intangible word can differ among cultures. Therefore, the use of drawing by respondents can remove language and cultural barriers during the research and implementation processes. Moreover, the advantage of using the triangulation method in this study is that the reliability and validity of the findings are increased.

The practical application of this study will allow the Chinese temple/shrine managers to define their temple and shrine image and uniqueness when developing marketing campaigns and turn their cultural asset into an all year-round cultural tourist attraction. Other cultural and heritage sites around the world may benefit in a similar way from these findings.

Destination management organisations will be able to identify market segments that are attracted to Chinese temples/shrines and use the findings to develop marketing strategies and cultural tourism products to attract international tourists all year round.

Other researchers can build upon this study and explore other factors not mentioned in the study to gain an overall understanding of the effect of Chinese temples/shrines on the world.

1.6 Scope of the Research

This research explores the image of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket as cultural tourism attractions through the perspective international tourists visiting Chinese temples and shrines.

1.6.1 Scope of Time

This research was conducted during 3rd of October to 13th November 2015.

1.6.2 Scope of Demographics

The population are international tourists who are 18 years old or over, on holiday for less than 12 months and had just left a Chinese Temple in Phuket.

1.6.3 Scope of Geographical Locations

Interviews with open-ended questions, projective questions and drawing at Bang Neow, Hok Nguan Kung, Jui Tui, Kathu, Pud Jor, Saphan Hin and Serene Light Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket.

1.7 Definition of Terms

Chinese (Taoist/Daoist) temple(s) or shrine(s) in Phuket, Thailand in this study is defined as a place of worship that is operated either by the local community or active monks living on the premises.

International tourists (including overnight visitors) are those tourists who travel to a country other than that in which they have their usual residence, but outside their usual environment, for a period not exceeding 12 months and whose main purpose in visiting is other than an activity remunerated from within the country visited (The World Bank, 2015).

Cultural tourism is “*the movement of persons to cultural attractions away from their normal place of residence, with the intention to gather new information and experiences to satisfy their cultural needs*” (Richards, 1996, p. 24).

Cultural Attractions facilitate a tourist’s experience of the different ways of life of local people through the physical environment which may be natural or man-made, culturally tangible or intangible and permanent or temporary in their nature. These may include natural landscapes, architectural sites, museums, cultural festivals and ethnic events, memories connected to historical persons, permanent spiritual or religious sites or live performance theatre (Csapó, 2012; Ivanovic, 2008; ICOMOS, 2004).

Destination images are images received by a (potential) tourist or visitor before, during and/or after a trip, through an organic, induced and/or modified process, which leads to the overall creation of an image that contains a collection of both positive and negative images, feelings, perceptions, beliefs, opinions, stories and experiences of a destination (Nghiem-Phú 2014; San Martin, & Rodríguez del Bosque, 2008; Tasci, Gartner, & Cavusgil 2007; Echtner & Ritchie, 2003; Sonmez & Sirakaya, 2002; Tapachai & Waryszak, 2000; Pearce, 1988, p.162; Gartner, 1993; Parenteau 1995; Fakeye & Crompton, 1991; Gunn, 1988; Gartner & Hunt, 1987; Dichter, 1985; Crompton, 1979; Hunt, 1975).

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter reviews the previous body of knowledge on cultural tourism in Thailand, Chinese Taoist/Daoist temples in Phuket as tourist attractions, destination image within cultural tourism, cultural perceptions of tourists, the influence of tourism destination image on destination selection, the definition of destination image, destination image formation, the components of destination image, measuring image destination, projective tests, projective questions, projective drawing, drawing analysis, drawing in colour, thematic and content analysis and triangulation methods.

2.1 Cultural Tourism in Thailand

Thailand's destination image campaign "*Amazing Thailand*" started in 1998, promoting mostly sun, sea and sand tourism and evolved at the beginning of 2015 with the "*Discover Thainess*" (2015) campaign, promoting unique aspects of Thai culture. The seven unique Thai cultural products being promoted on the Tourism Authority of Thailand's (TAT) Discover Thainess (2015) website are Thai Fun, Thai Festivals, Thai Food, Thai Way of Life, Thai Wellness, Thai Arts and Thai Wisdom. However, very few Chinese temples or shrines are being promoted (Art Culture Heritage, 2015; Places of Worship, 2015; Chao Por Fah Moong Muang Shrine, 2015). Yet the Vegetarian Festival in Phuket is promoted on the TAT website (TAT Phuket Vegetarian Festival, 2015). This could be seen as an effort on the part of the Tourism Authority of Thailand to increase mass tourism and revenue through the unique image of the Vegetarian Festival in Phuket rather than to preserve and promote local culture or Chinese temples (Kaosa-Ard, 1994). Nevertheless, the Tourism Authority of Thailand has identified the need to differentiate Thailand's destination image through its cultural tourism products in light of the growing competitiveness of tourism destination choices in Southeast Asian countries and other parts of the world.

2.2 Chinese Taoist/Daoist Temples in Phuket as Tourist Attractions

2.2.1 Taoist/Daoist Philosophy

In the 6th Century BC China, Lao Tzu, the father of Taoism or Daoism defined the philosophical aspect of Taoism as seeking inner reflection, self-development, being a virtuous person and spiritual union with nature while in pursuit of simplicity (Chinese Taoist Architecture, 2015; Oxford Dictionaries, 2015). The Tao is referred to as the "*The Way*" which is the universal principle, cosmic energy or life force that all things manifest from and are guided by including gods, deities and spirits. However, the Tao is not a God and not worshipped within Taoist/Daoist temples (BBC, 2015). Taoist/Daoist temple architecture has

integrated many of Lao Tzu's ideas and thoughts including the functions of mediation, reading and chanting of scriptures, Feng Shui and fortune telling.

2.2.2 Taoist/Daoist temples

For hundreds of years Chinese Taoist/Daoist temples around the world have been renowned for their unique image, architecture, culture and festivals. UNESCO (2015a) describes the ancient temple and palace complex of the Wudang Mountains in Hubei, China as representing the highest degree in Chinese culture and having a tremendous influence on the advancement of religious, architectural and cultural development in China for over a thousand years. Similarly, the Temple of Heaven in Beijing, China symbolizes the spiritual connection between earth and heaven where sacrificial ceremonies were conducted by Chinese emperors to signify this relationship of hierarchy (Li, 2010; Yao, 2005), which is also reflected through the architecture and landscape planning of the temple (UNESCO, 2015b), and social order (Overmyer 2009; Chan, 1989). The migration of Chinese workers has seen their ideology, culture, art, food, and temples spread far and wide across the world over hundreds of years.

2.2.3 Taoist/Daoist temples in Phuket

The Chinese came to Phuket, Thailand in the early 16th century, and established strategic trade routes for sea merchants to trade commodities (Phuket Provincial, 2015; Nasution, 2005). Tin was an important commodity in Phuket that was traded with the Dutch, English, French and Portuguese. As the demand for tin grew so did the demand for labour and an influx of Southern Chinese migrants from Fujian (Hokkien), Guangdong and Hainan came to Phuket in the early 19th century (History Tin and Colonization, 2014; Early Portuguese forays into Siam, 2013; TripAdvisor Phuket History, 2013; Maud, 2007; Nasution, 2005). Shortly after that period, the Hokkien Chinese assimilated into Thai culture and gained social influence in the Old Phuket Town area, where they established their cultural identity by building Chinese temples and shrines and performing their ritual Vegetarian Festival (Chinese Temples in Phuket, 2016; History of Phuket, 2015; Phuket Vegetarian Festival History, 2015; Phuket Wats and Temples, 2015; Thai-Malaysian legacy, 2013; Hamilton, 2003).

There are 15 major Chinese (Taoist/Daoist) temples and shrines in Phuket that are of religious and cultural importance. These can be seen in Table 2.1.

First is Kathu Shrine, which was founded in approximately 1825 (Shrines in Phuket, 2015) and is located in Kathu district. It is acknowledged as the original home of the Phuket's Vegetarian Festival

(Shrines in Phuket, 2015) and houses Tean Hu Huan Soy the God of Performing Artists and Dancers who are the patrons of the Chinese opera.

Second, the Shrine of the Serene Light was built by a local Chinese family in 1889 (Shrines in Phuket, 2015) in the Old Phuket Town area and contains the deity Tan Sheng Ong - Chen Sage.

Third, Jao Mae Kuan Im Shrine was constructed in 1891 in Old Phuket Town and houses Kuan Im/Guanyin/Kannon. The Goddess of Mercy is the most important ritual object (Shrines in Phuket, 2015).

Fourth, Ban Tha Rue Shrine was erected in Thalang district and is known as the fourth-oldest shrine in Phuket that holds the Kuan Im/Guanyin/Kannon the Goddess of Mercy (Shrines in Phuket, 2015) and God of Medicine Bo Seng Tai Tae.

Fifth, Cherng Thalay Shrine was established around 1901 in the Cherng Thalay area. Mr Ju Pai Tuk, a hairdresser, set up the shrine (Shrines in Phuket, 2015) which houses the Sam Ong Hu or Sam Hu Ong Ia and are known as the Three House Princes.

Sixth, Bang Neow Shrine was assembled in the year 1904 in Old Phuket Town after being relocated few times because of fires and is home to the deity Tean Hu Huan Suay.

Seventh, Pud Jor Chinese Temple was built around 1908 (Shrines in Phuket, 2015) Old Phuket Town and is an old Chinese temple in Phuket which accommodates Kuan Im/Guanyin/Kannon the Goddess of Mercy.

Eighth, Jui Tui Shrine was founded approximately 1911 (Shrines in Phuket, 2015) in Old Phuket Town and plays an important part in the Phuket Vegetarian Festival. Jui Tui Shrine also is home to the Tean Hu Huan Soy the God of Performing Artists and Dancers who are the patrons of the Chinese opera.

Ninth, Sapam Shrine was set up by Chinese migrants from Fujian in Sapam Village (Shrines in Phuket, 2015) sometime in 1915 with the deity of Guan Yu which is the symbol of righteousness and loyalty.

Tenth, Hok Nguan Keng Shrine is located in Old Phuket Town and was formed in 1930 approximately (Shrines in Phuket, 2015). Ju Su Kong was a famous Chinese monk born 800 years ago and is the most important ritual object at Hok Nguan Keng Shrine.

Eleventh, Sui Boon Tong Shrine was built by a group called Entranced Horses mediums in the 1980's (Shrines in Phuket, 2015) in the Old Phuket Town area and is home to Budai the deity of wealth and prosperity.

Twelfth, Boon Kaw Kong Shrine was built in 1980 on Patong Hill and is well known among locals for granting wishes (Shrines in Phuket, 2015). The main deity at Boon Kaw Kong Shrine is Hok Tek Jia Sin/Pun Tao Gong.

Thirteenth, Kiew Tien Keng Shrine, otherwise known as Saphan Hin, was constructed in the Saphan Hin Park in the vicinity of Old Phuket Town in 1997 and houses the deity Kiw Tian Eian Lu. The shrine is located next to the beach which is the departing point back to heaven by boat for all the Vegetarian Festival gods and deities on the final day (Shrines in Phuket, 2015).

Fourteenth, Samkong Shrine is privately owned and located in Old Phuket Town and its construction is unknown (Shrines in Phuket, 2015). However, it is known for healing and good health. Lim Hu Tai Su a (human) deity that once worked in the Imperial Palace in China is housed at Samkong Shrine.

Fifteenth, Yok Ke Keng Shrine is situated in Old Phuket Town and is home to the deity Jow Su Gong/Cheng Jui Jow Su Gong.

Two of the most important Chinese temples are Pud Jor and Jui Tui temples in Phuket Town, which are owned and operated privately by members of the local Chinese community and have no monks or nuns living in the temples. The author's interviews revealed that Chinese temples like Pud Jor and Jui Tui as cultural assets remain disconnected from tour operators and businesses in the local area. It was also discovered that the tourists' nationalities who visited the sites Pud Jor and Jui Tui temples were Chinese, Russian and Europeans. These nationalities visited Pud Jor and Jui Tui temples mainly on weekends by coach tours and spent on average 10 to 30 minutes at the site, with some tour groups engaging in controlled games conducted by the local tour guide.

The Pud Jor temple manager observed a difference in behaviour between Asians who prayed and westerners who took photos at the Chinese temple and the Jui Tui temple manager described the temple as a "*cultural tourism point*". The author points out that the self-realisation of the Chinese temple as a cultural tourism point is significant as Chinese temples in Phuket may be looking to form an alternative image to that created by the Vegetarian Festival in Phuket.

In summary, Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket have a long and memorable history that is worth promoting as a destination image within a cultural tourism context.

Table 2.1 The major Chinese (Taoist/Daoist) temples and shrines in Phuket.

Temple	Founded	Location	History or Importance	Main God/Deity/Spirit
1. Kathu Shrine	1825*	Kathu	Original home of the Phuket Vegetarian Festival.	Tean Hu Huan Soy - God of Performing artists and Dancers (patron of the Chinese opera)
2. Shrine of the Serene Light	1889	Old Phuket Town	Built by a local Chinese family.	Tan Sheng Ong - Chen Sage
3. Jao Mae Kuan Im Shrine	1891	Old Phuket Town	Kuan Im is the most important ritual object.	Kuan Im / Guanyin / Kannon - the Goddess of Mercy
4. Ban Tha Rue Shrine	Unknown	Thalang	The fourth-oldest shrine in Phuket.	Kuan Im / Guanyin / Kannon the Goddess of Mercy and Bo Seng Tai Tae God of medicine
5. Cherng Thalay Shrine	1901*	Cherng Thalay	Around 1901, Mr Ju Pai Tuk, a hairdresser set up the shrine.	Sam Ong Hu or Sam Hu Ong Ia - Three House Princes
6. Bang Neow Shrine	1904	Old Phuket Town	Relocated few times because of fires.	Tean Hu Huan Suay
7. Pud Jor Chinese Temple	1908*	Old Phuket Town	Known as old Chinese temple in Phuket.	Kuan Im / Guanyin / Kannon - the Goddess of Mercy
8. Jui Tui Shrine	1911*	Old Phuket Town	Plays an important part in the Phuket Vegetarian Festival.	Tean Hu Huan Soy - God of Performing artists and Dancers (patron of the Chinese opera)
9. Sapam Shrine	1915*	Sapam Village	Built by Chinese migrants from Fujian.	Guan Yu - symbol of righteousness and loyalty
10. Hok Nguan Keng Shrine	1930*	Old Phuket Town	Ju Su Kong is the most important ritual object.	Ju Su Kong – Famous Chinese Monk born 800 years ago
11. Sui Boon Tong Shrine	1980*	Old Phuket Town	Founded by a group called Entranced Horses mediums.	Budai - wealth and prosperity
12. Boon Kaw Kong Shrine	1980	Patong Hill	Known for granting wishes.	Hok Tek Jia Sin / Pun Tao Gong

13. Kiew Tien Keng Shrine (Saphan Hin)	1997	Old Phuket Town	The shrine is located next to the beach which is the departing point back to heaven by boat for all the Vegetarian Festival gods and deities on the final day.	Kiw Tian Eian Lu
14. Samkong Shrine	Unknown	Old Phuket Town	Privately owned. Known for healing and good health.	A (human) deity that once worked in the Imperial Palace in China. Lim Hu Tai Su
15. Yok Ke Keng Shrine	Unknown	Old Phuket Town	Unknown.	Jow Su Gong/Cheng Jui Jow Su Gong

Notes: * Approximate date

Source: Shrines in Phuket (2015); Cultural specialists, (2015).

2.3 Destination Image within Cultural Tourism

McKercher & Du Cros (2002) stated; “*Cultural tourism is first and foremost a tourism activity in which a destination’s cultural heritage assets are presented for the consumption of tourists*” and defined cultural tourism as being comprised of four elements (Table 2.2):

Table 2.2 Cultural Tourism Definition. The four elements that comprise cultural tourism.

Cultural Tourism Elements	Definition Key Points
Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Firstly, the asset should be based on commercial tourism reasons. - Secondly, the asset should be based on cultural heritage management. - The asset must attract non-local visitors or tourists. - The management understanding the tourist needs and limitations. - Tourists travelling for pleasure. - Tourists limited by time. - Tourists know very little about the importance of the site. - The asset must be developed with the visitors or tourists in mind.
Use of Cultural Heritage Assets.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The asset contains tangible and intangible aspects. - The asset has intrinsic values for the community. - The asset has extrinsic values for the tourists. - The management understanding the benefits sought by all stakeholders. - The management managing tourism and cultural heritage interests.
Consumption of Experience and Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The tourists desire to consume a range of cultural experiences. - The transformation of an asset using sustainable development and practices. - Definition distinctions. - Cultural or heritage asset as being uncommodified for its intrinsic values. - Cultural or heritage product as being transformed and/or commodified for tourism.
The Tourist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The tourist motivations. (See Fig. 9.2.1 in the appendix) - Serendipitous cultural tourist. - Purposeful cultural tourist. - Incidental cultural tourist. - Casual cultural tourist. - Sightseeing cultural tourist. - The information style, quality and accuracy received by the tourists before they visit will affect their expectations and behaviour when they visit the asset. - The information gatekeepers form more of an impression in shaping the tourist expectations before the experience than the asset itself.

Source: McKercher and Du Cros, (2002).

McKercher and Du Cros (2002) definition of cultural tourism gives some insight into the image dimensions that exist, such as reasons, values and benefits for travelling to a cultural site, the feelings and experiences associated with it, information sources of influence and tourists' needs and limitations.

Ramkissoon, Uysal and Brown's (2011) study on the relationship between destination image and behavioural intentions of tourists to consume cultural attractions, revealed several important destination image factors; learning about the local customs, different cultures at one destination, cultural attractiveness, and interesting cultural activities (PATA, 2010) were the main influences on tourists' cultural behavioural intentions. In addition, cultural attractions with a favourable image would lead to increased cultural behavioural intentions, with a positive image destination that may lead to revisits and enthusiasm to recommend (Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011). Moreover, Sánchez-Rivero and Pulido-Fernández's (2011) investigation found that cultural tourists were likely to appraise positively aspects such as hygiene and serenity, but were very disgruntled with the cost to quality ratio when compared to non-cultural tourists. Generally, cultural tourists seek to take full advantage of their experience and expect to receive the best service at the lowest price (Sánchez-Rivero & Pulido-Fernández, 2011). However, Gilbert and Lizotte's (1998) cultural tourism research suggests that cultural tourists are perceived as superior travellers and thus benefit from the cultural tourist's raised self-image among other travellers, friends and family.

2.4 Tourists' Cultural Perceptions

There is much debate about regional categorisation in anthropology (Bolnick, 2008) and economics (Schnore, 1961). However, a recent cross-cultural study analysing the perceptions of tourists from the USA, Russia, Japan, and China (An, 2014) found that Russian and Chinese attitudes were affected by the convenience of travel, but American attitudes were influenced by cost rather than convenience. Nisbett and Miyamoto (2005) investigated the effect of culture on perception, where it was found that Westerners were context-independent and used a perceptual analytic method that focused on the important object separately from its context, while Asians were context-dependent and used a perceptual holistic method by making relationships between the object and the context in which the object was located. Furthermore Matzler, Strobl, Stokburger-Sauer, Bobovnick and Bauer's (2016) research on "*brand personality and culture: The role of cultural differences on the impact of brand personality perceptions on tourists' visit intentions*" reported that the human personality dimension of activity (level of extroversion) had a fully mediating effect on visiting attentions whereas the dimensions of responsibility (level of conscientiousness), emotionality (level of emotional stability) and simplicity (level of openness) had a partially mediating effect. They suggested these indirect effects had more significance than the direct effects on a tourist's personal characteristics and influenced their intention to visit (Matzler,

Strobl, Stokburger-Sauer, Bobovnický, & Bauer, 2016; Verwiebe, 2011). Matzler, Strobl, Stokburger-Sauer, Bobovnický and Bauer (2016) concluded that grouping customer segments with similar cultural dimensions would clarify the understanding between a tourist's characteristics and a brand's identity, leading managers to develop a more meaningful, congruent brand personality strategy (Sonnleitner, 2011). Therefore, the author concluded from the literature that grouping nationalities by their cultural similarities within geographical proximity would provide information about the tourist's image visiting Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket.

2.5 Definition of Destination Image

The Cambridge English online dictionary (2015) defines "*destination; (as) the place where someone is going or where something is being sent or taken*". This can be understood as meaning a country, a state, a province, a city, a town or a specific location.

An image can be defined as any picture, text, moving image, or spoken word that refers to a specific destination and the physical or emotional experience of going to, being at and returning from a specific destination (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003; Sonmez & Sirakaya, 2002; Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1988), which may be favourable or unfavourable (Parenteau, 1995).

The author's definition of destination image: an image received by a potential tourist or visitor, before, during and/or after a trip, through an organic, induced and/or modified process, which leads to the overall creation of an image that contains a collection of both positive and negative images, feelings, perceptions, beliefs, opinions, stories and experiences of a destination (Nghiem-Phú 2014; San Martín & Rodríguez del Bosque, 2008; Tasci, Gartner, & Cavusgil 2007; Echtner & Ritchie, 2003; Sonmez & Sirakaya, 2002; Tapachai & Waryszak, 2000; Pearce, 1988, p.162; Gartner, 1993; Parenteau 1995; Fakeye & Crompton, 1991; Gunn, 1988; Gartner & Hunt, 1987; Dichter, 1985; Crompton, 1979; Hunt, 1975). The summation of these images may possibly lead to the continual development of knowledge, meaning, opinions and feelings that might sway a tourist's decision, behaviour and satisfaction level with regards to a destination (Pearce, 1988).

2.6 Destination Selection: The Influence of Tourism Destination Image

The global tourism industry has seen rapid growth of tourism products and new destinations over the last few decades, which has led to challenging marketing conditions for the local businesses and destination marketers in developing a unique, appealing and effective image to position and promote their

destinations. Recently, destination image has received much attention in the tourism sector, specifically in the areas of cultural and heritage tourism (Iazzi, Rosato, & Gravili, 2015; Sánchez-Rivero & Pulido-Fernández, 2011; Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009; Li, Wu, & Cai, 2008), spiritual tourism (Mann & Thapar, 2015; Kaplan, 2010; Fleischer, 2000), and sustainable tourism (UNEP, 2013).

The tourism destination image is recognised as one of the key factors in promoting and advertising a successful tourist destination. Some studies have demonstrated that the destination image has strong influence on the promotion and positioning of a tourist destination (Li, 2012; Prayag, 2007a; Tasci & Gartner, 2007). Similarly, several studies have agreed that the tourism destination image has a considerable impact in the image formation of a potential tourist's perception, destination selection, travel behaviour, travel experience and tourist satisfaction (Remoaldo, Ribeiro, Vareiro, Santos, 2014; Li, 2012; Chen, Chen, & Lee, 2010; Prebensen, 2007; Sirakaya & Woodside, 2005; Pike & Ryan, 2004; Echtner & Ritchie, 2003; Baloglu & McCleary, 1999; Jenkins, 1999; Dann, 1996; Gartner, 1993; Chon, 1990; Reilly, 1990; Stabler 1988; Gunn, 1988; Kotler, 1987), with the scale of destination image studies ranging from country, state or province, to city and local levels (Nghiem-Phú 2014; Pike, 2002). However, most destination image studies are focused at the country level using quantitative analysis methods (Gallarza, Saura, & Garcia, 2002; Pike, 2002). Nevertheless, tourism destination image studies have contributed to the greater understanding of the psychological functions and processes involved in image construction, thus aiding the tourism industry in the image management and promotion of tourist destinations.

2.7 Destination Image Formation

Reynolds (1965, p.69) classified the configuration process of destination image as an assembly of mental images that is based on numerous impressions selected from an avalanche of information about a certain destination. Since then, researchers have gone on to identify destination image as a combination of images that generate an impression about a specific destination (Table 2.3).

Table 2.3 Definitions of Destination Images from 1975 – 2014.

Author & Year	Definition of Image
Hunt (1975)	Images held by prospective tourist about a place.
Crompton (1979)	The sum of beliefs about a destination.
Gartner and Hunt (1987)	Images that a person holds outside of where they live.
Reilly (1990)	Not separated qualities, but a whole image.
Milman and Pizam (1995)	A sum of individual elements or images that create the tourism experience.
Tapachai and Waryszak (2000)	Images formed by tourists with regards to the expected advantage or values.
Faullant, Matzler and Füller (2008)	A structure containing cognitive and affective images.
Huang, Li and Cai (2010)	A psychological organization integrating images and values tourists project onto a destination.

Gunn's (1972, p.120) theoretical model of the seven phase model of travel experiences highlights the image formation process of the destination image. Gartner (1993) further developed the understanding of destination image by characterising "*image forming agents*" and their influence on image formation on an individual's awareness about a destination. The combined models describe the process of destination image formation (Fig. 2.1), which starts through the organic accumulation of autonomous images from the news, documentaries, movies, including unsought information from friends and relatives of a destination site. These can happen through a tourist's life experiences. Next, the induced stage starts once a decision is made to travel to a destination and the alteration of the destination image begins with the search for additional information overtly and/or covertly that may include organically induced image sources such as traditional forms of marketing, travel mediators, celebrity recommendations, stories, articles, reports, information from friends and relatives or word of mouth. This process continues when the decision to travel is acted upon until the tourist travels to the destination. Finally, the tourist moves into the modified induced stage where the experience and involvement at the destination to the time that they return home alters their image of a destination in a differentiated, complicated, and realistic way (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003).

It is noted that other aspects influence the image construction; these are the information acquired from destinations, the characteristics of the individual as well as the information from independent sources (Tasci, 2007; Beerli & Martin, 2004; McKercher & Du Cros, 2002).

Gartner (1993, p.193) also suggested that destination images are fashioned into three noticeably different but interconnected components: cognitive, affective and conative. The cognitive images are related to known characteristic of a destination; whereas affective images are linked to the emotions that

are associated to the individual's intentions in selecting a destination; and conative images are deemed comparable to behaviour and develop from both cognitive and affective images from a destination (Gartner, 1993).

Figure 2.1 Gunn's (1972, p.120) Seven phase model of travel experience and Gartner (1993) Image forming agents.

Gunn, (1972)	Gartner, (1993)
<p>Organic Image</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accumulation of images of a destination site through life experiences. 	<p>Cognitive Image</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Autonomous information from news, documentaries and movies. - Unsought organic information from relatives or friends.
<p>Induced Image</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Alteration of those images by additional research. - Decision to travel to the destination. - Travelling to the destination. 	<p>Affective Image</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organically induced information from friends, relatives, word of mouth. - Overtly induced through traditional forms of marketing. - Overtly induced information gathered from travel mediators. - Covertly induced recommendations from celebrities. - Covertly induced destination stories, articles and reports.
<p>Modified Induced Image</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience and involvement at the destination. - Returning back from the destination. - Alteration of the destination image from the authentic experience. 	<p>Conative Image</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organic experience through personal interaction and travel.

2.8. The Components of Destination Image

Echtner and Ritchie's (2003) three-dimensional model of the components of destination image (Fig. 2.2) captures and the essential cognitive, affective and conative components that describe the functional characteristics, psychological characteristics, attributes, holistic image, common and unique features of destination. This defines not only the perception of a destination's attributes but also the holistic image made by a destination. In addition, destination images can be ordered along the diagonal axis ranging from common characteristics used to assess all destinations to those that are unique to individual destinations. Gallarza, Saura and Garcia's (2002) comparison of the most common attributes used in tourism destinations studies demonstrates that Echtner and Ritchie's (2003) conceptual model has greatest coverage of functional and psychological characteristics when measuring image.

The components of the model and how it is used in quantitative and qualitative research can be explained thus: the upper hemisphere contains the functional characteristics that are tangible aspects of a destination's image and the lower hemisphere contains the psychological characteristics that are intangible aspects of a destination's image. On the left side are the functional attributes (weather and incense sticks) and psychological attributes (people and location) of a destination's image. On the right side are the functional holistic images that show the physical or quantifiable characteristics, such as a mental image (layout and activities) and the psychological holistic images that describe the general feeling or mood (peaceful or happy) of a destination. The common image is the impression of central qualities by which all destinations are commonly assessed (such as the smell of incense sticks) and the unique image is a destination that has a special atmosphere or mood (peaceful and intriguing). For example, the Vatican, which has an exclusive location that is linked to a set of ideals (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003), could be considered a peaceful and intriguing destination and therefore unique.

Figure 2.2 Echtner and Ritchie (2003). The Components of Destination Image. Modified examples.

COMMON Impressions of central qualities in which all destinations that are commonly assessed. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hot weather • Smell of incense 	FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS Tangible aspects. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hot • Smell 	FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS Tangible aspects. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temple • Space 	
FUNCTIONAL ATTRIBUTES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weather • Incense sticks 			FUNCTIONAL HOLISTIC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Layout • Activities
PSYCHOLOGICAL ATTRIBUTES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People • Location 	PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS Intangible aspects. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Friendly • Safe 		PSYCHOLOGICAL HOLISTIC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peaceful • Happy
PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS Intangible aspects. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Friendly • Safe 		PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS Intangible aspects. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mysterious • Intriguing 	UNIQUE The destination has a special atmosphere. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The (destination) is peaceful and intriguing.

2.9 Measuring Destination Image

Past studies have shown there to be two main techniques for measuring image using Echtner and Ritchie’s (2003) components of destination image model, these being structured and unstructured methods (Table 2.4).

Structured methodological studies have mostly used a pre-determined list of attributes forcing respondents to consider an image in terms of the attributes created by the authors. These attributes have usually been used on semantic differentials and/or Likert scales for measuring cognitive and affective components of the destination image (Baloglu & McCleary, 1999; Echtner & Ritchie, 1993; Gartner & Hunt, 1987; Crompton, 1979). The advantages of a structured approach are: they are simpler to administer and code; the results are quantifiable; and sophisticated statistical methods can be used easily to make comparisons between other destinations. However, they do not incorporate aspects of the

holistic imagery and therefore are attribute-focused, leading the respondents to think about the specific attributes of a destination image and possibly missing important dimensions of the image (Jenkins, 1999).

Unstructured methods allow the respondents to describe the important impressions of a destination's image without restraint, using approaches such as focus groups, open-ended questions, projective questions, content analysis and repertory grid. Then the organisation and labelling procedures are used to determine the attributes of the "*image dimensions*". The advantages are that the holistic image of a destination can be measured (Gallarza, Saura, & Garcia, 2002); the author bias can be reduced (Hsu & Huang, 2008); and the probability of absent image dimensions is significantly reduced. On the other hand, the information presented by respondents may vary greatly, with limited statistical analyses and the inability to make destination comparisons (Echtner & Ritchie, 1993, 1991).

More recent research studies by Rittichainuwat and Rattanaphinanchai (2015), Greaves and Skinner (2010), Dimitrios, Matina and Konstantinos, (2008), Cave, Ryan and Panakera (2003) and Choi, Chan and Wu (1999) have used mixed method approaches (Echtner & Ritchie 1991, 1993) by initially conducting a qualitative analysis to identify the important attributes, then integrating those attributes in quantitative surveys to conduct more sophisticated analyses of comparisons and relationships (Jenkins, 1999). As this is becoming the norm in the field of destination image research, the integration of a two-step process allows future research and statistical validation of the qualitative results as demonstrated by Echtner and Ritchie (2003). Still, a small amount of studies use qualitative analysis methods as the primary technique (Gallarza, Saura, & Garcia, 2002; Dann, 1996; Reilly, 1990) in unexplored fields, providing rich literature and new insights which leads to further empirical research.

In summary, McKercher and Du Cros' (2002) cultural tourism framework (Table 2.2) covers the necessary aspects in examining cultural tourism destination image. The importance of regional groupings of tourists for analysis will help destination image managers in promoting Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket. The destination image literature review revealed that using an unstructured approach to Echtner and Ritchie's (2003) Components of Destination Image model (Fig. 2.2) allows for a deeper exploration into the image of a destination.

Table 2.4 Methods used in destination image research: structured versus unstructured methods.

Structured Versus Unstructured Measuring Techniques		
	Structured	Unstructured
Description	- Various common image attributes are specified and incorporated into a standardised instrument and the respondent rates each destination on each of the attributes, resulting in an 'image profile'.	- The respondent is allowed to freely describe his or her impressions of the destination. Data are gathered from a number of respondents. Sorting and categorisation techniques are then used to determine the 'image dimensions'.
Techniques	- Usually a set of semantic differential or Likert type scales.	- Focus groups, open-ended survey questions, content analysis and repertory grid.
Advantages	- Easy to administer. - Simple to code. - Results easy to analyse using sophisticated statistical techniques. - Facilitates comparisons between destinations.	- Conducive to measuring the holistic components of destination image. - Reduces interviewer bias. - Reduces likelihood of missing important image dimensions or components.
Disadvantages	- Does not incorporate holistic aspects of image. - Attribute focused - that is, it forces the respondent to think about the product image in terms of the attributes specified. - The completeness of structured methods can be variable - it is possible to miss dimensions.	- Level of detail provided by respondents is highly variable. - Statistical analyses of the results are limited. - Comparative analyses are not facilitated.

Source: Echtner and Ritchie (1991, 1993).

2.10 Projective Tests

Projective testing is rooted in psychoanalytic psychology and argues that people's conscious and unconscious thoughts are concealed from mindful awareness (Donoghue, 2000). Its hypothesis is that an individual creates known structures or responses based on their conscious or unconscious needs when confronted with an ambiguous situation (Ritchie & Lewis, 2003 p.131). Projective testing through external stimuli brings to mind responses that may disclose features of the interviewee's persona by projection of internal images, attitudes, thoughts, emotions and behaviour patterns (Britannica, 2015; Westwood, 2007; Marnat, 2003a). As an indirect method, projective testing mitigates the temptation to fake, reduces dependence on verbal abilities and assesses both conscious and unconscious qualities. Projective testing techniques include: Rorschach Inkblot Test (Rorschach, 1921); Thematic Apperception Test, which involves looking at a picture and telling a story (Murray & Morgan, 1935); Incomplete Sentences

(Loevinger, 1976); Colour Test (Luscher & Scott, 1969); and Draw-A-Person (Machover, 1949). Scholars agree that the Thematic Apperception Test has more standardised methods of analysis than Draw-A-Person or dream interpretation; however, reliability and validity issues remain in the clinical use of projective techniques involving serious cases (Renata, 2011; Marnat, 2003b; Lilienfeld, Wood, & Garb, 2000; Walker, Hall, & Hurst, 1990). However, the use of projective questions in tourism studies is common and has provided a deeper insight into the inner image of tourists (Prayag, 2007b; Echtner & Ritchie 2003; Reilly, 1990). Nevertheless, the application of projective drawing as a qualitative technique to understand tourists' experiences remains almost unused. Therefore, the use of both projective questions and drawing will be used to assess the destination image.

2.10.1 Projective Questions

Projective questions provide an initial verbal impetus (Westwood, 2007), such as "*The feeling I get at this location is...*", which might disclose cognitive and affective images. The projective questions may include inquiries that investigate a range of sights, sounds, smells, tastes, feelings and experiences of an event or destination. Although the exclusive use of projective questions in unstructured destination images studies has been limited (Prayag, 2007b; Prebensen, 2007) the findings of such studies have been of great value in fields that remain mostly uncharted (Ramsey, Ibbotson, & McCole, 2006), contrasting with quantitative methods that specifically identify prearranged variables (Day, 1989) with an increased rate of obligatory answers. Therefore, the value of determining tourists' perceptions and connotations associated to a particular image (Keller, 1998, p.93) might profit destination managers and promoters when marketing an image of a destination (Cai, 2002) and the potential experience of it.

2.10.2 Projective Drawing

Korstanje's (2010) study into *The Power of Projective Drawings: A New Method for Researching Tourist Experiences* explored the underlying relationships of drawn images and their meanings. The research concluded that drawing is particularly valuable for research requiring the expression of profound feelings and thoughts. Likewise, Carmen-Garcia, Navas and Cuadrado (2003) stated that drawings symbolizes not only the internal emotions and representations but, in addition, how people perceive others (Dean, 2014), as well as the things around them (Morrow, 2001). Drawing as a data collection technique provides an in-depth and non-linear worldview (Zweifel & Wezemaal, 2012), including cross-cultural understanding (Bagnoli, 2009) of the tourist experiences. Therefore, the author argues that a qualitative

method using projective questions, incomplete questions, drawing and self-elicitation can give a deeper insight into images tourists hold which quantitative methods cannot access.

2.10.3 Drawing Analysis

The first systematic model analysing visual artwork was developed by Halliday (1973) and gave a specific variety of choices of functional of language to particular social circumstances. This model was used by O'Toole (1990) and Kress and Leeuwen (1996) effectively but was further developed by Riley (2001) as A Systemic-Functional Semiotic Model of the Domain of Drawing (Fig. 2.4). Riley describes drawn communication as having three main simultaneous functions: Compositional, Interpersonal and Experiential; with varying levels of drawn engagement, such as the drawing as displayed in context, the sub-divisions of the drawing surface, and the combination of drawn and individual drawn marks.

The Compositional choices describe the experiential and the interpersonal aspects into a coherent form through the level of completion, dimensions and perspective, proportions, location on the page, framing devices or cropping, colours, marks, tones, textures and patterns.

The Interpersonal expresses one's attitude or mood regarding one's experience. This positions the receiver or viewer to feel the mood and attitude being expressed through the drawn elements like the view, scale or size, and the pressure of marks, such as soft and hard.

The Experiential conveys some aspect of one's experience of the world through the items or themes drawn, realistic or abstract impressions, calligraphy, the line quality (for example, thick or thin), shadows or light upon surfaces, and the feeling or emotions associated with the image.

As the Systemic-Functional Semiotic Model of the Domain of Drawing is a comprehensive and complex model for drawing analysis, it is beyond the scope of this study to go into such detail. However, the model provides appropriate variables for assessing the drawn images of Chinese temple/shrines by international tourists as the variables are seen in visual communication imagery across all cultures (Bagnoli, 2009; Riley, 2004; Kress, 2001). Therefore, a modified version of Riley's (2001) drawing model (Fig. 3.4) is used to assess the Compositional, Interpersonal and Experiential aspects of the drawn images in this tourism study.

Figure 2.4 Riley (2001). A Systemic-Functional Semiotic Model of the Domain of Drawing

LEVELS OF ENGAGEMENT	FUNCTIONS OF DRAWING		
	COMPOSITIONAL	INTERPERSONAL	EXPERIENTIAL
The drawing as displayed in context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-textuality • Systems of Geometry: persp. orthographic, oblique, inverted persp., & topological • Size and format • Framing devices • Location options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems of modality: Mood, attitude, positioning: viewer-centred, object-centred • Public/Private • Intimate/Monumental 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems of Theme: Physical, emotional, imaginative experiences, narrative, Historical genre • Realistic/Abstract • Interplay between objects, poses, events
Sub-divisions of the drawing's surface	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secondary geometry • Gestalt relationships: horizontal, vertical, diagonal axes • Proportional relationships • Tonal passages (aerial persp.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems of gaze: Eye paths, focus points • Dynamic/Static • Calm/Excited • Balance/Unbalanced 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary geometry • Actions, poses, events, objects • Awareness of distal and proximal perceptual values
Combinations of drawn marks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relative size of marks • Relative orientation of marks • Relative position of marks • Colour, tone and texture contrast – boundaries • Pattern • Rhythm • False attachments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deep/shallow range of depth illusion • Foreground/Background range of positioning • Stability/Instability • Scale • Heavy/light 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distance between surfaces • Edges: occlusion of one surface by another • Direction • Transparency/Opacity of surfaces • Atmospheric conditions • Quality of light • Time of day • Awareness of haptic perceptual values • Weight
A drawn mark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Size relative to picture surface • Orientation relative to picture surface • Position relative to picture surface • Combination of surface texture and drawing medium • Picture-primitives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psychological orientation • Range of textural meanings: wet/dry; hard/soft; matt/gloss • Denotation level of meaning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial depth • Effects of gravity and other forces • Effects of light and water upon material surfaces • Scene primitives
M A T R I X O F S Y S T E M S O F C H O I C E S			

2.10.4 Drawing in Colour

The role of colour has been established as a significant and an influential device in the way of expression, as it operates at many discerning levels which add symbolic, emotional, significance and detail to an image (Moutinho & Durão, 2013; O'Connor, 2011; Burkitt, Barrett, & Davis, 2003; Winston, Kenyon, Stewardson, & Lepine, 1995). The use of colour can call to mind complex associations which are related to memory (Moutinho & Durão, 2013) such as sight, sound, touch, taste and smell and emotions. Moutinho and Durão (2013) go on to say that “drawing is used as a two-way tool: to think and to communicate information” and that colour enhances the quality of information and meaning of the drawing by the marks, impressions and arrangement of the elements of the image depicted. O'Connor (2011) states that colour and behaviour are influenced by mediating variables such as an individual’s character, cultural experiences and affective states. Therefore, use of colour may provide a deeper understanding of the psychological influence of colours and its possible effects on a tourist’s perception when describing Chinese temple/shrines in Phuket.

2.11 Content Analysis

As forms of Grounded Theory, thematic analysis and content analysis are similar coding techniques used for recognising, analysing, exposing and quantifying, in the case of content analysis (Vaismoradi, Turunen, & Bondas, 2013), patterns or themes within information such as written historical accounts, conversations with individuals, group conversations, face-to-face interviews, surveys, biographies, news reports, television broadcasts, photography, paintings, drawings and sculptures (Onwuegbuzie, Leech, & Collins, 2012; Scott, 2009; Kuhn, 2003; Morgan, 2002; Strauss & Corbin, 1994; Murray, 1943). Thematic analysis has been widely used in studies ranging from wildlife tourism (Cong, Wu, Morrison, A. Shu, & Wang, 2014), 'push' and 'pull' factors of a tourist destination (Prayag & Ryan, 2011), learning online (Scott, 2007), management (Holton, 2007), drawing children's wishes (Kuhn, 2003), hospitality management (Blum, 1997), culture (Goodwin, Yakubik, Gendel, & Franks, 1986) and dying (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) to observe the ways in which a respondent experience events to form meaning. Boyatzis (1998) described thematic analysis as going deeper to understand a variety of aspects of the study topic. Figure 2.5 shows how a participant's actual words can be used to create coded analytical structures to establish the associations among levels of neural systems (Cave, Ryan, & Panakera, 2003; Pattie, & Snyder 1996) and how the same words can be developed into categories or themes (Saldana, 2009). For content analysis, the frequency of the themes can then be statistically analysed to identify their significance. These are then developed into abstract theories.

Although there are no solid rules in coding data units, category formation, percentage requirements in forming a categories or theories, Braun and Clarke (2006), in their study *Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology* argue that the 'keyness' in developing a theme is not essentially reliant on the scientific measures but on whether the data features something significant in context to the research question.

Figure 2.5. Saldana, (2009, pp.12). An introduction to codes and coding. The coding manual for qualitative researchers.

2.12 Triangulation Methods

Triangulation is the combination of different methodologies used in a study to observe a specified phenomenon. Denzin (1970) identified four types of triangulation (Table 2.5) as data triangulation, investigator triangulation, theoretical triangulation and methodological triangulation. These methodologies may utilise both qualitative and quantitative aspects and become complementary in nature. Triangulation is also known as a convergent methodology (Campbell, & Fiske, 1959) or convergent validation (Webb, Campbell, Schwartz, & Sechrest, 1966) whereby the reliability and validity of a study may be established and enhanced through triangulation of two or more methods of data collection (Burns & Lennon, 1993). Lincoln and Guba (1985) developed four criteria to parallel the quantitative terminology for a qualitative inquiry; these are the credibility or internal validity of how truthful the findings are; the transferability or external validity of how relevant the research findings are in different environments and circumstances; the dependability or reliability of results reproduced in similar conditions; and the confirmability or

objectivity of the findings in reflecting the sample population's perceptions and not an author's preconceptions and biases.

Table 2.5 Types of Triangulation.

Triangulation/Convergent Methods	
1. Data triangulation	Refers to the gathering of data through several sampling strategies, so that slices of data at different times and social situations, as well as on a variety of people, are gathered.
2. Investigator triangulation	Refers to the use of more than one researcher in the field to gather and interpret data.
3. Theoretical triangulation	Refers to the use of more than one theoretical position in interpreting data.
4. Methodological triangulation	Refers to the use of more than one method for gathering data.

Source: Denzin, (1970).

Jick (1979) describes a complex designed triangulation method as having the potential to reveal a contextual portrayal that is complete and holistic. This may be pivotal when eliciting data and drawing conclusions to which singular methods might be blind. Triangulation could possibly be used to observe the same phenomenon from various points of view as well as to enhance our understanding by permitting unseen dimensions to surface (ibid). Donoghue (2000) also argues that combining projective techniques such as drawing and photographic images with informal interviewing enhances the reliability of the research. Yet, the mixed approach of triangulation may not result in a distinct, clear-cut or perfect result. However, it carries the potential to increase the overall comprehension of inconsistencies in various data sets (Holtzhausen, 2001). A more recent study by Koc and Boz (2014) examined triangulation in tourism research and revealed that 48 out of 1,964 studies used three or more methods to triangulate their data; additionally, 21 research papers used interviews and content analyses as their data collection method.

Therefore, the author believes that it is essential to use qualitative data and methodological triangulation in this study to uncover as many aspects of the image in Chinese temples in Phuket as possible, to increase validity and reliability and to improve the overall comprehension of the findings.

In conclusion, the literature has been examined to develop a more holistic and reliable method for assessing a destination's image. The next chapter explains the methods and procedures involved.

3 METHODOLOGY

The chapter explains the methods used for population and sample, data collection, research instruments, interview materials, interview process, pilot test, limitations, ethics, data analysis, reliability and validity and triangulation analysis in pursuing the research objectives.

Overview

An unstructured qualitative approach was employed to holistically and specifically to explore the image of Chinese temples/shrines as a tourist attraction in Phuket using open-ended questions, projective questions and projective drawings to mitigate the likelihood of contrived responses. The investigation also aimed to identify the uniqueness of Chinese temples/shrines by data triangulation. In addition, the differences in perception between Asian and European tourists were also observed using open-ended questions, projective questions and projective drawings.

153 international tourists were interviewed from the 3rd of October to the 13th November 2015 using open-ended questions, projective questions and drawing as the data collection implements. Thematic analysis and content analysis were used to interpret the data and then the results were triangulated to explore the image and identify the uniqueness of each site and the perceptions of tourists at Chinese temples in Phuket.

Initial interviews were conducted with two cultural specialists with ten years of local historical experience, six local tour guides and two Chinese temple managers (Fig. 3.1) to identify the appropriate approach and instruments for this study and factors that might affect the measurement of the Chinese temples image. The interviews indicated that the sample size would be too small for a quantitative or a combined qualitative and quantitative study during low season. For example, ten to twenty independent international tourists on average went to Jui Tui Chinese temple during weekdays according to the temple manager. However, the months of September to November are known as high volume months for international tourists due to the Vegetarian Festival. Careful consideration was given when creating the interview questions to reduce the interference and influence of the images created by the Vegetarian Festival onto the image of Chinese temples.

Figure 3.1 Total number of interviews conducted for this study.

Interviews	Total
Cultural Specialists	2
Local Tour Guides	6
Chinese Temple/Shrine Managers	2
International Tourists	153

3.1 Population and Sample

An purposive sampling method (Higginbottom, 2004; Calder, Phillips, & Tybout, 1982) was used at seven of the Chinese temples/shrines around Phuket. The sample population was identified as international tourists who were 18 years old or above, on holiday and had just left a Chinese temple in Phuket. The author approached visitors leaving and asked three filter questions to qualify them for this study. The first was if they were international tourists, the second if they were more than 18 years old and the third if they were on holiday for less than twelve months.

3.2 Data Collection

The sample locations were selected from Table 2.1. These were cross-referenced using sources such as local cultural specialists with over 10 years of local experience, local tour guides, temple managers (Appendix 9.5, interview questions 1 and 2), the 2015 Vegetarian Festival activity schedule, direct observations relating to geographic location and Google searches. The selection factors included the Chinese temple's historical age, cultural significance, religious artefacts, tourist attractions, tourist numbers, 2015 Vegetarian Festival events, passing traffic patterns, known tourist areas and Google search results (Fig. 3.2). The summation of these results identified seven popular Chinese temples in Phuket which were suitable for data collection; these were Bang Neow, Hok Nguan Kung, Jui Tui, Kathu, Pud Jor, Saphan Hin and Serene Light. Out these seven Chinese temples, Kathu temple is located in Kathu district and the remaining six are located in Phuket Town district (Fig. 3.3).

Figure 3.2 Data used to select the interview locations at Chinese temples/shines in Phuket.

Source	Factors	Chinese Temples	
Local cultural specialists	Historical age	Bang Neow, Hok Nguan Kung, Jui Tui,	
	Cultural significance	Kathu, Pud Jor, Saphan Hin, Serene Light	
	Religious artefacts		
Local tour guides	Tourist attractions	Bang Neow, Jui Tui, Kathu, Pud Jor, Saphan	
	Tourist numbers	Hin, Serene Light	
Temple managers	Tourist numbers	Jui Tui, Kathu, Pud Jor, Saphan Hin	
Vegetarian Festival	2015 activity schedule	Bang Neow, Jui Tui, Kathu	
Geographic location	Passing traffic	Bang Neow, Hok Nguan Kung, Jui Tui, Pud	
	Tourist areas	Jor, Saphan Hin, Serene Light	
Google	Search results	Bang Neow	About 96,700 results
	“(temple name) Temple Phuket”	Hok Nguan Kung	About 4,450 results
	Date 12 September 2015	Jui Tui	About 12,500 results
		Kathu	About 381,000 results
		Pud Jor	About 517,000 results
		Saphan Hin	About 73,600 results
		Serene Light	About 153,000 results

Figure 3.3 Google Maps (2016). A map of Phuket Island showing the location of Chinese temples and shrines where interviews with international tourists were conducted.

3.3 Research Instruments

An extensive review of the literature was conducted to identify the methodologies and techniques used for measuring image which could then be triangulated. This approach used open-ended questions (Echtner & Ritchie 2003; Jenkins, 1999), projective drawing (Korstanje, 2010; Carmen-Garcia, Navas, & Cuadrado, 2003; Machover, 1949) and projective questions (Westwood, 2007; Loevinger, 1976). See appendix 9.5 for the tourist questionnaire.

The interview questions were divided into seven parts. In part one there were (3) open-ended questions (Table 3.1). Part two had (2) projective drawings questions (Table 3.2). Part three contained (19) projective questions (Table 3.3). Part four consolidate questions that discussed the (1) activities (Table 3.4), (3) culture promotion (Table 3.5); (2) information questions about the site (Table 3.6); (6) recommendation questions (Table 3.7). Part five addressed questions to the (7) respondents profile (Table 3.8), (9) travel behaviour (Table 3.9) and (6) behaviour at the Chinese temple (Table 3.10).

Part	Questions	Appendix Reference
1. Open-Ended Questions	3	Table 3.1
2. Projective Drawings	2	Table 3.2
3. Projective Questions	19	Table 3.3
4. Satisfaction & Recommendations	12	
- Activities at the Chinese temple		Table 3.4
- Cultural promotion		Table 3.5
- Information about the site		Table 3.6
- Recommendation		Table 3.7
5. Respondents Profile	7	Table 3.8
6. Respondents' Travel Behaviour	9	Table 3.9
7. Respondents' Behaviour at the Chinese Temple	6	Table 3.10

The first three open questions in Table 3.1 were designed to capture the attributes, holistic image, and common and unique features of the Chinese temples.

Table 3.1 Open-ended questions variables.

Variable	Author & Year
What image(s) come into your mind first, when you think about a Chinese temple/shrine? Why?	Phakdee-auksorn, P. (2009); Tran, L. (2013); Ryan, C., & Cave, J. (2005).
What are the distinctive features of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket?	Phakdee-auksorn, P. (2009); Kim, H., & Stepchenkova, S. (2015); Tran, L. (2013); Li, X., Pan, B., Zhang, L., & Smith, W. (2009).
What was your first impression/feeling when you entered into this Chinese temple/shrine?	Phakdee-auksorn, P. (2009); Kim, H., & Stepchenkova, S. (2015); Ryan, C., & Cave, J. (2005), Li, X., Pan, B., Zhang, L., & Smith, W. (2009).

In the second part (Table 3.2), respondents were asked two projective drawings questions to illustrate the specific attributes and unique features of the image. A design consideration included a square drawing area which was used to reduce the chance of a participant's selecting landscape or portrait view.

Table 3.2 Projective drawings variables.

Variable	Author & Year
Can you please draw a picture of the Chinese temple/shrine as a whole?	Panagiotaki, G., Nobes, G., & Potton, A. (2009); Čalýk, M., Ayas, A., & Ebenezer, J. V. (2005).
Please describe what you have drawn.	
Can you draw any details of this Chinese temple/shrine?	Panagiotaki, G., Nobes, G., & Potton, A. (2009); Čalýk, M., Ayas, A., & Ebenezer, J. V. (2005).
Please describe what you have drawn.	

The third part in Table 3.3 used projective question with the components of destination image conceptual model by Echtner and Ritchie (2003) which provided a tried and tested method for measuring both the functional and psychological characteristics, as well as the holistic and common aspects of the Chinese temples.

Table 3.3 Projective questions variables.

Variable	Author & Year
The (object of study) is...	Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003).
The layout of the (object of study) is...	Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003).
The space is...	Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003).
The area around the (object of study) is...	Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003).
The view from the outside is...	Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Jenkins, O. H. (1999).
The view from the inside is...	Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Jenkins, O. H. (1999).
The architecture is...	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Kim, H., & Stepchenkova, S. (2015); Hsu, C. H., & Song, H. (2012); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Jenkins, O. H. (1999).
The decorations are...	Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Hsu, C. H., & Song, H. (2012); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003).
The staff or keepers are...	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Kim, H., & Stepchenkova, S. (2015); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Jenkins, O. H. (1999); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b).
The climate is...	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Jenkins, O. H. (1999); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b).
The feeling I get at this location is...	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Kim, H., & Stepchenkova, S. (2015); Tran, L. (2013); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b).
The smell is...	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Lee, W., & Gretzel, U. (2006).
The environment is...	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Kim, H., & Stepchenkova, S. (2015); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b).
The sounds are...	Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Lee, W., & Gretzel, U. (2006).
The atmosphere is...	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Kim, H., & Stepchenkova, S. (2015); Tran, L. (2013); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Jenkins, O. H. (1999); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).
The activities are...	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Tran, L. (2013); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011a); Ramkissoon, H., & Uysal, M. S. (2011); Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Jenkins, O. H. (1999); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).

The religion is...	Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003); Jenkins, O. H. (1999); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).
The culture is...	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Kim, H., & Stepchenkova, S. (2015); Tran, L. (2013); Hsu, C. H., & Song, H. (2012); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011a); Jenkins, O. H. (1999).
The experience is...	Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Jenkins, O. H. (1999); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).

The fourth part (Table 3.4) had one multiple answer question which asked respondents what activities they had participated in while visiting the Chinese temple (Ramkissoon & Uysal, 2011; Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011a). The most common activities were; pray (Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011b; Sathpathy & Mahalik, 2010), buy a souvenir (Correia, Oliveira, & Silva, 2009; Pizam & Jeong, 1996), take photos (Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011b; Pizam & Jeong, 1996), get your fortune told (Shein, Li, & Huang, 2014; Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011b), light incense (Huang & Yeh, 2015; Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011b), (Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011b; Sathpathy & Mahalik, 2010) and another choice with a blank space for alternative responses.

Table 3.4 Activities at the Chinese temple variables.

Variable	Author & Year
What did you do in the Chinese temple? (You can tick more than one.)	Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011a); Ramkissoon, H., & Uysal, M. S. (2011).
Pray	Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Sathpathy, B., & Mahalik, D. (2010).
Buy a souvenir	Correia, A., Oliveira, N., & Silva, F. (2009); Pizam, A., & Jeong, G. H. (1996).
Take photos	Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Pizam, A., & Jeong, G. H. (1996).
Get your fortune told	Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Shein, P., Li, Y., & Huang, C. (2014).
Light incense	Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b).; Huang, W., & Yeh., Y. (2015).
Ask of advice	Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Sathpathy, B., & Mahalik, D. (2010).
Others	-

Table 3.5 contained three cultural promotion questions. These questions were used to gain insights into what promotion images visiting tourists might find attractive.

Table 3.5 Cultural promotion variables.

Variable	Author & Year
What images or pictures would you use to promote Chinese temples in Phuket? Why?	Nicoletta, R., & Servidio, R. (2012).
What activities at the Chinese temple would appeal to you the most? Why?	Tran, L. (2013); Ryan, C., & Cave, J. (2005).
If you were the Chinese temple manager, how would you promote Chinese temples and shrines as cultural tourist attractions?	Tran, L. (2013); Nicoletta, R., & Servidio, R. (2012).

The information section asked two questions (Table 3.6). The first was a multiple choice question on what information influenced them the most to visit the site (Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011b; Correia, Oliveira, & Silva, 2009; Sonmez, & Sirakaya, 2002). The variables included

newspaper/magazine, guidebook, TV, word of mouth and internet (Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011b; Lee, & Lee, 2009). The second question asked visitor to rate on a five-point Likert scale (1. very poor to 5. excellent) what they thought about the information available at the Chinese temple (Qu, Kim, & Im, 2011; Pizam & Jeong, 1996).

Table 3.6 Information about the site variables.

Variable	Author & Year
Which influenced you the most when deciding to visit a Chinese temple in Phuket?	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Correia, A., Oliveira, N., & Silva, F. (2009); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b).
Newspaper/Magazine	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).
Guidebook	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).
TV	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).
Word of mouth	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).
Internet	Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).
What do you think about the information available to you at the Chinese temple?	Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011); Pizam, A., & Jeong, G. H. (1996).

The recommendations segment (Table 3.7) asked six questions in total: five open-ended and one Likert scale question. These questions were used to discover how recommendations would be made and to whom.

Table 3.7 Recommendation variables.

Variable	Author & Year
What were your expectations before visiting the Chinese temple?	Furlan, C., & Gambarotto, F. (2008).
How satisfied were you with the way the Chinese temple is organised?	Tran, L. (2013).
Would you recommend others to visit this temple?	Mocanu, R. (2014); Ramkissoon, H., & Uysal, M. S. (2011); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b).
How would you recommend it?	Phakdee-auksorn, P. (2009).
To whom would you recommend it?	Phakdee-auksorn, P. (2009); Mocanu, R. (2014); Ramkissoon, H., & Uysal, M. S. (2011); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b).
Would you like to make any other comments?	Phakdee-auksorn, P. (2009).

Part five (Table 3.8) addressed seven basic questions to the respondent's profile. The first was gender (Matlovičová & Kolesárová, 2012). Second, Erikson's (1956) stages of psychosocial development was used to determine the age ranges of the visitors, these were; 13–19, 20–39, 40–64 and 65 years old and above (Psychology Charts, 2016; Cramer, Flynn, & LaFave, 1997). Erikson's (1956) work shows that each age brackets is met with its own specific environmental, psychological and existential challenges (McLeod, 2008). Therefore, using Erikson's (1956) stages of psychosocial development with the exploration of the Chinese temples image using the psychological technique of projective questions and drawing on international tourists might give some light to the study's understanding of the personal factors attracting and motivating international visitors of a certain age group to visit Chinese temples in Phuket (Learning Theories; 2014). Third was education level with the variables; no education, college level, high school, bachelor's degree, master's degree and, doctorate (Nyaupane, Timothy, & Poudel, 2015; Matlovičová & Kolesárová, 2012). Fourth, the level of income was defined by the monthly salary of international tourists in American dollars using the brackets of \$1000 or below, \$1001–\$3000, \$3001–\$5000, \$5001–\$10,000 and \$10,000 and above (Xu, & Zhang, 2016). Fifth was marital status, which variables contained single, married, divorced and widowed (García, Gómez, & Molina, 2012; Phakdee-auksorn, 2009). The sixth was an open question that asked the respondent to specify their nationality (Tapanes, Smith, & White, 2009; Gobin, & Subramanian, 2007). The respondents' nationalities were than categorised into the region of Africa, Asia, Australia, Europe, North America, South America (Matzler, Strobl, Stokburger-Sauer, Bobovnický, & Bauer, 2016; Nisbett, & Miyamoto, 2005; An, 2014;

Sonnleitner, 2011; Verwiebe, 2011; Schnore, 1961). Lastly religions were classed as Buddhist, Christian, Hindu, Jewish, Muslim, Sikh, Taoist and None (Balboni, Bandini, Mitchell, Epstein-Peterson, Amobi, Cahill, Enzinger, Peteet, & Balboni, 2015; Kataoka, 2012).

Table 3.8 Respondent's profile variables.

Variable	Author & Year
Male/Female	Matlovičová, K., & Kolesárová, J. (2012).
Age	García, J., Gómez, M., & Molina, A. (2012); Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002); Erikson, E. H. (1956).
Education	Matlovičová, K., & Kolesárová, J. (2012); Nyaupane, G., Timothy, D., & Poudel, S. (2015)
Income	Xu, Z., & Zhang, J. (2016).
Marital Status	Phakdee-auksorn, P. (2009); García, J., Gómez, M., & Molina, A. (2012).
Nationality	Tapanes, M., Smith, G., & White, J. (2009); Gobin, B., & Subramanian, R. (2007).
Religion	Kataoka, T. (2012); Balboni, M., Bandini, J., Mitchell, C., Epstein-Peterson, Z., Amobi, A., Cahill, J., Enzinger, A., Peteet, J., & Balboni, T. (2015).

Part six (Table 3.9) asked nine questions to identify the respondent's travel behaviour. Question one requested if the respondent was on holiday (Lee, & Lee, 2009; Hanley, 1989). This was followed by how long the visitor was on holiday for (Pizam, & Jeong, 1996). Next the respondent was asked to classify themselves as to the type of tourist they thought they were (Coccosis, & Constantoglou, 2008; Choibamroong, 2006). The variables were cultural (Pizam, & Jeong, 1996), leisure (Foo, McGuigan, & Yiannakis, 2004), religious (Yfantidou, 2008) or spiritual (Yfantidou, 2008) tourist and another option with a blank space was given for alternative responses. The remaining questions then asked whether it was the respondent's first visit to a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket (Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011a; Mohammad, & Som, 2010). Did the visitor intentionally planned to visit this specific Chinese temple/shrine (Ramkissoon & Uysal, 2011; Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011a; Mohammad, & Som, 2010). What time of the day did the tourist visit; morning – 06:00-12:00, afternoon – 12:01-18:00 or evening – 18:01-00:00 (Haiyan, & Jasper, 2007). The amount of time the respondent spent inside the Chinese temple/shrine; less than 30 minutes, about 31–60 minutes, about 61–90 minutes or more than 91

minutes (Olsen, 2015; Haiyan, & Jasper, 2007). Did the respondent have a consort accompanying them or not. The variables were alone, friend(s), with family member(s), with a tour group or with a personal tour guide (O'Brien, & Morris, 2009). Finally, the number of Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket respondents had been to before visiting the current Chinese temple/shrine (Backlund, & Williams, 2003).

Table 3.9 Respondent's travel behaviour variables.

Variable	Author & Year
Are you on holiday?	Hanley, N. D. (1989); Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009).
How long are you on holiday for?	Pizam, A., & Jeong, G. H. (1996).
What type of tourist would you consider yourself as?	Coccosis, H., & Constantoglou, M. E. (2008); Choibamroong, T. (2006).
Is this your first visit?	Mohammad, B., & Som, A. (2010); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011a).
Did you intentionally plan your visit?	Mohammad, B., & Som, A. (2010); Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011a); Ramkissoon, H., & Uysal, M. S. (2011).
What time did you visit?	Haiyan, H., & Jasper, C. R. (2007).
How long did you spend?	Olsen, J. (2015); Haiyan, H., & Jasper, C. R. (2007).
Who did you visit this temple/shrine with?	O'Brien, L., & Morris, J. (2009).
How many Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket have you visited?	Backlund, E. A., & Williams, D. R. (2003).

The final part (Table 3.10) asked six questions regarding the respondent's behaviour at the Chinese temple in Phuket. The questions included how much money respondents spent (Hartling, & Meier, 2010; Long, & Perdue, 1990); the values were defined as zero, 1–100, 101–200, 201–300, 301–400 or 401 Thai Baht or more. If items were purchased they were asked to state which ones (Xu, & McGehee, 2012; Teas, 1988). Next respondents were asked if they made a donation (Hall, 2001). The following dichotomous question was asked to determine the willingness of respondents to pay a future entrance fee into the Chinese temple/shrine (Hidalgo, Hidalgo-Fernández, Madueño, & Arriaza, 2015; Trivourea, Karamanlidis, Tounta, Dendrinis, & Kotomatas, 2011) and how much entrance fee (Hirai, Kitama, & Nishimura, 2000) would be acceptable. The ranges were; zero, 1-50, 51-100, 101-150, 151-200, 201-205 or 251 Thai Baht or more. The final question was an open question asking why respondents visited the Chinese temple/shrine (O'Brien, & Morris, 2009).

The interview questions were checked by three PhD lecturers at the Faculty of Hospitality and Tourism, Prince of Songkla University, Phuket Campus. One question from the first part of open-ended questions became redundant and minor format changes were made.

Table 3.10 Respondents behaviour at the Chinese temple variables.

Variable	Author & Year
How much money (in Thai Baht) did you spend at this Chinese temple/shrine?	Hartling, J. W., & Meier, I. (2010); Long, P. T., & Perdue, R. R. (1990).
What did you buy at this Chinese temple/shrine?	Xu, Y., & McGehee, N. G. (2012); Teas, J. (1988).
Did you make a donation?	Hall, M. H. (2001).
Would you be willing to pay an entrance fee?	Hidalgo, A. F., Hidalgo-Fernández, R. E., Madueño, J. A. C., & Arriaza, M. (2015); Trivourea, M. N., Karamanlidis, A. A., Tounta, E., Dendrinis, P., & Kotomatas, S. (2011).
How much entrance fee (in Thai Baht) would you pay to visit this Chinese temple/shrine?	Hirai, S., Kitama, H., & Nishimura, T. (2000).
Why did you visit this Chinese temple/shrine?	O'Brien, L., & Morris, J. (2009).

3.4 Interview Materials

The materials used for this study included a clip board, a Staedtler 2B pencil, an eraser and a Hores box set of 12 colouring pencils (red, orange, yellow, light green, emerald green, light blue, blue, purple, pink, flesh, brown and black) that included a pencil sharpener in the box (Purchase, 2014; Burkitt, Barrett, & Davis, 2003). Pencils were used due to the environmental considerations of heat, humidity and rainy season in Phuket. Because pencils are dry, they were not likely to bleed or run when made wet. They were also considered easy to use and allowed for a variety of expressive marks through line thickness, pressure, mixture of colour and tonal variation when drawing. Also the interviews were audio recorded using a Samsung Galaxy 8.0 smart phone.

3.5 Interview Process

The author administered all the interviews outside of the selected Chinese temples' entrances. As visitors left the Chinese temple they were greeted warmly and asked 2 filter questions: what nationality they were, followed by whether they were on holiday or not. If they were a Thai national or an international visitor not on holiday the interview was politely drawn to a halt. Participants that passed the

filter questions were then told of the purpose of the study and they were asked if they would like to participate; although a few participants declined on the grounds that their English language ability or lack of time, most were happy to comply. The instructions of the interview were read to the participants which included the interview length (30 to 45 minutes), how the results would be used, confidentiality of the information given, the interviewer's identity and the instructions: that there were no right or wrong answers (Solomon, 1994, p.25) and to give as much information as possible.

The interview started with 3 open-ended questions which then lead to the drawing part of the study; before the first drawing question was asked the interviewer explained the copyright, constant, confidentiality, publication and agreement of the drawing section. Then the interviewee was asked the first drawing question, which was to draw a picture of the Chinese temple/shrine as a whole. They were told that they could not look at the Chinese temple and no verbal suggestions were given. At the same time, a box colouring pencils was presented before them and they were encouraged to draw. Some interviewees responded with hesitant statements like, "*I cannot draw well*", "*I draw really badly*" or even "*I am not a visual person*". However, the interviewer replied with phrases such as, "*whatever you draw will be perfect*", "*draw what you remember*" or "*there is no right or wrong way of drawing*". The participants were given as much time as need to complete the activity and were allowed to stop whenever they felt like. This allowed them to explore their feelings and experience (Williams, 2002, p3-4) in a more complete and uninterrupted way. After they had finished their drawing the interviewee was asked to explain what they had drawn. This process was repeated when the interviewee was asked to draw any details of this Chinese temple/shrine. The interview then continued to the projective questions and the remaining questions.

3.6 Pilot Test

A pilot test of 30 international tourists was conducted and minor changes were made. Initially the study included a drawing and photograph part. The photograph part was used as an alternative to drawing should the interviewee decide not to draw however the photographic element was not used as all the participants opted to draw and therefore it was taken out. Other minor changes included the addition of two variables, "*look around*" and "*ring the bell*", to the activities section. An additional variable was added to the information about the site, this being "*walking around*", as it became apparent that some respondents didn't intentionally plan on visiting a Chinese temple but were attracted to it. Finally, four additional variables were added to the demographic part. "*Spiritual*" and "*agnostic*" were added to the

question about their religious belief and “*backpacker*” and “*explorer*” were added to the type of tourist they consider themselves to be.

3.7 Data Analysis

To achieve the study’s objectives, the raw data was inputted into a custom-made repository grid in Excel, 2010 edition. First, thematic analysis (Saldana, 2009) was used to code the open-ended, closed-ended and the verbal responses to the drawing elements of the study. Adjustments were made through recoding and codes were developed into categories and finally themes (Table 9.3.1). Next the open-ended questions were exported into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 and statistical analyses of the frequencies were done to determine the results of the content analysis. Similarly, the closed-ended questions were checked for their frequencies, mean and standard deviation. Then the Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing in Fig. 3.4 was used to recode the graphical elements into an Excel spreadsheet and analysed for results.

The Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing (Fig. 3.4) was modified from Riley’s (2001) A Systemic-Functional Semiotic Model of the Domain of Drawing to measure individual attributes of a drawn element within a picture to uncover the most memorable images, including the salient Compositional, Interpersonal, and Experiential function elements in composition, colours and feelings which could be used in future tourism marketing material.

The model was divided into four main attributes (Fig. 3.4). The first group of attributes identified the compositional components and were: the number of unique or identical items in the picture; the drawn completeness of an object that was either whole, part or a mixture; and the dimensionality of the drawn item whether in 2D, 3D or a mixture. The view of an object from the viewer’s perspective was divided into two parts: object with non-directional perspective (Fig. 3.5). The fixed objects, for example columns were objects that had no facing direction, such as a candle. Objects with a directional perspective (Fig. 3.6) were defined as moving objects, for instance a car; or continuous objects like the sky.

The size of a drawn object was determined by using grid system. The rule of thirds (Kemp, 2016; Dhar, Ordonez, & Berg, 2011) was used to divide the canvas into an equal nine squares (Fig. 3.7). The small items were identified as half a square size or less, medium items were classed as half to one whole square size and large items were bigger than one grid square. An object’s proportion was identified by its real life dimension in comparison to the drawn items around it.

The drawn impression of an object was evaluated as either abstract or realistic. This was evaluated based on the correctness of an object's dimensions.

The location of an object was recorded in one of four different ways depending on the area it occupied, firstly if an item was drawn into one of the nine square grid (Fig. 3.7), secondly if an item was crossed two or more horizontal grid spaces (Fig. 3.8), thirdly if an item was crossed two or more vertical grid spaces (Fig. 3.9) and if the item covered four grid spaces equally or more it was considered a mixture.

Items with calligraphic inscription or impression were noted and drawn objects that were cropped off the canvas recorded.

The second group of attributes described the stylistic use of the pencil by international tourists; whether or not they used a Staedtler 2B pencil when drawing, the soft, medium, hard or mixed used of pencil pressure; the varying line thickness; the range of liner, patterned, textural, dotted, solid or mixed marks made when describing the visual form of an object; the shaded, gradation, solid or mixture of tone used and if an object had a shadow.

The third group of attributes analysed; whether colour was used; the range of colours and the techniques of pressure, line quality, pencil marks, tones and shadow and the fourth attribute analysed the feelings associated with the object.

Finally, the Compositional (C) elements examine the level of completion, dimensions and perspective, proportions, location on the page, framing devices or cropping, colours (including pencil), marks, tones, textures and patterns. Interpersonal (I) elements inspect the view, scale or size, the pressure of marks such as soft and hard. Experiential (E) elements study the items or themes drawn, realistic or abstract impressions, calligraphy, the line quality, for example thick or thin, shadows or light upon surfaces and the feeling or emotions associated with the image.

Figure 3.4 Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing. Modified; Riley (2001).

Attributes		Variables	C/I/E	
Image	Composition	Number of items.	E	
		Completion	whole, part, mixture	C
		Dimensions	2D, 3D, mixture, none	C
		View - viewer to object	Object non-directional perspective: front below right, front below, front right, front left, front, front below left, front above right, front above, front above left, birds eye, mixture. Object directional perspective: profile below, profile below left, profile below right, profile left, profile right, profile above left, profile above right, profile above, mixture.	I
		Size	large, medium, small, mixture, none	I
		Proportionate	yes, no	C
		Impression	realistic, abstract	E
		Location on the page	across the bottom, across the centre, across the top, bottom, bottom left, bottom right, centre, down the left, down the middle, down the right, left, majority of the page, right, top, top left, top right, mixture	C
		Calligraphy	yes, no	E
		Crop	yes, no	C
Image	Pencil	Pencil	yes, no	C
		Pencil - Pressure	hard, normal, soft, mixture, none	I
		Pencil - Line Quality	thin, medium, thick, mixture, none	E
		Pencil - Marks	liner, pattern, texture, dots, solid, mixture, none	C
		Pencil - Tone	shaded, gradation, solid, mixture, none	C
		Pencil - Shadow	yes, no	E
Image	Colours	Colours Used	yes, no	C
		Colour - Red, Green, Yellow, Blue, Orange, Purple, Pink, Brown, Flesh, Black, White/None	yes, no	C
		Colour - Pressure	hard, normal, soft, mixture, none	I
		Colour - Line Quality	thin, medium, thick, mixture, none	E
		Colour - Marks	liner, pattern, texture, dots, solid, mixture, none	C
		Colour - Tone	shaded, gradation, solid, mixture, none	C
		Colour - Shadow	yes, no	E
Image	Feelings	Themes	E	

Note: C = Compositional, I = Interpersonal, E = Experiential

Figure 3.5 Drawn objects with non-directional perspective.

Figure 3.6 Drawn objects with directional perspective.

Figure 3.7 Canvas with (three by three) nine grid locations. Note: not to scale.

Top left	Top	Top right
Left	Centre	Right
Bottom left	Bottom	Bottom right

Figure 3.8 Canvas with three horizontal locations. Note: not to scale.

Across the top
Across the centre
Across the bottom

Figure 3.9 Canvas with three vertical locations. Note: not to scale.

Down the left side	Down the middle	Down the right side
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3.8 Reliability and Validity

Qualitative studies are exploratory in nature and work in the context of discovery; empirical and theoretical findings may surface as the process of data collection commences (Baker & Edwards, 2012). It therefore may not be known in advance exactly how much data should be gathered to ensure the reliability and validity of a study. Howard Becker suggests that one should stop when one learns nothing new (Baker & Edwards, 2012) or at data saturation. However, he also states that a few interviews may demonstrate an event or experience as being far more intricate or wide-ranging than previously thought, thus identifying an exact number of interviews to a study would be difficult. Yet, Adler and Adler (Baker & Edwards, 2012) have advised their graduate students to sample anywhere from 12 to 60 respondents with 30 being the mean. In Marshall, Cardon, Poddar and Fontenot's (2013) quantitative study on sample sizes in qualitative research, they argued in their findings that grounded theory qualitative investigation should usually comprise of 20 to 30 interviews. Whereas Ragin (in Baker & Edwards, 2012, p.5) suggests a convincing amount is 20 for a master's thesis and 50 for a doctoral dissertation. With this in mind it was decided that a minimum of 20 interviews would be carried out at each of the seven Chinese temples in Phuket and a total was set at 140 interviews as a minimum, subject to data saturation to established reliability and validity. In addition, data and methodological triangulation were used to increase the reliability and validity (Westwood, 2007) of this study as discussed earlier.

3.9 Triangulation Analysis

Lastly, the results from the three components (open-ended questions, projective questions and projective drawings) were triangulated using the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image model (Fig. 1.1). The top ten themes for each of the three open-ended questions were counted. Then, all the first level themes and significant themes that occurred three times or more in the projective questions were tallied. Next, the top ten items, the top ten feelings and the most frequently used colours in the projective drawings were calculated. After that any duplicated answers within each of the three components were removed to reduce confusion in the analysis process. Finally, the results were combined and the same recurring themes in all of the three components were considered significant. Thus, the reliability and validity of the findings has been increased.

3.10 Research Limitations

The limitations for the data collection included an unknown population size and unknown distributions of gender, nationality, and frequency of visits to any Chinese temple in Phuket. Environmental limitations such as the rainy weather had the potential to hamper visitations (Petr, 2015) as the time of data collection was during the raining season. As the interviews were conducted outside, the international tourists may not have felt comfortable in the uncustomary hot and humid weather. This reduced the overall length of some interviews. However, the structure of the three open-ended questions were short. The drawing aspect allowed the tourist to engage more deeply in the study while giving them the ability to control their time; and the projective questions (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003) captured the various aspects of the perception of the Chinese temple image.

The tourists' limitations may have been their level of English and their ability to articulate their thoughts and feelings within the parameters of the questions and their ability to describe their experience through drawing. For example, colour blindness may have been a factor.

3.11 Research Ethics

Careful consideration was given in the drawing part of this study to the issues of the creator's identity (Gibson & Riley, 2010), informed consent and confidentiality (Frith, Riley, Archer, & Gleeson, 2005), copyright and ownership of images, notification of future reproductions of the images (Rouse, 2013) and the potential of the negative interpretations by third parties, which are outside the control of the author and respondent (Frith, Riley, Archer, & Gleeson, 2005).

Taking all these considerations into account it was therefore decided, firstly, that copyright would be given to the creator of the image. Secondly, the creator's name, signature, email and creation date were recorded on each drawn image page and kept confidential. Then, each image was given an identification code (Image ID) consisting of thirteen digits under each image box. Thirdly, two dichotomous yes or no questions were asked about the agreed use of the image for non-profit and/or international academic publications and the creator of the image transferring full copyright to the author for future publications. If the creator checked the no box, written permission would seek from the creator. Lastly, the important agreement notes outlined only the use of the Image ID instead of the respondent personal details with their drawings for both printed or electronic publications. No details of the creator's name, signature or email will be released and the creator agreed that any potential negative interpretations of this image outside of this study are beyond the control of the author and therefore the author cannot and will not be held liable,

nor face any legal prosecution in any court of law (9.5 tourist interview questionnaire). These formed the terms and conditions used ensured the ethical treatment of the creator/respondent.

In conclusion, the sampling methods, survey construction, data collection procedures and methods of analysis of this study have been explained with regards to the literature review. The following chapter discusses the findings.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents and discusses the findings pertaining to the study objectives. The aims of the study were firstly, to explore the image of Chinese temples in Phuket, secondly to identify the uniqueness of Chinese temples/shrines, and thirdly to examine the differences in perception between Asian and European tourists. The data was collected from 153 international tourists at seven Chinese temples and shrine around Phuket during 3rd of October to the 13th November 2015, using a questionnaire designed with open-ended questions, projective questions and projective drawings. The data was analysed using content analysis then triangulated using the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image (Fig. 4.1) to increase the reliability and validity for the results.

4.1 Respondents

4.1.1 Response Rate

A total of 210 international tourists were approached and asked to participate in this study at each of the Chinese temples in Phuket. However, only 153 visitors voluntarily participated, with an average of 21 interviews per Chinese temple (Table 9.4.1) giving a total response rate of 72%.

4.1.2 Respondent's Profile

The international tourist profile in Table 9.4.2 showed that there are slightly more male than female visitors. The majority (75.2%) of international tourists are aged from 20–39 years old. It may have been believed that Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket would have attracted an older international age group but this was not the case in the present study. Similar findings of Chinese temple/shrine visitors revealed that 62% of worshippers were aged 20–39 years old (Lang, Chan, & Ragvald, 2005) and 87% of believers were aged between 21–50 years old (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009). The age range of international tourists and pilgrims to Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket is similar, but their reasons for visiting are different. For example, the seeking of new knowledge and cultural experiences (Table 9.4.11) by tourists is mainly associated with higher levels of education (Richards, 2011), and is reflected in the result of 81.0% of respondents having a bachelor's degree, which agrees with Chen and Chen's (2010) cultural heritage study findings.

The average income of international tourists is between \$1001 to \$3000 USD per month. Interestingly 74.5% of visitors reported themselves as being single (Table 9.4.2), yet many were accompanied by a travel companion (Table 9.4.4). Considering many of the international tourists are aged

from 20–39 years old, Erikson's (1956) stages of psychosocial development defines this as the love stage, where there is need to explore love, intimacy and relationships. On the other hand, the avoidance or failure of relationships may lead to negative behaviour and isolation. Lang, Chan, and Ragvald, (2005) reported that half of men aged from 30–39 years old visiting Chinese temples were accompanied by a female partner. Furthermore, they observed that male and female worshippers of a similar age visiting Chinese temples pray to statues, figures and gods (Fig. 4.1) which includes the use of items for divination to ask for advice about their personal issues, predicaments and solutions to troubles. Erikson's (1956) love phase may well point to a subconscious need for male and female archetypal figures for personal (Vazire & Carlson, 2011; Groesbeck, 1975) or spiritual guidance which could cross cultural boundaries.

European (42.5%) and Asian (36.6%) tourists were the most common visitors (Table 9.4.2.1). In Table 9.4.2, 34.6% of respondents specified themselves as having no religious belief and 31.4% were Christian, therefore showing there to be a much wider appeal to Chinese temples/shrines (Lang, Chan, & Ragvald, 2005) as cultural tourism points. As almost half (48.4%) of all international tourists labeled themselves as cultural tourists (Table 9.4.3). These (cultural) tourist types (Table 2.2 and Fig 9.2.2.1) are described as mostly serendipitous, incidental and casual in nature, and seek both a mixture of deep and shallow experiences and therefore their purpose to visit intentionally is rated low to medium (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002). This behaviour is emphasised in Table 9.4.4 where 72.5% of the visits were unplanned. In addition, some international visitors can be further described as wandering tourists who have a wide range of aims but have no fixed plans and thus act with a serendipitous spirit; similarly, other adventuresome travellers with seasoned international travel experience are known to accompany other travellers and repeat visits (McKercher, Wong, & Lau, 2006) without prior planning. This would possibly explain why a little over half (50.9%) of international tourists had visited between one to three Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket (Table 9.4.4) and may have been influenced by word of mouth (Groepel-Klein & Germelmann, 2003; Gartner, 1993). The predominate time to visit is throughout the afternoon hours. Most visits lasted less than 30 minutes (70.6%). McKercher & Du Cros (2002) also highlight the time limitation for tourist visitations (Table 2.2).

Through careful planning it is possible to increase the time and money spent at the location by providing accurate historical and cultural information about the site to tourists (Table 2.2). Over 81.0% of respondents who visited a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket had higher levels of education, such as bachelor's degree. This is similar to Petr's (2015) findings. Educated tourists who engage in cultural activities were noted to experience higher levels of fascination (Table, 4.11 and Table 9.4.35) at Chinese

temples and shrines (Lang, Chan, & Ragvald, 2005). This revealed the assets to have extrinsic value (Table 2.2) for international tourists even though the information at the sites were limited. These extrinsic values are represented in significant images found in Fig. 4.1 which were statues/figures/gods, religious/traditional, fascinating, attractive, mysterious, peaceful and unique. This indicates that the most potent images created by Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket are both tangible (statues/figures/gods) and intangible (religious/traditional, fascinating, attractive, mysterious, peaceful and unique), which possibly leads to the desire for tourists to consume a culture experience at Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket according to McKercher & Du Cros's (2002) definition in Table 2.2.

Remarkably, over half (52.3%) of all tourists acted upon the influence of word of mouth (Table 9.4.5) and 46.3% indicated that they had no preconception of what they would see or experience at the Chinese temple or shrine (Table 9.4.6). As one respondent said, "*I didn't really think of anything*". However, most international tourists' negative perception at the lack information available to them at Chinese temples/shrines (Table 9.4.7) was contrasted by the high level of satisfaction with the organisation of it (Table 9.4.8). Therefore, this indicates that having no prior ideas of a destination might lead to more exclusive images being formed, while the lack of information enhances the overall fascination (Table 9.4.11, Table 9.4.18 and Table 9.4.35) and focuses a tourist's attention on symbols, images and experiences that are unique to the site. McKercher & Du Cros's (2002) definition in Table 2.2 explains that the information style, quality and accuracy received by the tourist before they visit will affect their expectations and behaviour when they visit the asset. However, this may be an exceptional circumstantial when considering how the lack of information was offset by the high level of satisfaction.

Gartner's (1993) model (Fig. 2.1) illustrates that a visitor's cognitive and affective images can be significantly influenced by positive word of mouth (Groepel-Klein & Germelmann, 2003), causing a higher quality experience of the cultural and heritage site with increased positive behavioural intentions, which leads to a greater chance of recommendation and re-visitation (Chen & Chen, 2010; Ramkissoon, Uysal, & Brown, 2011). This is clearly seen in Table 9.4.34 where 97.4% said they would recommend Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket to another visitor. In addition, the act of taking photos (29.2%), as shown in Table 9.4.9, stimulates the memory of a visitor's images and is known to exert a strong influence on the behavioural intentions of other travellers through the publication of personal photos on social media communities (Cheng, Chen, Huang, Hsu, & Liao, 2011). 38.1% of international tourists stated that they would recommend their experience of visiting a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket using the internet (Table 9.4.34).

Although 61.4% did not buy anything at the Chinese temples/shrines (Table 9.4.10) due to the varying size, popularity and items available at each Chinese temple and shrine, 58.2% made a donation. Finally, fascination (35.6%) emerged as the predominate reason for visiting a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket (Table 9.4.11). Previous research on tourists visiting Taoist temples and have also shown the reason of “*curiosity*” as a motivating factor to visit (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009), and is seen as one of the main reasons for recommending a Chinese temple/shrine (Table 9.4.35). Fascination is unique to each individual and is difficult to specify what elements cause fascination (Degen, 2012). However, within the context of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket it is interesting to note the repeated use of the word look, revealing that the traditional architectural style and colour (Table 9.4.22) may causes a visual contrast against modern buildings thus generating interest.

Another salient but less obvious point was use of the terms “*inviting*” and “*friendly*” (Table 9.4.22), suggesting a feeling of warmth and safety where one can seek refuge regardless of one’s personal beliefs. This impression might be formed through the traditional architectural style, the cultural experience, and the friendly staff, as identified in the projective questions image (Table 9.4.22). McKercher & Du Cros’s (2002) framework in Table 2.2 specifically points to the gatekeeper’s role in forming more of an impression and in determining the tourists’ expectations before the experience rather than upon experience of the asset itself. Therefore, the staff’s friendly behaviour is seen to play an important role in managing the tourist’s experience.

4.2 Objective 1: To Explore the Image of Chinese temples as a Visitor's attraction in Phuket

Objective one was to explore the image of Chinese temples in Phuket. The main findings firstly give an overview of the triangulation results (Fig. 4.1), then identification of the significant tangible and intangible images of statues/figures/gods, religious/traditional, fascinating, attractive, mysterious, peaceful and unique is discussed (Fig. 4.1).

The triangulation analysis for Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket (Fig. 4.1) shows the top ten results from the three open-ended questions (Table 9.4.12, Table 9.4.15 and Table 9.4.17), the projective questions (Table 9.4.22) and projective drawings (Table 9.4.24 and Table 9.4.25), with all duplicated themes omitted from the open-ended and projective questions.

Figure 4.1 Triangulation Analysis Results of the Image of Chinese Temples/Shrines in Phuket from the Perspective of International Tourists.

Note: Red = Significant image in all three components

4.2.1 Holistic Tangible Image of Chinese Temples/Shrines in Phuket

The result of the tangible aspect of the holistic image of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket for objective one is discussed next.

4.2.2 Statues, Figures and Gods

The most recognised tangible images perceived by international tourists at Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket were statues, figures and gods (Fig. 4.1). As the discussed earlier in the respondent's profile, the psychological influence on international tourists' perceptions may spring from a deep subconscious need for archetypal figures that is specific to their age or personal situations (Lang, Chan, & Ragvald, 2005; Vazire & Carlson, 2011; Groesbeck, 1975; Erikson 1956). However, this section discusses the impact of statues, figures and gods at Phuket's Chinese temples/shrines from a tourism perspective.

4.2.2.1 Open-ended Results

The breakdown of Fig. 4.1, showed that statues, figures and gods were ranked number one in the open-end questions relating to images that first came to mind (Table 9.4.12), but third in the distinctive features (Table 9.4.15) of the text based responses (Nghiem-Phú, 2014). The open-ended questions of this study were able to identify the organic interactive experience with the destination (Fig. 2.1). They reveal the conative image (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972) of statues, figures and gods as having a significant impact on tourist subconscious and memory after a visitation, which can lead to re-visitations and recommendations.

4.2.2.2 Projective Results

Next in the projective questions (Table 9.4.22 and Fig.4.1), statues, figures and gods were identified to a high level in the functional attributes, of decorations and to a lower degree in functional holistic area of the view from the inside (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003), as "*images perceived by the audiences*" (Nghiem-Phú, 2014). This shows that the statues, figures and gods are seen as common and functional parts of the temples and shrines from an international tourist's perspective, thus stressing the intrinsic value of the uncommodified assets in Table 2.2 for the community (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002). Although the statues, figures and gods were not shown to be high frequency themes in Table 9.4.23, the 'keyness' of statues, figures and gods, according to Braun and Clarke (2006) was significant in

other parts of the study (Table 9.4.12, Table 9.4.15, Table 9.4.22, Table 9.4.24 and Table 9.4.37) and in the overall context of the study after triangulation (Fig. 4.1).

4.2.2.3 Drawing Results

Using of the Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing (Fig 3.4), the experiential function of physical and emotional themes embedded in the respondents' drawings can be described (Riley, 2001). Statues, figures and gods were the second highest items in the projective drawings (Table 9.4.24), as "*images created by the destination*" (Nghiem-Phú, 2014). Table 9.4.24 indicates that most statues, figures and gods were unknown and genderless in character, while the feeling associated with the statues, figures and gods were unique, fascinating and attractive (Table 9.4.26). This specifies, as stated in Table 2.2, that international tourists know very little about the importance of the sites (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002) and the items in them, but are fascinated and attracted by them, thus making statues, figures and gods unique. The importance and uniqueness is further expressed by the composition elements in the central positioning and medium size of the drawn statues, figures and gods by respondents (Table 4.1, Fig. 9.4.21a and Fig. 9.4.21b). Therefore, the composition elements are useful insights when marketing a destination (Cai, 2002).

4.2.2.4 The Impact of Statues, Figures and Gods Images on Tourism

So, from a tourism viewpoint (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002) Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket have extrinsic values for international tourists (Table 2.2) because statues, figures and gods are the focal points for travellers that cause fascination. Whether visitors are marvelling at or paying respect to idols (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009), the desire to consume a cultural (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002) or religious experience exists. The lack of information (Table 9.4.4) about the statues, figures and gods enhance the level of curiosity (Table 9.4.11) and attraction. Furthermore, statues, figures and gods were the most suggested image by respondents to use for promoting Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket (Table 9.4.37).

4.2.3 Holistic Intangible Image of Chinese Temples/Shrines in Phuket

The findings of the intangible characteristics of the holistic image of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket for objective one follow.

4.2.4 Religious/Traditional

Religious and traditional feelings were very highly recognised as one would expect in a place of worship (Fig. 4.1). Compelling feelings of a holy atmosphere were also found in Shuo, Ryan, and Liu's (2009) study.

4.2.4.1 Open-ended Results

The subdivision of Fig. 4.1, showed that religious and traditional feelings came second in the open-end questions of images that first came to mind (Table 9.4.12), which included images of "*Chinese culture, history, rituals, ancestral place of worship, Lao Tzu and Shaolin kung fu*". In the distinctive features (Table 9.4.15) section, religious and tradition were in fourth place with such imagery as "*cultural stories on the wall, history of the shrine, Feng Shui, no monks and the Vegetarian Festival*", while feelings of religion and tradition, for example, "*cultural history, religious thoughts about god, a sacred feeling, holy, seriousness, complicated rituals and watch the rules*", were the most frequent first impressions upon entering (Table 9.4.18). The qualitative accounts of respondents disclose a mixture of organic, cognitive and affective image sources (Fig. 2.1) that form the impressions of religious and traditional ideas. Additionally, these concepts could be formed by similar travel experiences (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972) by tourists visiting their respective places of worship back home (Fig. 2.1). Social norms and behaviour may also affect the cognitive image when entering another place of worship. Yet it is clear to see that the overall responses lacked specific details about the Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket.

4.2.4.2 Projective Results

The projective questions (Table 9.4.22), exposed a distinction between religious and traditional imagery while the intangible aspects of religiousness were counted more often than traditional (Table 9.4.23). Religious impressions in Fig. 9.4.1 were seen to be well established in the holistic domains of the view from inside, activities and feelings, with a presence in the psychological characteristics of religious shrine. This combination created a strong religious uniqueness in the Echtner and Ritchie (2003) model. Interestingly, the smell is also described as religious in the functional characteristics part. The cause of this religious smell is in the use of incense sticks and is common amongst Chinese temples and shrines (Jetter, Guo, McBrian, & Flynn, 2002). On the other hand, traditional is regarded as a tangible aspect in the form of traditional architecture (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009) and is prevalent in the functional characteristics sector (Fig. 9.4.1).

4.2.4.3. Drawings Results

The projective drawings identified the key images that are associated with intangible religious and traditional feelings (Fig. 9.4.26b) for marketing purposes. Fig. 4.2 shows the drawn items and the levels of association with a specific image. Firstly, religious is most connected to the courtyard image which agrees with the religious view inside in Fig. 9.4.1. However, it was one of the least drawn items (Table 2.24). This perhaps can be explained by the fact that the courtyard is a general area and maybe deemed less important to international tourists. In contrast, offerings of tea cups and fruits on a plate (Fig. 9.4.33b) were drawn very frequently and strongly linked to religious. The items of ornaments, ding/pot/cauldron, doorway/archway and altar were moderately associated to religious and objects of divinations, religious artefacts, banners and columns were the least associated. However, traditional was mostly related to the image of the roof, while the gate and musical instruments were moderately associated. The burnt offering, courtyard, ding/pot/cauldron, placard/plate/sign and religious artefact were less associated with the image of traditional.

Figure 4.2 Drawn items and the levels of association with religious and traditional feelings.

Religious	Traditional	
Courtyard	Roof	High level of association
Offerings	Gate	
Ornaments	Musical Instruments	
Ding/Pot/Cauldron	Burnt Offering	
Doorway/Archway	Courtyard	
Altar	Ding/Pot/Cauldron	
Divination	Placard/Plate/Sign	
Religious Artefact	Religious Artefact	
Banner		
Column		

4.2.4.4 The Impact of Religious and Traditional Images on Tourism

Finally, McKercher & Du Cros (2002) in Table 2.2 highlight the importance of Chinese temple and shrine managers understanding the tourists' needs and limitations. In addition, it may be surmised from responses to the images that first came to mind (Table 9.4.12) and distinctive features (Table 9.4.15) that very little is known about the importance of Chinese temples/shrines that are being visited by tourists in Phuket. However, promotional managers may seize the opportunity to educate tourists (Shuo, Ryan, &

Liu, 2009) as found in Table 9.4.38 and Table 9.4.39, both on and off the site using religious and tradition imagery (Lang, Chan, & Ragvald, 2005) of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket.

4.2.5 Fascinating

Strong feelings of fascination were discovered through this study (Fig. 4.1). This was more pronounced than the findings of Shuo, Ryan, and Liu's (2009) research.

4.2.5.1 Open-ended Results

Overall the feeling of fascination for international visitors (Table 9.4.18) was more surprising and significant when compared with other results. For example, fascination was the main reason for visiting (Table 9.4.11), the third highest feeling and experience in the projective questions (Table 9.4.22), the third highest spoken theme in the projective drawings (Table 9.4.25) and the one of the main reasons for recommending a visit to a Chinese temple or shrine in Phuket (Table 9.4.35), thus indicating the effect of fascination on the cognitive, affective and conative (Fig. 2.1) processes (Gartner, 1993), which may be connected to the need for social exploration to fulfil an individual's curiosity (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009).

4.2.5.2 Projective Results

Feelings of fascination were totally positioned in the unique dimension of the Echtner and Ritchie (2003) model (Fig 4.1). Although fascination was ranked moderately, its significance is emphasised in the other results of this study (Table 9.4.11, Table 9.4.25 and Table 9.4.35). Fascination may be aroused by a subconscious psychological need, a focused intention to learn and understand or merely a passing interest. Nevertheless, the feeling of fascination generated in an individual also seems to have a relationship in their likelihood to recommend (Table 9.4.35) a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket.

4.2.5.3 Drawings Results

The projective drawings identified the tangible "*images created by the destination*" (Nghiem-Phú, 2014) to feelings of fascination (Table 9.4.26). Fig. 4.3 exposed the architecture as having the highest level of association with fascination, whereas the chimney, banners and windows were associated much lower. The drawings of the Chinese temples/shrines architecture that caused fascination were mostly created by males who were accompanied by another individual. A few drawings were incomplete and drawn in three-dimensions (Fig 3.4). The overall scale of the drawn image was medium to large.

Sometimes a thin pencil line was used while the most applied colours were white, then yellow and brown. On the other hand, most single international tourists drew the chimney in three-dimensions. More than half drew the chimney down the right side of the canvas using white, yellow, and black colours. Males who were accompanied by someone drew banners small to medium in scale across the top of the canvas. Lastly, single tourists with friends illustrated windows to a medium scale.

Figure 4.3 Drawn items and the levels of association with feelings of fascination.

Fascinating	
Architecture	High level of association
Chimney	
Banner	
Window	
	Low level of association

4.2.5.4 The Impact of Fascinating Images on Tourism

In conclusion, fascination could be said to generate the strongest feeling overall when visiting a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket. Even within the limited visitation time (Table 2.2 and Table 9.4.4), international tourists form a firm cognitive (Gartner, 1993) and modified-induced image (Gunn, 1972). Therefore, the feeling of fascination is more consciously experienced, as revealed in the first impressions (Table 9.4.18) and the reasons for visiting (Table 9.4.11), compared to the subconscious projective questions (Table 9.4.22) where fascination was less frequent. This is valuable for temple managers and destination image managers because the experience of fascination can be used to entice tourists to consume the destination (Table 2.2) based on the conscious experience, thus leading to organic recommendations (Gartner, 1993) from other international tourists to visit (Table 9.4.35).

4.2.6 Attractive

The feelings of attractiveness experienced by respondents at Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket were high overall (Fig. 4.1).

4.2.6.1 Open-ended Results

In the responses to the open-ended questions in Table 9.4.12 and Table 9.4.15 the level of attraction was low, but in the first impressions (Table 9.4.18) it was found to be at a medium level. While a closer examination of the first impressions responses such as “*beautiful, pretty from the outside, stands out*

against the busy background and the beautiful architecture is in harmony with nature” reveal more general images of attractive which are set in the context of their surroundings. Therefore, Gartner’s (1993) and Gunn’s (1972) models may suggest that the effect of the modified-induced and cognitive image (Fig 2.1) of attractive is weak, but all inclusive of the destination.

4.2.6.2 Projective Results

Furthermore, the results in projective questions (Table 9.4.22) also support the findings of the open-ended questions. Table 9.4.22 points strongly to the psychological characteristics (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003) of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket as being attractive and more specifically viewed as a cultural attraction. Likewise, the presence of attractive is located in the views from the inside and outside of the functional holistic sector and in the environment of the psychological attributes component (Fig. 9.4.1), further strengthening the idea of attractiveness as being comprised of a combination of general images. Therefore, the results might suggest that the atmosphere and scenery (Lee & Lee, 2009) add to a sense of attractiveness overall.

4.2.6.3 Drawings Results

In contrast, the Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing (Fig 3.4) was able to identify tangible images that were linked to attractive as “*images created by the destination*” (Nghiem-Phú, 2014). Burnt offerings and the general public were found to be most associated images with feelings of attraction (Fig. 4.4). The other images of the altar, artwork, flag and outside wall were highly linked to attractive. Moderate levels of attraction were attributed to images of the banner, chimney, donation safe/box, gate, nature, offerings, placard/plate/sign, statues/figures/gods, architecture and calligraphy. The doorway/archway, stairs/steps/ramp, roof and window were less attractive. Interestingly, most single European women drew burnt offerings such as candle with a flame (Table 9.4.24) to a small scale and sometimes at the bottom of the canvas (Fig 3.7), while using white, yellow, orange, and brown colours occasionally, whereas an equal number of European and Asian respondents who visited with a friend mostly drew small to medium size groups of people that were sometimes praying. The most common location of the general public in the drawings was to the left and sometimes to the bottom left or bottom of the canvas (Fig 3.7). The pencil pressure force was noted to be occasionally hard, possibly showing high energy (Foley & Mullis, 2008) and focus. While white was used the most, black was applied sometimes and blue, yellow, and purple were seldom employed. Fascinatingly, just over half of European and Asian

respondents that drew members of the public spent 1-100 THB at the Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket.

Figure 4.4 Drawn items and the levels of association with feelings of attraction.

Attractive	
Burnt Offering	<p>High level of association</p> <p>Low level of association</p>
General Public	
Altar	
Artwork	
Flag	
Outside Wall	
Banner	
Chimney	
Donation Safe/Box	
Gate	
Nature	
Offerings	
Placard/Plate/Sign	
Statues/Figures/Gods	
Architecture	
Calligraphy	
Doorway/Archway	
Stairs/Steps/Ramp	
Roof	
Window	

The use of burnt offerings (Table 9.4.9) is known to change the mood of an individual to meditative, purifying and healing states (Jetter, Guo, McBrian, & Flynn, 2002), in addition to repelling demons, invoking the spirit of the deities and to please the gods (Lin, Krishnaswamy, & Chi, 2008). The specific use of incense sticks can alter a person's psychological state (Ferdenzi, Schirmer, Roberts, Delplanque, Porcherot, Cayeux, Velazco, Sander, Scherer, & Grandjean, 2011) through its multi-sensory experience of touch (when praying), smell (being religious and intoxicating, in Table 9.4.22) and sight (through smoke, in Fig. 9.4.12b). Therefore, the impression of burnt offerings are salient and memorable images (Table 9.4.24) when marketing Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket to single tourists, whereas, promotional pictures of other tourists visiting may indeed encourage potential groups of tourists across cultures to visit and possibly spend money.

4.2.6.4 The Impact of Attractive Images on Tourism

Hence, the overall attractiveness of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket exists and is noted as one of the main reasons for recommending a visit (Table 9.4.35). Furthermore, the experience of using burnt offerings (Table 9.4.9, Table 9.4.11 and Table 9.4.38) as a cultural activity for the consumption of tourists (McKercher & Du Cros 2002) is present and maybe enhanced as stated in Table 2.2 with the tourists' needs and sustainable practises (Sakolnakorn, Naipinit, & Kroeksakul, 2013) in mind. Lastly, the purposeful selection of cultural tourists (Fig. 9.2.1) within promotional material may also attract the targeted tourist segment.

4.2.7 Mysterious

The intangible impressions of mystery were moderately experienced by international visitors at Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket (Fig. 4.1).

4.2.7.1 Open-ended Results

The first impressions (Table 9.4.18) of mysterious were described as "*secretive, hidden, colourful outside and dark inside, going into the darkness, forgot the rest of the world, enchanted, magical and lucky*". The responses indicate that the experience of the visitation as having a powerful impact on the modified-induced and cognitive image (Fig 2.1). Images of magic, but more specifically luck, may have been formed by an accumulation of respondents' experiences (Gartner, 1993), organically induced information by word of mouth or covertly induced destination stories (Gunn, 1972). This would possibly link with the 14.7% of international tourists that recommended activities such as praying because visitors could "*make a wish*" (magic) or engage in acts of divination for "*luck*" (Table 9.4.37).

4.2.7.2 Projective Results

The findings of mystery in projective questions (Table 9.4.22) were not strong overall, but were more frequent in occurrence (Table 9.4.23), thus strengthening its presence. The intangible quality of mysteriousness is seen across (Fig. 9.4.1) the psychological characteristics hemisphere of the atmosphere and culture and is also present in the functional holistic part of layout and inside view (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003). Similarly, Shuo, Ryan, and Liu's (2009) study also found that visitors experienced high levels of mystery from the religion at Taoist temples.

4.2.7.3 Drawings Results

The Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing (Fig 3.4) identified the tangible “*images created by the destination*” (Nghiem-Phú, 2014). Fig. 4.5 highlights the religious ornaments that cause the highest sense of mystery as the ding/pot/cauldron, statues/figures/gods and the alter. While offerings (pineapples in particular), burnt offering, musical instruments and kneeler pads cause the lowest sense of mystery. Single male and female international tourist mostly drew the ding/pot/cauldron, sometimes with drawn legs, but always with incense inside of it and sometimes with smoke (Fig. 9.4.12a and Fig. 9.4.12b). The 3-dimensional view-point was mostly from the front and above (Fig 3.5) and items were generally in medium scale. This group mostly used white, then black, orange, and sometimes blue colours. Next, most single European females illustrated unknown statues/figures, then images of lions (Table 9.4.24). Interestingly, less than half of the drawing were incomplete, with most items being located across the top (Fig. 3.8) or in the centre (Fig. 3.7). White was the most used colour, then orange and brown. Finally, the altar was either drawn as a solid block (Fig. 9.4.9b) or as a table by male and female tourists from native English speaking countries who were accompanied with a friend or family member. The altar was commonly in 3 dimensions from the perspective of front-above (Fig. 3.5), using predominately white and sometimes purple and brown.

Figure 4.5 Drawn items and the levels of association with feelings of mysterious.

Mysterious	
Ding/Pot/Cauldron	High level of association Low level of association
Statues/Figures/Gods	
Alter	
Offerings	
Burnt Offering	
Musical Instruments	
Kneeler Pads	

4.2.7.4 The Impact of Mysterious Images on Tourism

In summary, the tangible religious items (Fig. 4.5) that cause an intangible mystery for international tourists have been discovered. Furthermore, the information about these items at the site might be developed for the education of international tourists’ (Table 9.4.37) cultural consumption (McKercher & Du Cros 2002). This would allow the careful and controlled commodification of the cultural attraction. In addition, the religious items’ (Fig. 4.5) imagery could be used to promote the

Chinese temples and shrines and improve the information style, quality and accuracy received by the tourists before they visit (Fig 2.2).

4.2.8 Peaceful

The feelings of peace experienced by respondents at Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket were high in total (Fig. 4.1).

4.2.8.1 Open-ended Results

The intangible first impressions of peace such as “*tranquillity, relaxation, quiet, sanctity, inner peace, things moving slowly and feelings of timelessness*” ranked third in Table 9.4.18. The cognitive images (Gartner, 1993) of peace are likely to have been formed by the organic experience (Fig 2.1) of visiting a Chinese temple or shrine (Table 9.4.4). Shuo, Ryan, and Liu’s (2009) research found that a search for peace was a moderate factor for visiting a Chinese temple or shrine in Phuket. Yet, peace was rarely a reason for recommending a visitation based in this study (Table 9.4.35).

4.2.8.2 Projective Results

Nevertheless, the peaceful “*images perceived by the audiences*” (Nghiem-Phú, 2014) were most potent in the atmosphere, followed by the feeling at the location, and least powerful in the environment (Table 9.4.22). Moreover, the presence of peaceful was restricted to the psychological domain (Fig 4.1), but covered all the all aspects of characteristics, holistics and attributes (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003), thus showing a strong peaceful sense inside and round the boundaries of the Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket, but with a reduced effect outside the perimeter.

4.2.8.3 Drawings Results

The projective drawings revealed the tangible images associated with peace where the open-ended and projective questions could not, although peace was not evident in Table 9.4.26 as a strong image with any items when compared to other themes. Building features (Fig. 4.6) emerged with the highest associations of peace. The first building feature was the roof and was mostly drawn by female native English speakers with no religious belief using more red, white and green colours. Next was the gate drawn by international tourists that visited with a friend using pencil only, while the columns were sometimes linked with peace. The stairs/steps/ramps, doorway/archway, architecture, chimney, firecracker

room and outside wall were rarely mentioned. Interestingly, the visitation length was not a factor with the experience of peace for the respondents who drew building features items and associated them with peace.

Figure 4.6 Drawn items and the levels of association with feelings of peace.

Peace	
Roof	High level of association
Gate	
Column	
Stairs/Steps/Ramp	
Doorway/Archway	
Architecture	
Chimney	
Firecracker Room	
Outside Wall	

4.2.7.4 The Impact of Peaceful Images on Tourism

In conclusion, the overall exploration of peaceful (Table 9.4.18, Table 9.4.22 and Fig. 4.6), revealed the experience of the feeling to be confined within the site grounds (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009). In addition, the experience of peace is not time bound. This is significant because tourists are limited by time (Fig 2.2). Therefore, having identified peace as a salient image (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009), it can thus be marketed as a serene destination to a variety of cultural tourists (McKercher & Du Cros 2002), using the general building feature images of the Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket.

4.2.8 Unique

Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket are seen to be unique overall (Table 9.4.22), for international tourists (Fig. 4.1). The findings of uniqueness are discussed next.

4.3 Objective 2: To Identify the Uniqueness of Chinese Temples in Phuket

Objective two was to identify the uniqueness of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket. The main findings examine the open-ended questions, projective questions, projective drawings (Fig. 4.1) and the implications within in a cultural tourism context (Table 2.2). The overall experience of visiting was found to be unique and the most salient unique images are of the altar, calligraphy, columns, ding, pot and cauldron, divination, donation safe or box, firecracker room, lanterns, nature, outside walls, placards, plates and signs, roof and statues, figures and gods.

4.3.1 Open-ended Results

Table 9.4.18 identified the intangible first impressions of unique as being moderately placed compared to religious/traditional and peaceful. Feelings of uniqueness were described as “*extraordinary, important, unusual and different from the other buildings, something special is inside and totally different than Thai temples*”, indicating some aspect of the architecture as being unique, but remaining ambiguous towards the specific features. More significant is the response of the Chinese temples/shrines as being “*important*”. This is also noted in Table 9.4.11 as one of the reasons for visiting, although its position is weak overall, possibly due to the lack of information about the site (Table 9.4.7). Educational marketing about the culture (Table 9.4.38 and Table 9.4.39) may increase the effect of the (Fig 2.1) induced decision to travel to the destination (Gunn, 1972) and the affective images that cause visitations through word of mouth (Gartner, 1993).

4.3.2 Projective Results

Similarly, the projective questions (Table 9.4.22) agreed with the findings in the open-ended questions. The unique image of the Chinese temple and shrine architecture was present in the functional and psychological characteristics (Fig 4.1). However, the more significant finding was that the experience of the visitation was found to be unique overall in Echtner and Ritchie’s (2003) model. This is explained by the religious and cultural feelings at the site (Table 9.4.22), while a sense of peace (Table 9.4.22) and fascination (Table 9.4.11, Table 9.4.18, and Table 9.4.25) also added to the experience of uniqueness (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009).

4.3.4 Drawing Results

The projective drawings analysis (Fig 3.4) revealed thirteen tangible objects which all had the highest levels of uniqueness (Table 9.4.26). These were the altar, calligraphy, columns, ding, pot and cauldron, divination, donation safe or box, firecracker room, lanterns, nature, outside walls, placards, plates and signs, roof and statues, figures and gods.

The Taoist altar is the central point of worship that contains many religious artefacts. It made a significant impression on international tourists as the altar was identified as unique, colourful, attractive, religious and of specific dimensions (Table 9.4.26). Interestingly, Verellen (1995) describes the Taoist altar like a mountain which has an enclosed and secretive space that encapsulates the Tao. This may

explain the overall psychological image. As one respondent said, *“it is where you go to pray in private”* (Fig. 9.4.9b).

The uniqueness of Chinese calligraphy as a purely decorative visual feature may enhance the memory of it (Schmitt, Pan, & Tavassoli, 1994). This can be seen in Table 9.4.24 where a higher number of calligraphy impressions were depicted and is illustrated in examples in Fig. 9.4.10. The dimensions of the typography might also increase the attractiveness and fascination of it. As one tourist said, *“I liked the big Chinese writing, looks pretty”*.

Columns were identified as unique and colourful while their decorative features of dragons (Fig. 9.4.11) and calligraphy inscriptions were expressed as having both fascinating and religious qualities. As one tourist said, *“These columns have green dragons and stand out”*.

The ding’s, pot’s or cauldron’s uniqueness and dimensions were the most prominent features for international tourists. This is because of the traditional location in front of the main temple/shrine (Fig. 9.4.20 and Fig. 9.4.28) or on the altar (Fig. 9.4.12). As one respondent said, *“The first thing I saw was this big metal thing in the middle”*. The religious and traditional functions were also mentioned. However, colourful was an unusual finding as the ding, pot or cauldron is neither colourful in reality nor in the colour usage findings in Fig. 9.4.12a, where the top three colours are white, brown and black.

Objects of divination such as Moon Blocks or Jiaobei Blocks and yarrow sticks in a box which were on or close to the altar (Fig. 9.4.13b) were revealed as unique with varying dimensions and decorativeness that induced emotions of religiousness and respect. For instance, *“I saw these crescent shaped things on the altar, not sure what they were for, may be religious”* and *“I pray and use lucky sticks and see my future”*.

The donation safes/boxes were generally located in front of the shrine area. As a unique image, international tourists described them as fascinating, attractive, well-known and *“large”* in size (Fig. 9.4.14a).

The firecracker room (Fig. 9.4.15) was identified as unique (as one international tourist said, *“I have never seen anything like it before”*), then colourful, as *“it was colourful box, where you let off firecrackers”*. Next was noisy and age which was possibly from the burnt material left over. Finally, feelings of ascending might refer to the driving away of bad spirits and lifting of an individual’s spirit (Lin, Krishnaswamy, & Chi, 2008).

Lanterns (Fig. 9.4.16) were perceived as unique, religious and colourful, such as “*I only saw them inside the shrine*”, “*they look religious*” and “*red lanterns*”. Then mentioned were its dimensions, while the decorative aspects are highlighted in Table 9.4.12 and Table 9.4.15.

The daily features of nature (Fig. 9.4.17b), such as bushes, hedges, trees and clouds were interestingly seen as unique, varying in form, attractive and fascinating, which added to the decorative feeling of the Chinese temple/shrine.

The outside wall (Fig. 9.4.34b) was voiced as unique and attractive while “*the outside wall hid the larger space inside*”, which perhaps caused fascination. Decorations like “*flags and lanterns*” were also noticed on the outside walls.

Placards, plates and signs (Fig. 9.4.19a) were viewed as focal points, while the uniqueness was identified by its dimensions and the ability to attract the eye, triggering fascination with the traditional Chinese calligraphy, such as “*I saw Pud Jor sign above the door*”.

The roof was identified a significant feature of the Chinese temple/shrine as it was defined as unique (Eberhard, 1967), having “*a traditional Chinese style roof*”, being fascinating, varying in dimensions and attractive.

The stairs, steps and ramp were described by their dimensions, then with fascination, uniqueness, attraction and decorativeness. As one visitor said, “*the steep ramp had a design, but you could not see inside temple*” (Fig. 9.4.23b).

The Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing shows that most items were drawn from the front view (Table 4.1), although the ding, pot and cauldron, objects of divination and the donation box are drawn from a front and above point of view (Fig 3.5). The size of most of the drawn objects were in general proportion to the actual physical objects and located in the correct locations of the canvas regularly. Interestingly, the donation box was mostly illustrated in 3 dimensions and appeared in the bottom left corner while the firecracker room is depicted down the left-hand side of the canvas. Finally, the column, the ding, pot and cauldron, objects of divination, the donation safe or box, lantern and placards plates and signs had calligraphic associations.

Table 4.1 The thirteen unique drawn elements view, size, location and calligraphic associations for overall respondents.

Item	View	Size	Location	Calligraphy
Altar	Font	M	Centre	-
Calligraphy	Font	S	Centre	-
Column	Font	M	Across the Centre	Yes
Ding/Pot/Cauldron	Front Above	M	Centre	Yes
Divination	Front Above	S	Centre	Yes
Donation Safe/Box	Front Above Right	M	Bottom Left	Yes
Firecracker Room	Front	M	Down the Left	-
Lantern	Front	S	Across the Top	Yes
Nature	Front	M	Across the Top	-
Outside Wall	Front	M	Across the Centre	-
Placard/Plate/Sign	Front	M	Centre	Yes
Roof	Front	L	Across the Top	-
Statues/Figures/Gods	Front	M	Centre	-

The predominant colour of Chinese temples and shrines is red (and in some cases red and yellow), yet white was the predominant colour used (possibly by default) for nine of the thirteen unique images (Table 9.4.33). Previous colour research has described the perception of white as being good, passive, the most pleasing compared to other colours and eliciting the lowest level of dominance (Madden, Hewett, & Roth, 2000; Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994). This is significant as peaceful is one the first impression felt by visitors (Table 9.4.18) and is experienced in the overall atmosphere of the Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket (Table 9.4.22).

Red and yellow on the other hand are known to be more arousing, active, warm, visible and vibrant colours and are associated with higher states of anxiety although their meanings vary across cultures (O'Connor, 2011; Madden, Hewett, & Roth, 2000; Jacobs & Hustmyer, 1974; Spielberg, Gorsuch, & Lushene, 1970; Wilson, 1966; Gerard, 1958). Therefore, red and yellow's energising properties (De Bortoli & Maroto, 2001) may be associated with the drawer subconsciously expressing areas of fascination. Table 4.2 shows that nine of the thirteen unique items were mainly coloured red and yellow with six out of the nine mentioning fascination. Interestingly, yellow was the second main colour used to illustrate statues, figures and gods with fascination ranking second (Table 9.4.26). Yet, objects like lanterns that are known to be red, were firstly coloured red, but had no significant mention of fascination.

Red was the second most used colour when representing calligraphy and received a low mention of fascination by international tourists. Interestingly, it is very uncommon to see red Chinese calligraphy in a Chinese temple/shrine because of its connotations with imminent death in Chinese and Asian cultures (He, 2009). Therefore black, yellow and gold Chinese calligraphy are more common in a Chinese temple/shrine. Most columns and roofs are red and were correctly coloured with some references to fascination. Placards, plates and signs, outside walls and firecracker rooms are sometimes red, but were coloured red more often with only the placards, plates and signs, and the outside walls having some mentions of fascination. Finally, red altars are less common in Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket but were coloured red more frequently, however no remarks to fascination were made.

Brown and black are associated with the ideas of masculinity, power, strength, masterfulness and formality (Madden, Hewett, & Roth, 2000; Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994). Black was used more often than red for calligraphy as one would expect, while brown was used mostly for the ding, pot and cauldron, objects of divination and the donation safe/box, which may be connected to formality and masculinity.

Orange is described as having high arousal properties (Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994) and is in between red and yellow in the colour spectrum and therefore may also be linked to fascination. Orange is observed mostly with the outside walls and lanterns, close to red and yellow (Fig. 9.4.16b).

Green and blue are believed to be calming, gentle and beautiful (Madden, Hewett, & Roth, 2000) and are seen mostly in the depictions of nature (Fig. 9.4.17b), whereas, flesh, pink and purple were not significant in the unique drawing elements.

Table 4.2 The main colours used by overall respondents in the unique drawn items in Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket.

Item	Fascination	Colour 1 st	Colour 2 nd
Altar		White	Red
Calligraphy	Yes	Black	Red
Column	Yes	White	Red
Ding/Pot/Cauldron		White	Brown
Divination		White	Brown
Donation Safe/Box	Yes	White	Brown
Firecracker Room		White	Red
Lantern		Red	White
Nature	Yes	Green	White
Outside Wall	Yes	White	Red
Placard/Plate/Sign	Yes	White	Red
Roof	Yes	White	Red
Statues/Figures/Gods	Yes	White	Yellow

4.3.4 The Impact of Unique Images on Tourism

Finally, the identification of the thirteen uniquely drawn elements gives insight into the most salient images that international tourists remember through their organic (Gunn, 1972) visitation experience (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003). The uniqueness of the experience is highly significant (Fig 4.1) because of the number of visits by international tourists to other Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket. For example, 50.9% had visited between one to three (Table 9.4.4).

Religious/traditional, attractive, mysterious and peaceful feelings may also be attributed to the overall feelings of uniqueness, while fascination is identified as the main reason for visiting a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket (Table 9.4.11). The combination of uniqueness, attractiveness, mysteriousness, peacefulness and fascination (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009) are the motivating factors in visiting other Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket, therefore, increasing the likelihood of recommending (Gunn, 1972) other tourists to visit (Table 9.4.35). Experiencing a religious feeling might be less of a motivating factor for international tourists and more of a recognition of a place of worship as seen in the first impression results (Table 9.4.18). Thus, temple managers and destination image marketers should use the tangible (Table 4.2) and intangible image aspects found in the study to enhance the quality of their sites' information (Table 2.2), so it adds to the extrinsic value (McKercher & Du Cros 2002). Furthermore, they

should offer a range of experiences, such as fascinating, cultural (base on religious and traditional), peaceful, mysterious and unique experiences for international tourist to consume (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009; McKercher & Du Cros 2002) at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket.

4.4 Objective 3: To Examine the Differences in Perception Between Asian and European

Objective three examines the differences in perception between Asian and European tourist groups using the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image (Fig. 1.1). The overall results showed that Asian and European tourists' perceptions differed. Asian tourists related to more religious and traditional imagery while European tourists experienced greater feelings of peace and fascination.

4.4.1 Open-ended Questions by Asians and Europeans

4.4.1.1 First Images that Come to Mind for Asians and Europeans

The images that first came to mind for Asians were similar in comparison to the overall image (Table 4.3) excepting the location and music, which were not mentioned. Religion and tradition emerged as the strongest image (Schmitt, 1996), followed by statues, figures and gods. This can be explained by Asian visitors having more organic experiences (Fig. 2.1). Meanwhile, the exposure by Asian news and movies showing Chinese temples/shrines would be more frequent in Asian countries (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972). The building features of the Chinese temple/shrine made a greater impression on Asians, while the decorations and religious ornaments were less distinct, which may be caused by their familiarity. Likewise, the experience of the atmosphere, such as "*mysterious, peaceful and spiritual*", was more heightened for Asians than Europeans and the overall image. This could be explained by the need to seek spiritual comfort and peace from everyday stress, as found by Shuo, Ryan, and Liu (2009) study. The images of divination, fame and organisation were more pronounced when compared with the overall image, while the architecture, offerings, education and attractiveness were less distinct for Asian international tourists.

The images that first came to mind for Europeans were more limited than overall image and Asian image (Table 4.3). This indicates that European tourists have less exposure to Chinese temples and shrines in general and are more influenced by the induced and affective images (Fig. 2.1) of word of mouth (Table 9.4.5), for example (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972). The most significant images for Europeans are of statues, figures and gods. This once again may point to a subconscious need for archetypal figures (Grosbeck, 1975) or the unconscious search for an identifiable image that can the viewer can relate to. As

Nisbett and Miyamoto (2005) explain, western cultures concentrate on relevant images and use internal rules for categorising and organising the environment. The initial impressions made by statues, figures and gods, decorations, religion/tradition and religious ornaments were highly significant as they were also recognised as the top four distinct features in Table 4.4, while atmosphere, building features and attractiveness were weaker images.

In conclusion, both the Asian and European tourists could benefit from better information (Table 2.2) about the importance of the Chinese temple or shrine both on and off the site (McKercher & Du Cros 2002). Therefore, the images discovered in Table 4.3 should be used to target specific cultural groups.

Table 4.3 The images that first came to mind about Chinese temples/shrines.

Overall Image (%)	Asian Image (%)	European Image (%)
statues/figures/gods (21.2)	religion/tradition (21.4)	statues/figures/gods (26.9)
religion/tradition (19.3)	statues/figures/gods (20.0)	decorations (21.2)
decorations (16.5)	building features (11.9)	religion/tradition (21.2)
religious ornaments (13.7)	decorations (11.9)	religious ornaments (20.2)
building features (9.2)	religious ornaments (11.9)	atmosphere (5.8)
atmosphere (7.3)	atmosphere (10.0)	building features (3.8)
architecture (3.3)	architecture (2.4)	attractive (1.0)
offerings (2.3)	divination (2.4)	
education (1.6)	offerings (2.4)	
attractive (1.4)	fame (1.9)	
divination (1.4)	education (1.4)	
the location (1.2)	organisation (1.4)	
fame (0.8)	attractive (1.0)	
organisation (0.5)		
music (0.3)		

4.4.1.2 Distinctive Features for Asians and Europeans.

The top eight distinct Asian images of decorations, religious ornaments, statues, figures and gods, religion/tradition, building features, architecture, donation box and offerings amazingly matched the overall unique features (Table 4.4). This further suggests that Asian tourists are more familiar with the religious functions of Chinese temples and shrines through their life experiences (Fig 2.1) and thus are more naturally aware of the religious ornament images (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972). The characteristics

of fame and smell however, were more noticeable to Asian international tourists as they focus on objects in an all-inclusive manner through their similarities and relationships with the environment (Nisbett & Miyamoto, 2005). The location, attractiveness, atmosphere and music were considered less distinctive images.

The distinctive features for Europeans were of statues, figures and gods (Table 9.4.24 and Table 9.4.37) and decorations were considered noteworthy (Table 4.4). This was followed by religion/tradition and religious ornaments; however, the donation box image was more significant to European tourists due to its visible location and uniqueness (Fig. 9.4.30a). Offerings, the location, the architecture and the fame of the temple/shrine were less important. The results further suggest that European tourists have less organic images (Fig. 2.1) formed by their life experiences (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972) about Taoist religious items and customs.

Therefore, the McKercher & Du Cros (2002) model in Table 2.2 could be used to develop the assets' extrinsic aspects that European tourists find unique, attractive and informative while preserving the intrinsic functional features for Asian tourists.

Table 4.4 The distinctive features of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket.

Overall Image (%)	Asian Image (%)	European Image (%)
decorations (24.3)	decorations (26.5)	statues/figures/gods (24.8)
religious ornaments (18.7)	religious ornaments (17.3)	decorations (23.3)
statues/figures/gods (17)	statues/figures/gods (15.0)	religion/tradition (16.5)
religion/tradition (11.7)	religion/tradition (12.8)	religious ornaments (15.8)
building features (7.6)	building features (6.2)	building features (7.5)
architecture (5.0)	architecture (5.8)	donation box (6.8)
donation box (4.7)	donation box (5.3)	offerings (2.3)
offerings (3.6)	offerings (3.1)	the location (1.5)
the location (2.6)	fame (2.7)	architecture (0.8)
smell (1.6)	smell (2.2)	fame (0.8)
atmosphere (1.2)	the location (1.3)	
fame (1.2)	attractive (0.9)	
attractive (0.4)	atmosphere (0.4)	
music (0.3)	music (0.4)	

4.4.1.3 First impressions upon entering a Chinese Temple for Asians and Europeans

The first impressions for Asian tourists were religious/traditional and fascinating, as with the overall impressions (Table 4.5). Interestingly, Asians reported a higher level of uniqueness attributed to particular objects such as the ding, pot and cauldron and objects for divination used in religious activities (Table 9.4.27). Additionally, the architecture and fame made stronger impressions as first (Table 4.3) and distinctive (Table 4.4) images when compared to the European tourists. This uniqueness is also present in the architecture and placard, plate, sign (fame) in the drawn element of the study (Table 9.4.27), thus indicating the effect of specific objects in religious activities, the architecture and fame to create unique images for Asian tourists (Ross & Wang, 2010).

Next were impressions of peaceful, respectful and spiritual, while architecture was noticeably higher to the overall and European image. After attraction were feelings of joy which were more distinct in Asians than in European tourists. This can be explained by the higher levels of engagement by Asian tourists in religious worship, thus enhancing the joyous impressions (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009) upon first sight. Mystery, energy and decorativeness were less prevalent in comparison to the overall and European image. In contrast, Asians were more sensitive to the organisation and busy environment, as impressions of confusion were also noted.

The first impression for European tourists matched the first five overall impressions of religion and tradition, fascination, peacefulness and respect (Table 4.5). Mysteriousness made a greater impression on European visitors in comparison to the overall and Asian impressions, which leads to the increased awareness of the decorations, which was also noted in Table 4.3 and Table 4.4. Likewise, decorative features were noticeably higher in Table 4.5 when compared to the overall and Asian impressions.

The impression of attraction remained consistent while uniqueness and architecture were surprisingly less impressive when evaluated against the overall and Asian impressions. The lack of uniqueness was associated with the European tourist's deficiency in knowledge about the site, its customs and rituals, therefore possibly enhancing the impressions of religion, tradition, fascination, peacefulness, respect and mystery (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009). Although architecture was perceived as less distinct in the open-ended questions (Table 4.4 and Table 4.5), its uniqueness was revealed in the projective questions (Table 9.4.22), which may suggest it having a deeper subconscious effect.

The feeling of being welcomed or invited was stronger for European tourists, perhaps as they considered themselves outsiders to the culture and temple. Higher levels of energy were also noted

compared to Asian visitors. Europeans also felt slightly less confusion, and were more conscious of the natural environment around them. Last, came the organisation of the Chinese temple/shrine.

In conclusion, the most overwhelming feelings for both Asian and European tourists remain religious/traditional and fascinating (Table 4.5), although some difference in the first impression are present. The summation of the findings coupled with the McKercher & Du Cros (2002) model (Table 2.2) could allow temple and destination image managers to skilfully craft the consumption of experiences at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket to form stronger cognitive images (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972).

Table 4.5 First impression/feeling when entering a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket.

Overall Image (%)	Asian Image (%)	European Image (%)
religion/tradition (16.1)	religion/tradition (17.9)	religion/tradition (15.6)
fascinating (11.6)	fascinating (11.1)	fascinating (10.8)
peaceful (9.9)	uniqueness (9.9)	peaceful (10.8)
respect (9.7)	peaceful (9.3)	respect (10.4)
spiritual (7.5)	respect (6.8)	mysterious (8.2)
uniqueness (7.4)	spiritual (6.8)	spiritual (7.8)
mysterious (7.2)	architecture (4.9)	decorative (6.1)
attraction (5.0)	attraction (4.9)	attraction (5.2)
decorative (4.3)	joy (4.3)	uniqueness (5.2)
architecture (3.3)	mysterious (4.3)	inviting (3.9)
joy (2.5)	busy (3.7)	architecture (3.0)
energy (2.1)	organisation (3.1)	energy (2.6)
inviting (2.1)	confusion (2.5)	confusion (1.7)
organisation (2.1)	decorative (2.5)	nature (1.7)
nature (1.9)	energy (1.9)	organisation (1.7)
others (7.3)	others (6.1)	others (5.3)

4.4.5 Projective Questions: Asian and European Image

The biggest difference between the two groups (Fig 4.2 and Fig 4.3) was in psychological characteristics and the psychological holistic image that form the uniqueness aspect of a destination elements (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003). Where Asians specified the Taoist religion and Chinese culture that were linked to a religious feeling (Lang, Chan, & Ragvald, 2005) and a pleasant experience (Fig 4.2), meanwhile the European impression was more general, in that the religion was noted to be Chinese and

the cultural traditional aspect led to a peaceful feeling and unique experience (Fig 4.3). Additionally, peaceful as a psychological characteristic was also significant in the atmosphere. Therefore, European tourists' experience of peace (Fig 4.3 and Table 4.5) at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket is salient (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009).

Furthermore, Asian tourists showed a greater difference between the European tourist's image and the overall image (Table 9.4.23). Statues, figures and gods are viewed by Asian visitors as the main decoration, as opposed to colour by Europeans. Interestingly, the results of the drawn elements and themes by Asian and European respondents (Table 9.4.27) show that Asians considered statues, figures and gods as being unique and the main decoration, whereas European tourists see the statues, figures and gods as fascinating (Table 9.4.26) and possibly associate them with being colourful. This occurrence explains the stronger presence of Taoist culture in other Asian cultures leading to some knowledge of the statue, figure and god images and their significance (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009), hence enhancing the memory through the organically induced images (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972). As Asian cultures have a greater number of Chinese temples/shrines and therefore increased chances of visiting (Fig. 2.1), this explains the contrasts in perceptions of an unorganised environment, musical sounds and humid atmosphere (Fig 4.2), which are seen in the attributes of half of both the functional and psychological dimensions (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003).

In summary, the extrinsic value (Table 2.2) for European tourists is in the feelings of peace and fascination, whereas, the intrinsic value for Asian tourists is in the religious and traditional aspects of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket (McKercher & Du Cros 2002). Therefore, temple and shrine managers may consider building a range of tour experiences to match the cultural groups' needs (Table 9.4.38).

4.4.6 Projective Drawings by Asian Respondents

The seven unique objects identified by Asian tourists are the temple architecture, the banners, the ding, pot and cauldron, the objects of divination, placard, plate and sign, the roof and the statues, figures and gods. Table 4.6 shows that the elements were mostly drawn looking front on and were medium in size, however Asians were slightly inclined to draw larger items. The illustrated location of the objects on the canvas suggests that Asians concentrate unique elements mainly in the centre and the top parts of the canvas, such as the statues, figures and gods (Fig. 9.4.28a). Surprisingly, the top position of the Asian drawn statues, figures and gods differed from the overall statues, figures and gods central location (Fig.

9.4.21a). This may be due to the obvious raised location of the deities within the temples and shrine and possibly to a need to express a subconscious reverence of them. Calligraphic associations on the other hand are emphasised in the middle of the canvas.

Table 4.6 The seven unique drawn elements view, size, location and calligraphic associations for Asian respondents.

Item	View	Size	Location	Calligraphy
Architecture	Front	L	Across the Centre	-
Banner	Front	M	Centre	Yes
Ding/Pot/Cauldron	Front Above	M	Centre	Yes
Divination	Front Above	S	Centre	Yes
Placard/Plate/Sign	Front	M	Centre	Yes
Roof	Front	L	Across the Top	-
Statues/Figures/Gods	Front	M	Top	-

Table 4.7 shows that white is the main colour used, then red for banners, placards plates and signs, and roofs, and brown for the temple architecture, the ding, pot and cauldron and objects of divination. Interestingly, black and white are used more than red by Asian (Chinese and western landscape painting, 2011) tourists for the statues, figures and gods. This may be connected with balancing the male and female aspect of the image while expressing its religious formality (Madden, Hewett, & Roth, 2000; Valdez & Mehrabian, 1994).

Table 4.7. The main colours used by Asian respondents in the unique drawn items in Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket.

Item	Colour 1 st	Colour 2 nd
Architecture	White	Brown
Banner	White	Red
Ding/Pot/Cauldron	White	Brown
Divination	White	Brown
Placard/Plate/Sign	White	Red
Roof	White	Red
Statues/Figures/Gods	White	Black

4.4.7 Projective Drawings by European Respondents

The seven unique objects identified by European tourists are the chimney, donation safe or box, firecracker room, lanterns, offerings, outside walls and roof. Table 4.8 reveals that only the offerings and donation safe/box are drawn in 3D from the front above position. Interestingly, Europeans illustrated the position of the donation safe/box in the bottom right hand corner of the canvas, which is opposite to the overall drawings in Table 4.1, which is in the bottom left. Most elements are drawn to a medium and sometimes a small scale. Surprisingly, the location and calligraphic association of the uniquely drawn objects are sporadic, which may suggest a visual and sensory bombardment from a new environment.

Table 4.8 The seven unique drawn elements' view, size, location and calligraphic associations for European respondents.

Item	View	Size	Location	Calligraphy
Chimney	Front	M	Left	Yes
Donation Safe/Box	Front Above Right	M	Bottom Right	Yes
Firecracker Room	Front	M	Down the Left	-
Lantern	Front	S	Across the Top	Yes
Offerings	Front Above	S	Centre	-
Outside Wall	Front	M	Across the Centre	Yes
Roof	Front	L	Across the Top	-

Table 4.9 displays the use of colours by European tourists. White is used the most often, then red. Lanterns are depicted in red as in the overall results (Table 4.2). Strangely, offerings are mostly coloured yellow. This is curious as Table 9.4.24 shows that tea cups and apples on a plate are the most frequently drawn items not red in colour and the author is not able to explain the phenomena.

Table 4.9 The main colours used by European respondents in the unique drawn items in Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket.

Item	Colour 1 st	Colour 2 nd
Chimney	White	Red
Donation Safe/Box	White	Black
Firecracker Room	White	Red
Lantern	Red	White
Offerings	Yellow	White
Outside Wall	White	Red
Roof	White	Red

In conclusion, Asian tourists are notably attracted to the religious and traditional images of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009). This is seen in first images that came to mind (Table 4.3), the distinctive features (Table 4.4), first impression (Table 4.5), the feelings at the location in the projective questions (Fig. 9.4.2) and in the projective drawings of religious objects such as the ding, pot and cauldron, objects of divination and statues, figures and gods (Table 4.6). Meanwhile, European tourists experience more feelings of peace and fascination at Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket. This is evident in first impression (Table 4.5) while the most distinct feeling of peace is seen in the projective questions of location and atmosphere (Fig. 9.4.3). Overall, European tourists are less focused on religious imagery as indicated by the items and their placement on the canvas overall (Table 4.8). Therefore, Chinese temple/shrine and destination image managers should consider designing products and experiences (Table 2.2) that meet the needs of various tourist groups (McKercher & Du Cros 2002).

4.5 Respondent Recommendations

The international tourists' recommendations to others, reasons for recommendations, future admission fee, recommendations for promotional images and pictures, recommendations for promotional activities and recommendations for management are discussed.

4.5.1 Possibility to Recommend

Table 4.10 shows that international tourists are very likely to recommend (97.4%) their experience (Chen & Chen, 2010) at a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket by word of mouth (60.3%), then digital media (38.1%) such as pictures, videos, location shares and reviews on Facebook, Instagram,

Youtube, personal blogs, Trip Advisor, travel blogs and forums. More than half (58.5%) said they would recommend it to friends and family (Boukas, 2008), after specific groups like cultural tourists (Fig. 9.2.1), spiritual travellers, backpackers, like-minded people and then anyone interested in Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket.

The finding thus show that the organic experience (Fig 2.1) of visiting a Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket forms a strong cognitive image that is likely to lead to organically induced referrals through word of mouth and social media (Gartner, 1993). Therefore, Chinese temple managers should explore the use of social media imagery through personal recommendations to raise the profile of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket. This pre-trip information (Table 2.2) would perhaps form a favourable impression before the experience of the asset (McKercher & Du Cros 2002).

Table 4.10 Recommending Chinese Temples in Phuket to Others.

Category	Frequency	%
Recommend Others to Visit		
Yes	149	97.4
No	4	2.6
Total	153	100
How They Would Recommend		
Word of mouth	144	60.3
Internet	91	38.1
None	4	1.7
Total	239	100
Recommend to Whom		
Friends and family	113	58.5
Specific group of people	28	14.5
Anyone interested	22	11.4
Website followers	10	5.2
Like-minded people	9	4.7
Everyone	7	3.6
None	4	2.1
Total	193	100

4.5.2 Reasons for Recommendations

The two main reasons for recommending Chinese temples in Phuket (Table 9.4.35) are firstly to “*experience the tradition and culture*” (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009; McKercher 2004; Poria, Butler, & Airey, 2004) and to see “*the culture with nature*” (Ramkissoon & Uysal, 2011) and secondly because of fascination in “*the history and gods*” (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009). Expressions of fascinations have been highlighted in the visitors’ reasons for visiting (Table 9.4.11), the feeling and experience they got at the location (Table 9.4.22), the drawn descriptions Table 9.4.25 and the first impressions (Table 4.5). Additional factors that may contribute to the attractiveness, uniqueness and mysteriousness include the atmospheric colours (Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, 2007) like white and red (Table 4.2), an ambiance (Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, 2007) such as peace (Table 9.4.18, Table 9.4.22 and Table 9.4.25) and layout and design (Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, 2007) including the space, decorations and views (Table 9.4.22). Exploring religious festivals has also been identified as a reason for visiting Chinese temples/shrines (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009), especially the Vegetarian Festival in Phuket.

In contrast, the reasons for not recommending are confusion about ritual practices, the layout (Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, 2007) the smallness in size and similarity of Chinese temples/shrines.

These findings confirm the international tourists’ desire to consume (Table 2.2) a variety of information and select experiences at the location (Table 9.4.9), thus revealing the cultural attractions’ (Table. 4.22) extrinsic value for tourists (McKercher & Du Cros 2002).

4.5.3 Future Admission Fee

Under forty percent (39.2%) of international tourists said they would be willing to pay an admission fee (Table 9.4.36) with a little less than twenty-five percent (24.8%) suggesting price of 1-50 THB. Before a Chinese temple/shrine decides to develop their asset into a cultural tourist attraction it may be suggested that international tourists buy a ticket so that the temple/shrine can record the current number of visitors (McKercher & Du Cros 2002). This would also assist in the development of a sustainable site through measuring tourist traffic (Table 2.2). The purposes of purchasing a ticket should not be to generate revenue initially, but rather used as a management, informational and promotional tool (Table 9.4.34) that may link to additional information on a website about the temple’s or shrine’s history, Taoist

philosophy or promotional events at the Chinese temple/shrine. This could possibly be used as a covertly induced technique (Fig 2.1) to influence the affective image of international tourists (Gartner, 1993).

4.5.4 Recommendations for Promotional Images and Pictures

Over a quarter (25.8%) of international tourists suggested the images of statues, figures and gods for promoting Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket (Table 9.4.37) and cited such reasons as “*they are at the centre of the shrine, they are the most important*”, “*attractive and colourful*”, “*look mysterious*”, “*looks pure and clean*” and “*look interesting*”. The significance of the statues, figures and gods is revealed in the first images that come to mind (Table 9.4.12), a distinctive (Table 9.4.15) and decorative feature (Table 9.4.22) and is the second highest drawn image (Table 9.4.24) unique image (Fig. 9.4.21a). Similarly, Shuo, Ryan, and Liu’s (2009) study also identified religious idols as being a motivating factor for visiting a Taoist temple. Therefore, the use of statues, figures and gods as archetypal imagery may have a subconscious effect on a tourist’s intention to visit (Vazire & Carlson, 2011; Lang, Chan, & Ragvald, 2005; Groesbeck, 1975). The pictures in Fig. 9.4.21a and Fig. 9.4.28 may provide insight into the compositional arrangement of the statues, figures and gods within promotional material to stimulate fascination or the experience of belief in god (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009; Lang, Chan, & Ragvald, 2005).

A little over one-fifth (20.1%) recommended promotional images of religious ornaments, for example the altar with idols (Fig. 9.4.9b), bells, fortune sticks, incense and candles because “*it gives out light and hope to people praying*”, which is seen in the activities engaged in Table 9.4.9 and the ding, pot and cauldron with the incense (Table 9.4.24) as ancient arts and crafts that express feelings of holiness and mystery (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009).

The next recommendation was the Chinese temple/shrine’s internal and external building features because “*it has atmosphere and feels sacred*” and “*it is very decorative and colourful*” (Table 9.4.22), then image of people doing religious activities such as praying or wish for good luck (Chan, & Ragvald, 2005). After that, the grand architectural aspects are recommended (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009), like the columns (Fig. 9.4.11), the entrance or gate to the shrine and the roof (Fig. 9.4.20), and finally images of Chinese calligraphy (Fig. 9.4.10), ornaments, historical and cultural information and aspects of natural environment that the Chinese temple/shrine is set in (Fig. 9.4.17b).

Therefore, understanding the array of promotional advertising imagery and their meanings may induce (Fig. 2.1) future visitations to Chinese temples and shrines (Shuo, Ryan, & Liu, 2009; Lang, Chan,

& Ragvald, 2005). This would help visitors know more about the importance of the site (Table 2.2) and possibly add to the cultural experience (McKercher & Du Cros 2002).

4.5.5 Recommendations for Promotional Activities

Over a third (36.2%) of respondents requested (Table 9.4.38) educational activities such as learning about the “*history and culture of the religion and shrine*” (Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, 2007; McKercher, 2004; Poria, Butler, & Airey, 2004) with information translated into other languages like English and Russian to meet their needs (Table 2.2). Some said (14.7%) praying to “*make a wish*” or casting fortune sticks for “*luck*” are appealing activities. Other tourists mentioned looking around (13.1%), a (10.6%) guided tour and taking photos and videos to “*post it on my Facebook*”. Notably, looking around and taking photos are the main activities for international tourists visiting Chinese temples/shrine in Phuket (Table 9.4.9). Interestingly, some visitors recommend a “*cultural show*” (Lang, Chan, & Ragvald, 2005; McKercher, 2004) which could be commodified for the consumption of tourists (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002); however, this could require careful consideration on the impact of the local culture and religion. Suggestions then followed including making an offering, meditating activities like “*Tai Chi Chuan*”, eating “*vegetarian food*”, workshops for international tourists to do with making local “*arts and crafts*”, selling souvenirs and fundraising activities to “*generate revenue*” for the Chinese temple (Yang, 2005).

In conclusion, the recommendations for promotional activities by international tourists give valuable ideas into possible development of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket as cultural attractions (Table 2.2). Nevertheless, McKercher and Ho (2006) stress the importance of a site audit by the management and/or independent assessors being taken to assess the practicality and tourism potential in developing the cultural tourism asset of the Chinese temple/shrine (Table 2.2). However, temple and shrine managers may consider simple activities such as directing tourists to selected spots to take photos (Table 9.4.9). This in turn might enhance the involvement and interaction with the site and strengthen the cognitive and induced image (Fig. 2.1) of the Chinese temple or shrine (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972).

4.5.6 Recommendations for Management

The recommendations for temple and shrine managers (Table 9.4.39) showed that more than a third (38.4%) of international tourists suggested standard marketing methods, for example “*street signs and billboard posters*” for potential tourists passing by (Table 9.4.11). This may be turned into an

opportunity to attract visitors who negatively perceive a Chinese temple/shrine to be small from the outside and have a limited amount of time to see it (Table 9.4.4) while walking past it (Table 9.4.35) to enter and enjoy the atmosphere of peace and fascination (Fig. 4.1). Other marketing ideas included advertising in brochures and magazines (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972). Television documentaries are also mentioned, but more interesting is the use of internet and mobile technology as marketing methods. The recommendations included *“having a temple website, using Facebook, Instagram, Youtube, TripAdvisor, Google Maps and QR Codes”*, which are sensible, cost effective and practical initiatives, considering that 29.2% of international tourists engage in taking photos (Table 9.4.9). Additionally, as Phuket endeavours to become a smart city (Phuket Gazette, 2016, The Nation, 2016) the possible use of *“augmented reality technology with mobile application for signs and information around the Chinese temple”* could become a reality (Augmented Reality, 2016; New Scientist; 2016). As Phuket’s Smart City project aims to develop the key areas of smart tourism, smart environment and smart education (The Nation, 2016), Chinese temples/shrines may be able to integrate educational and learning activities (33.9%), for example *“cultural education, statues, figures, and gods including other religious artefacts both at the Chinese temple and on the internet”*, as recommended by respondents. Innovations in technology like augmented reality may overcome awkward physical displays for tourists in religious places. Furthermore, the use of augmented reality tour guides or virtual *“monks and nuns to talk to”* could provide interactivity for tourists while reducing costs and the demand on staff and training staff to speak English or other languages (Table 2.2). Leveraging the use of the internet might also fulfil the smart education objective beyond the scope of Phuket, through the development of resources relating to the Chinese temples/shrines’ history, artefacts, culture and religion online, like the Temple of Heaven (2016). In addition, it may be possible to attract new market segments to Chinese temples in Phuket through educational (Table 9.4.38) seminars such as *“courses teaching people to meditate”* and *“how to pray”* (Table 9.4.9) and thus serve the Phuket’s smart tourism aim. Also, the tourists’ desire to consume a cultural destination (Table 2.2) may be satisfied. Other suggestions included *“creating cultural and pilgrimage tour packages with overseas tour companies for temple Chinese, Russian and European tourists”* that could be developed into *“home stays for westerners”* (Wang, 2011) and result in a *“Chinese temples network both local area and international”* for tourists and pilgrims. On-site activities (Table 2.2) that may be developed like *“Tai Chi and painting”* or *“having food for sale in the temple, food fairs, information about vegetarian food and green tea at the Chinese temples”* could entice potential visitors; however, physical space and cost may restrict such activities (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002).

In conclusion, many possibilities have been suggested by respondents to temple managers which are noteworthy, and they should be studied carefully within the context of each individual temple or shrine.

5 CONCLUSION

The conclusion summarises the key aspects of objectives, methods and results this study, then addresses the practical and academic implications of using projective questions, visual techniques and the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image (Fig. 1.1) within a tourism context. Lastly, Chinese temples and shrines as cultural attractions in Phuket are discussed.

5.1 Review

The main purpose of the study was to explore the current image of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket as cultural tourist attractions. Therefore, a qualitative approach was used involving projective techniques. Three objectives were assessed by using projective methods; these were to explore the overall image, identify the uniqueness and to compare Asian and European perceptions. Additionally, the research aimed to tangibilise (through projective drawings) the intangible aspects of the results (such as fascination) for the benefit of destination image marketers.

The cultural tourism definitions (Table 2.2) from McKercher & Du Cros (2002) were used to contextualise the results from the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image (Fig. 1.1) model. This method was used to assess the viability of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket as cultural attractions for the consumption of international tourists (Table 2.2). The model (Fig. 1.1) contained three parts which used the complementary methodologies of open-ended questions (Table 3.1), projective questions (Table 3.3) and projective drawings (Fig. 3.4).

First, the open-ended questions employed Gartner's (1993) and Gunn's (1972) conceptual frameworks (Fig 2.1). These models assessed the induced or perceived images held and the conative images experienced at the location. The results indicated strengths and weaknesses of the destination image through the travel processes and possible suggestions were offered in the context of the cultural tourism definitions (Table 2.2).

Second, the projective questions were constructed using Echtner and Ritchie's (2003) Components of Destination Image model which allowed for the holistic and systematic qualitative exploration of subconscious images (Table 9.4.22 and Fig. 9.4.1). This technique gave a valuable insight into the underlying functional, psychological and unique images formed by tourists.

Third, the projective drawings used the Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing (Fig. 3.4). This model was based on Riley's (2001) A Systemic-Functional Semiotic Model of the Domain of Drawing (Fig. 2.4) which covers in detail the experiential, interpersonal and compositional elements of a

drawing. In addition, the Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing (Fig. 3.4) identifies important aspects and provides visual examples to destination image marketers.

Finally, the findings from the three components were triangulated to uncover the salient images (Fig. 4.1) and to assess the possibility of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket becoming cultural attractions (Table 2.2).

5.2 Summary of Findings

The first objective explored the overall image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image (Fig. 4.1). The projective questions (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003) uncovered most of the significant images such as religious/traditional, attractive, mysterious, peaceful and unique (Table 9.4.22), whereas the projective drawings (Riley, 2001) identified the important images of statues/figures/gods (Table 9.4.24) and fascination (Table 9.4.25). However, the combination of both projective techniques (Fig 3.4) enhanced the overall findings by triangulation (Fig. 4.1) and provided visual imagery to match the intangible feelings discovered (Table 9.4.26). In addition, the Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing (Fig 3.4) assisted in interpreting the valuable projective drawing data for destination marketers to ponder and use in advertising material.

The second objective was to identify the uniqueness of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image (Fig. 4.1). The projective questions (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003) unmasked the experience of visiting to be unique (Table 9.4.22), but the open-ended responses (Table 9.4.18) did not identify this vital point. The projective drawing themes (Table 9.4.25) supported the overall impression of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket being unique whilst clearly identifying the images associated to the uniqueness (Table 9.4.26). The most salient unique images are of the altar, calligraphy, columns, ding, pot and cauldron, divination, donation safe or box, firecracker room, lanterns, nature, outside walls, placards, plates and signs, roof and statues, figures and gods. Consequently, the findings using projective techniques (Table 2.22 and Fig 3.4) provided extremely significant visual information to temple managers for promoting their unique cultural assets.

The third objective was to compare Asian and European perceptions of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image (Fig. 4.1). The open-ended questions (Table 4.5) in this case agreed with the projective questions findings (Table 9.4.22). It was found that the Asian tourists related to more religious and traditional feelings while European tourists experienced greater feelings of peace. However, the Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing (Fig

3.4) provided a visual insight into the different cogitative image arrangement of objects (Table 4.6 and Table 4.8) between Asian and European tourists, thus giving important graphical information about the cultural groups visiting Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket and the experiential needs and information required (McKercher & Du Cros 2002) to satisfy their fascination (Table 9.4.11).

5.3 Assessment of Research Methodology Used

The use of projective techniques (Table 3.2 and Table 3.3) in tourism research is common and is known to reduce bias (Hsu & Huang, 2008), identify missing variables and uncover salient factors which are vital for the assessment of a destination's image (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003, 1993, 1991). However, studies that use words alone to identify "*images perceived by the audiences*" (Nghiem-Phú, 2014) may not accurately portray an affective visual image of a destination nor be useful to marketers for promoting a destination or be applicable across cultures. For example, the word "*mystic*" (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003) may conjure an array of pictures, yet the word cannot inform a destination manager of what "*mystic*" or mysterious images to use. Also, the statistical analysis of words alone may not assist in the selection of useful images for publication either. Therefore, the range of images for promotional usage based on words alone could be said to be ineffective in terms of marketing images for a destination as in the case of Echtner & Ritchie's (2003) study. Similarly, if the results of the projective questions in Table 9.4.22 were solely relied upon to generate marketing material, they would surely be limited in use. However, within this research it is possible to compare the results of both projective (questions and drawings) data sets and conclude that both aspects are of equal importance for marketing purposes. Therefore, this study endeavoured to combine the use of projective questions and drawings (Fig. 1.1) to extend the destination image theory, analysis and applications for managers and promoters.

Moreover, the author argues for additional visual techniques such as photography, film, video or drawings (Rakić & Chambers, 2011), together with word association investigations, to be strongly considered in tourism destination image studies to uncover the "*images perceived by the audiences*" and the "*images created by the destination*" (Nghiem-Phú, 2014).

The use of photography with tourism studies is not new--it has been said that a picture paints a 1000 words (Garrod, 2009; Stedman, Beckley, Wallace, & Ambard, 2004). Some studies have strived to see the tourist's perception or tourist's gaze by allowing the participants to photographically record imagery from their points of view (Garrod, 2009; Stedman, Beckley, Wallace, & Ambard, 2004). Those methods allow the current tourism image to be assessed while permitting either further reinforcement of

the established tourism image or alternative images to be promoted through marketing. Nevertheless, photographic imagery might capture the exact image that a tourist may see but fail to isolate key features within the image, unless examined in questioning.

Drawing, on the other hand, captures the essence of an image within a non-linear context that is not time- or worldview-dependent (Zweifel & Wezemaal, 2012). Additionally, the drawers can express themselves through (Fig. 3.4) shapes, colours, scales, marks, tones, composition, arrangement and calligraphy (Riley, 2001), while being free to recall the images and features that are the most meaningful and poignant to them within their cultural norms. The cultural difference in perception were specifically identified in objective three (Table 4.6, Table 4.7, Table 4.7 and Table 4.8) and the tangible and intangible features of Phuket's Chinese temples and shrines were uncovered using the Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing (Fig 3.4), thus demonstrating the strength of projective drawing techniques compared to photographic pictures and film, which may be limited in personal representation. However, drawn images from memory may be susceptible to interference and conflict with other experience and images. Nonetheless, the use of photography (Virdee, 2017), film, video or drawings as data collection methods within destination image research must be considered by all researchers for the benefit of the research and its practical application in tourism marketing.

Thus, the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image (Fig. 1.1) has attempted to contribute to the methodological advancement of destination image research. The use of projective questions and drawings (Riley, 2001) within this research has allowed for a comprehensive qualitative investigation of tangible and intangible image dimensions, including the functional and psychological characteristics of the destination image (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003), whilst giving insight into the induced and conative images (Gartner, 1993; Gunn, 1972) and identifying significant images with increased reliability and validity through the process of triangulation (Fig. 1.1). However, the quantitative aspect of Echtner and Ritchie's (2003) Components of Destination Image (Fig. 2.2) was not used in this study as it was exploratory in purpose, but could be used to further establish other important finding that may not be detectable by qualitative analysis alone and provide statistical reliability and validity. Thus, the Triangulation Analysis of a Tourism Destination Image (Fig. 1.1) technique has demonstrated itself to be a holistic tool for the examination of a destination's image and provides destination image managers and organisers with visual imagery and sensory information to construct promotional material (Table 9.4.37) and experiences (Table 9.4.38). Hence, the triangulation of projective techniques is a useful method for other researchers to use in the study of a destination's image as *"this would help convincing readers that*

qualitative interpretive research is not only an art but also a science” (Decrop, 1999). Therefore, the author believes that this study has contributed to the scientific body of knowledge in tourism and to the study of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket and beyond.

5.4 Promoting Chinese Temples and Shrines in Phuket

The wider context of this study was to reveal the cultural attraction image of Phuket by examining the image of Chinese temples and shrines so that it may be used as an alternative image to the sun, sea and sand destination image. The findings highlighted the important and unique aspects of the image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket and showed significant findings from international tourists about how Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket can be promoted using materials like “*street signs, billboard posters, brochures, magazines, TV documentaries, internet and mobile technology*” (Table 9.4.39) and educational activities such as “*learning about the history and culture of the religion and shrine*” (Table 9.4.38). The research attempted to differentiate the intangible image of the annual Phuket Vegetarian Festival from the tangible image of Chinese temples and shrines as all year-round cultural tourist attractions, as both the tangible and intangible images are intrinsically linked and focus around the religious and traditional beliefs with activities that centre around prayers to statues, figures and gods and acts of divination. Specific functional items such as the altar, calligraphy, columns, the ding, pot or cauldron, objects of divination, the donation safe or box, the firecracker room, lanterns, nature, outside walls, placards, plates and signs, the roof and statues, figures and gods have been found to be significant images in the minds of tourists, whereas the psychological images of fascination, religion, tradition, attraction, mysteriousness and peace have been declared as salient to the image of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket. However, before the promotion of any Chinese temple or shrine in Phuket, individual temple and shrine managers and local communities need to further assess their image and evaluate the impetus and feasibility before turning their religious sanctuary into a cultural tourist attraction (Table 2.2). Wat Mangkon Kamalawat temple in Bangkok, Thailand and the Temple of Heaven in Tiantan Park, Beijing, China are successful examples of cultural tourist attractions and should be examined as case studies for the development of local Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket. While Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket are recognised as important cultural and historical points by both managers and tourists, their effects on the local economy and environment needs to be carefully assessed so as not cause adverse conditions through development (McKercher & Du Cros, 2002). With deliberate planning and proactive management, it is

possible for Phuket form an alternative destination image to join the cultural tourism market share and expand its destination image.

6 LIMITATIONS

The limitations of this study were that only seven Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket were used based on their known popularity. In addition, the collect data took place during the months of October and November and not all year round. Finally, as each site is different the findings are not generalizable.

7 FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

Suggestions for future areas of research include a longer period of data collection (preferably a year) to assess the potential tourism appeal and possible at more sites. Should the tourism potential be significant then an in-depth study into the local desirability of the Chinese temple/shrine in Phuket as cultural attractions be undertaken (Table 2.2). This must identify the possible commodification of the local culture and its impacts as defined by McKercher & Du Cros (2002) in Table 2.2. Followed by the sustainability and environmental impact of increased tourists (McKercher & Du Cros 2002). In addition, the technological innovations suggested in this research should also be investigated for the benefit of Chinese temple and shrine in Phuket.

REFERENCES

- An, D. (2014). Understanding Medical Tourists in Korea: Cross-Cultural Perceptions of Medical Tourism among Patients from the USA, Russia, Japan, and China. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 19(10), 1141-1169. doi:10.1080/10941665.2013.840659
- Art Culture Heritage. (2015). Tourism Authority of Thailand. Retrieved April 15, 2015, from <http://www.tourismthailand.org/See-and-Do/Sights-and-Attractions/Art-Culture-Heritage>
- Augmented Reality. (2016). Augmented Reality Translator App - Google Translator. Retrieved December 21, 2016, from <https://www.newscientist.com/article/mg23231044-600-augmented-reality-set-to-overtake-vr-as-new-apps-go-live/>
- Backlund, E. A., & Williams, D. R. (2003). A quantitative synthesis of place attachment research: Investigating past experience and place attachment. In *Northeastern Recreation Research Symposium* (pp. 320-325).
- Baedcharoen, I. (2000). Impacts of religious tourism in Thailand.
- Bagnoli, A. (2009). Beyond the standard interview: The use of graphic elicitation and arts-based methods. *Qualitative Research*, 9(5), 547-570. doi:10.1177/1468794109343625
- Baker, S. E., & Edwards, R. (2012). How many qualitative interviews is enough? National Centre for Research Methods Review Paper. Discussion Paper. Retrieved from <http://eprints.ncrm.ac.uk/2273>
- Balboni, M.J., Bandini, J., Mitchell, C., Epstein-Peterson, Z.D., Amobi, A., Cahill, J., Enzinger, A.C., Peteet, J. & Balboni, T. (2015). Religion, spirituality, and the hidden curriculum: Medical student and faculty reflections. *Journal of pain and symptom management*, 50(4), 507-515.
- Baloglu, S., & McCleary, K. W. (1999). A Model of Destination Image Formation. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 26, 808-889.
- Bangkok.com. (2015). Chinatown Attractions - What to See in Chinatown - Wat Mangkon Kamalawat. Retrieved June 16, 2015, from <http://www.bangkok.com/chinatown/what-to-see-and-do.htm>
- BBC. (2015). BBC, Religions, Taoism at a glance. Retrieved July 5 2015, from <http://www.bbc.co.uk/religion/religions/taoism/ataglance/glance.shtml>
- Berli, A., & Martin, J. D. (2004). Factors influencing destination image. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 31(3), 657-681.
- Beijing International Film Festival. (2015). Beijing International Film Festival, China.org.cn. Retrieved May 9, 2015, from http://www.china.org.cn/bjzt/2015-04/17/content_35346451_13.htm

- Beijing Market Profile (2014). Beijing Market Profile – HKTDC, Major Economic Indicators. (2014, December 23). Retrieved June 6, 2015, from <http://china-trade-research.hktdc.com/business-news/article/Fast-Facts/Beijing-Market-Profile/ff/en/1/1X000000/1X06BPU3.htm>
- Beijing Temple of Heaven. (2015). Beijing Temple of Heaven: Imperial Sacrificial Altar with Pictures, Map, Tours. Retrieved May 9, 2015, from <http://www.travelchinaguide.com/attraction/beijing/heaven/>
- Bennett, C. (2007). Venturing into scary places: The minority experience. *About Campus*, 12(2), 26-29.
- Bettencourt, B., Talley, A., Benjamin, A. J., & Valentine, J. (2006). Personality and aggressive behavior under provoking and neutral conditions: a meta-analytic review. *Psychological bulletin*, 132(5), 751.
- Blum, S. (1997). Current concerns: A thematic analysis of recent hospitality industry issues. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 9(7), 350-361.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09596119710191029>
- Bolnick, D. A. (2008). Individual ancestry inference and the reification of race as a biological phenomenon. *Revisiting race in a genomic age*, 70-85.
- Bonn, M. A., Joseph-Mathews, S. M., Dai, M., Hayes, S., & Cave, J. (2007). Heritage/cultural attraction atmospherics: Creating the right environment for the heritage/cultural visitor. *Journal of Travel Research*, 45(3), 345-354.
- Bonn, M. A., Joseph-Mathews, S. M., Dai, M., Hayes, S., & Cave, J. (2007). Heritage/Cultural Attraction Atmospherics: Creating the Right Environment for the Heritage/Cultural Visitor. *Journal of Travel Research*, 45(3), 345-354. doi:10.1177/0047287506295947
- Boukas, N. (2008). Cultural Tourism, Young People and Destination Perception: A Case Study of Delphi, Greece.
- Boyatzis, R. E. (1998). *Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Britannica. (2015). Projective test, psychology. Retrieved July 28 2015, from <https://global.britannica.com/science/projective-test>
- Brown, D. A., & Cheng, T. J. (2012). Religious Relations across the Taiwan Strait: Patterns, Alignments, and Political Effects. *Orbis*, 56(1), 60-81.
- Burkitt, E., Barrett, M., & Davis, A. (2003). Children's colour choices for completing drawings of affectively characterised topics. *Journal of child psychology and psychiatry*, 44(3), 445-455.

- Burns, L. D., & Lennon, S. J. (1993). Social perception: methods for measuring our perception of others. *International Textile and Apparel Association Special Publication*, 5, 153-159.
- Business Monitor International. (2012). Thailand Tourism SWOT. In *Thailand Tourism Report Q1 2013* Includes BMI'S Forecasts. London: Business Monitor International.
- Buzinde, C., Choi, Y., & Wang, A. Y. (2012). Tourism Representations of Chinese Cosmology: The Case of Feng Shui Tourism. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 39(2), 975-996.
doi:10.1016/j.annals.2011.11.015
- Cai, L. A. (2002). Cooperative branding for rural destinations. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 29(3), 720–742.
- Calder, B. J., Phillips, L. W., & Tybout, A. M. (1982). The concept of external validity. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 9(3), 240-244.
- Çalýk, M., Ayas, A., & Ebenezer, J. V. (2005). A review of solution chemistry studies: Insights into students' conceptions. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 14(1), 29-50.
- Cambridge English Dictionary. (2015). "Destination" Meaning in Cambridge English Dictionary. Retrieved June 25, 2015, from <http://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/british/destination>
- Canny, I. U. (2013). An empirical investigation of service quality, tourist satisfaction and future behavioral intentions among domestic local tourist at Borobudur Temple. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 4(2), 86.
- Carmen-García, M, Navas, M. and Cuadrado, I. (2003). Los turistas se divierten, los inmigrantes trabajan: una descripción de dos grupos sociales a través del dibujo infantil. *Revista Internacional de Psicología y Terapia Psicológica*, 3(1), pp. 59-79.
- Cave, J., C. Ryan, & C. Panakera. (2003). Residents' Perceptions, Migrant Groups and Culture as an Attraction—The Case of a Proposed Pacific Island Cultural Centre in New Zealand. *Tourism Management*, 24(4). 371–85.
- Chan, S. C. (2005). Temple-building and heritage in China. *Ethnology*, 65-79.
- Chang, L. Y., & Liu, W. (2009). Temple fairs in Taiwan: Environmental strategies and competitive advantage for cultural tourism. *Tourism management*, 30(6), 900-904.
- Chang, S. C., Hsu, C. K., Tzeng, Y. S., Teng, S. C., Fu, J. P., Dai, N. T., Chen, S.G., Chen, T.M., & Feng, C. C. (2012). Deep sole burns in several participants in a traditional festival of the firewalking ceremony in Kee-lung, Taiwan—Clinical experiences and prevention strategies. *Burns*, 38(7), 1079-1083.

- Chang, Y. M., Lu, N. H., & Wu, T. C. (2005). Application of 3D laser scanning technology in historical building preservation: a case study of a Chinese temple. In *Optical Metrology* (pp. 585711-585711). International Society for Optics and Photonics.
- Chao Por Fah Moong Muang Shrine. (2015). Tourism Authority of Thailand. Retrieved April 15, 2015, from <http://www.tourismthailand.org/See-and-Do/Sights-and-Attractions-Detail/Chao-Por-Fah-Moong-Muang-Shrine--3872>
- Chen, C. F., & Chen, F. S. (2010). Experience quality, perceived value, satisfaction and behavioral intentions for heritage tourists. *Tourism management*, 31(1), 29-35.
- Chen, C. F., & Phou, S. (2013). A closer look at destination: Image, personality, relationship and loyalty. *Tourism management*, 36, 269-278.
- Chen, C. M., Chen, S. H., & Lee, H. T. (2010). Assessing Destination Image Through Combining Tourist Cognitive Perceptions with Destination Resources. *International Journal Of Hospitality & Tourism Administration*, 11(1), 59-75. doi:10.1080/15256480903539628
- Cheng, A. J., Chen, Y. Y., Huang, Y. T., Hsu, W. H., & Liao, H. Y. M. (2011). Personalized travel recommendation by mining people attributes from community-contributed photos. In *Proceedings of the 19th ACM international conference on Multimedia* (pp. 83-92). ACM.
- Chia-chü, L. (1981). The creation of the Chinese Banners in the early Ch'ing. *Chinese Studies in History*, 14(4), 47-75.
- China National Tourism Administration. (2013). Foreign Tourists to China from January to June 2013 (by purpose). Retrieved June 6, 2015, from http://en.cnta.gov.cn/Statistics/TourismStatistics/201507/t20150707_721711.shtml
- Chinese and western landscape painting. (2011). Chinese and western landscape painting. Retrieved December 19, 2016, from <https://culturetheory.wordpress.com/differences-2/>
- Chinese Taoist Architecture. (2015). China Taoist Constructions: Temple, Palace, Altar, Nunnery. Retrieved July 5, 2015, from <https://www.travelchinaguide.com/intro/architecture/styles/taoist.htm>
- Chinese Temples in Phuket. (2016). Phuket.com, Chinese Temples in Phuket, Phuket Attractions. Retrieved April 16, 2016, from <http://www.phuket.com/island/chinese-shrines.htm>
- Choe, J., Blazey, M., & Mitas, O. (2015). Motivations of non-Buddhists visiting Buddhist temples. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 18(1), 70-82.
- Choe, J., Dong, E., Chick, G., Breckenridge Wright, S., & Zhang, L. (2013). Turner's communitas and non-Buddhists who visit Buddhist temples. *Turizam: znanstveno-stručni časopis*, 61(3), 245-257.

- Choeichuenjit, K., & Sapsanganboon, W. (2014). Foreign Tourists' Demand on Thai Cultural Tourism Supply Chain. *The Journal of Thai Hospitality and Tourism*, 9(2), 74-85.
- Choi, W., Chan, A., & Wu, J. (1999). A qualitative and quantitative assessment of Hong Kong's image as a tourist destination. *Tourism Management*, 20(3), 361-365. doi:10.1016/S0261-5177(98)00116-2
- Choibamroong, T. (2006). Knowledge of tourists' behavior: A key success factor for managers in tourism business. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 1-8.
- Chon, K. S. (1990). The role of destination image in tourism: A review and discussion. *The Tourist Review*, 45(2), 2-9.
- Coccosis, H., & Constantoglou, M. E. (2008). The use of typologies in tourism planning: problems and conflicts. In *Regional Analysis and Policy* (pp. 273-295). Physica-Verlag HD.
- Cohen, A. P., & Jaw, Y. (1977). A Chinese Temple Keeper Talks about Chinese Folk Religion. *Asian Folklore Studies*, 1-17.
- Cohen, E. (2001). *The Chinese Vegetarian Festival in Phuket: Religion, Ethnicity, and Tourism on a Southern Thai Island* (9). White Lotus Company, Limited (Thailand).
- Cong, L., Wu, B., Morrison, A. M., Shu, H., & Wang, M. (2014). Analysis of wildlife tourism experiences with endangered species: An exploratory study of encounters with giant pandas in Chengdu, China. *Tourism Management*, 40 300-310. doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2013.07.005
- Correia, A., Oliveira, N., & Silva, F. (2009). Bridging perceived destination image and market segmentation-an application to golf tourism. *European Journal of tourism research*, 2(1), 41.
- Cramer, C., Flynn, B., & LaFave, A. (1997). Erikson's Stages of Development Chart. Retrieved May 13, 2016, from <http://www.psychologycharts.com/erikson-stages-of-development-chart.html>
- Crompton, J. L. (1979). An assessment of the image of Mexico as a vacation destination and the influence of geographical location upon that image. *Journal of travel research*, 17(4), 18-23.
- Crowe, P. (2011). Universal Buddhist Temple (世界佛教會): Embracing a Myriad Dharmas. *Canadian Journal of Buddhist Studies*, (6).
- Csapó, J. (2012). 10 - The Role and Importance of Cultural Tourism in Modern Tourism Industry. In *Strategies for tourism industry: Micro and macro perspectives* (pp. 201-232). Rijeka: InTech. Available from: <http://www.intechopen.com/books/strategies-for-tourism-industry-micro-and-macroperspectives/the-role-and-importance-of-cultural-tourism-in-modern-tourism-industry>
- Dann, G. (1977). Anomie, ego-enhancement and tourism. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 4, 184-194.

- Dann, G. M. S. (1996). Tourists Images of a Destination: An Alternative Analysis. *Journal of Travel and Tourism Marketing* 5(1/2), 41-55.
- Day, E. (1989). Share of heart: What is it and how can it be measured? *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 6(1), 5-13.
- De Bortoli, M., & Maroto, J. (2001). Colours across cultures: Translating colours in interactive marketing communications. *European Languages and the Implementation of Communication and Information Technologies*.
- Dean, J. (2014). Drawing What Homelessness Looks Like: Using Creative Visual Methods as a Tool of Critical Pedagogy. *Sociological Research Online*, 20(1), 2. doi:10.5153/sro.3540
- Decrop, A. (1999). Triangulation in qualitative tourism research. *Tourism management*, 20(1), 157-161.
- Degen, A. (2012). Concepts of Fascination, from Democritus to Kant. *Journal of the History of Ideas*, 73(3), 371-393.
- Della Dora, V. (2012). Setting and blurring boundaries: Pilgrims, tourists, and landscape in Mount Athos and Meteora. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 39(2), 951-974.
- Deng, Z., Lin, Y., Zhao, M., & Wang, S. (2015). Collaborative planning in the new media age: The Dafo Temple controversy, China. *Cities*, 45, 41-50.
- Denzin, N. K. (1970). *The research act: A theoretical introduction to sociological methods*. Transaction publishers.
- Desmet, P. M. A. (2012). Faces of Product Pleasure: 25 Positive Emotions in Human-Product Interactions. Retrieved 2016, from <http://www.ijdesign.org/ojs/index.php/IJDesign/article/view/1190/459>
- Dhar, S., Ordonez, V., & Berg, T. L. (2011). High level describable attributes for predicting aesthetics and interestingness. In *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), 2011 IEEE Conference on* (pp. 1657-1664). IEEE.
- Dichter, E. (1985). What's in an image? *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 2(1) (Winter), 75-81.
- Dimitrios, S., Matina, T., & Konstantinos, T. (2008). Islands and Destination Image: The Case of Ios. *Tourismos : An International Multidisciplinary Journal Of Tourism*, (1), 180.
- Discover Thainess. (2015). Tourism Authority of Thailand. Retrieved June 30, 2015, from [http://www.tatpr.org/webdatas/files/Fact%20Sheet_2015%20Discover%20Thainess%20Final\(1\).pdf](http://www.tatpr.org/webdatas/files/Fact%20Sheet_2015%20Discover%20Thainess%20Final(1).pdf)
doi:10.1016/j.iheduc.2008.12.001
- Donoghue, S. (2000). Projective Techniques in Consumer Research. *Journal of Family Ecology and Consumer Sciences*, (28), 47-53.

- Early Portuguese forays into Siam. (2013). *Phuket Gazette, Phuket History, Early Portuguese forays into Siam, Phuket History*. Retrieved April 17, 2015, from <http://www.phuketgazette.net/phuket-lifestyle/Phuket-History-Early-Portuguese-forays-Siam/21345>
- Eberhard, W. (1967). Topics and moral values in Chinese temple decorations. *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 87(1), 22-32.
- Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (1991). The meaning and measurement of destination image. *Journal of Tourism Studies*, 2(2), 2-12.
- Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (1993). The measurement of destination image: An empirical assessment. *Journal of Travel Research*, 31(4), 3-13.
- Echtner, C. M., & Ritchie, J. B. (2003). The meaning and measurement of destination image. *Journal of Tourism Studies*, 14(1), 37-48.
- Erikson, E. H. (1956). The problem of ego identity. *Journal of the American Psychoanalytic Association* 4, 56-121. DOI: 10.1177/000306515600400104
- Fakeye, P. C., & Crompton, J. L. (1991). Image differences between prospective, first time and repeat visitor to the lower Rio Grande Valley. *Journal of Travel Research*, 30(2): 10-16.
- Fang, G. C., Chang, C. N., Wu, Y. S., Yang, C. J., Chang, S. C., & Yang, I. L. (2002). Suspended particulate variations and mass size distributions of incense burning at Tzu Yun Yen temple in Taiwan, Taichung. *Science of the Total Environment*, 299(1), 79-87.
- Farquhar, J. N. (1928). Temple-and-Image Worship in Hinduism. *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain & Ireland (New Series)*, 60(01), 15-23.
- Ferdenzi, C., Schirmer, A., Roberts, S. C., Delplanque, S., Porcherot, C., Cayeux, I., Velazco, M.I., Sander, D., Scherer, K. R. & Grandjean, D. (2011). Affective dimensions of odor perception: a comparison between Swiss, British, and Singaporean populations. *Emotion*, 11(5), 1168.
- Fisher, G. (2008). The spiritual land rush: merit and morality in new Chinese Buddhist temple construction. *The Journal of Asian Studies*, 67(01), 143-170.
- Fleischer, A. (2000). The tourist behind the pilgrim in the Holy Land. *International Journal Of Hospitality Management*, 19, 311-326. doi:10.1016/S0278-4319(00)00026-8
- Foo, J. A., McGuiggan, R., & Yiannakis, A. (2004). Roles tourists play: An Australian perspective. *Annals of tourism research*, 31(2), 408-427.
- Foley, Y. C., & Mullis, F. (2008). Interpreting Children's Human Figure Drawings: Basic Guidelines for School Counselors. *Georgia School Counselors Association Journal*, 1(1), 28-37.

- Formoso, B. (1996). Chinese temples and philanthropic associations in Thailand. *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies*, 27(02), 245-260.
- Frith, H., Riley, S., Archer, L. & Gleeson, K. (2005). Imag(in)ing visual methodologies [Editorial], *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 2(3), 187-198. Retrieved from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1191/1478088705qp037ed>.
- Furlan, C., & Gambarotto, F. (2008). The Evaluation of the Process of Cultural Good Consumption for Different Profiles of Consumers. The case of the Scrovegni Chapel.
- Gallarza, M., Saura, I., & Garcia, H. (2002). Destination Image Towards a Conceptual Framework. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 29(1), 56-78.
- Gao, M. C. F. (2000). Jun Jing: The Temple of Memories: history, power and morality in a Chinese village. *Asian Studies Review*, 24(1), 118-120.
- García, J., Gómez, M., & Molina, A. (2012). A destination-branding model: An empirical analysis based on stakeholders. *Tourism Management*, 33, 646-661. doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2011.07.006
- Garrod, B. (2009). Understanding the relationship between tourism destination imagery and tourist photography. *Journal of Travel Research*, 47(3), 346-358.
- Gartner, W. C. (1993). Image Formation Process. *Journal of Travel and Tourism Marketing*, 2(2-3): 191-215.
- Gartner, W.C., & Hunt, J.D. (1987). An analysis of state image change over a twelve-year period (1971-1983). *Journal of Travel Research*, 16(2) (Fall), 15-19.
- Gatrell, J. D., & Collins-Kreiner, N. (2006). Negotiated space: Tourists, pilgrims, and the Bahá'í terraced gardens in Haifa. *Geoforum*, 37(5), 765-778.
- Gerard, R. (1958). Differential effects of colored lights on psychological functions. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of California, Los Angeles.
- Gibson, S. & Riley, S. (2010). Approaches to data collection in qualitative research. In Forrester, M.A. (Ed.), *Doing Qualitative Research in Psychology: A Practical Guide* (59-76). London: Sage.
- Gilbert, D., & Lizotte, M. (1998) Tourism and the performing arts. *Travel and Tourism Analyst*, 1(1998), pp. 82-96.
- Glaser, B. and Strauss, A. (1967) *Awareness of Dying*. Chicago: Aldine Publishing Company.
- Gobin, B., & Subramanian, R. (2007). Knowledge Modelling for a Hotel Recommendation System. *International Scholarly and Scientific Research & Innovation*, 1(1), 24-28.

- Gomez, P., & Danuser, B. (2004). Affective and physiological responses to environmental noises and music. *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 53, 91–103.
- Goodwin, R. C., Yakubik, J. K., Gendel, P. A., & Franks, H. A. (1986). Cultural Resources Survey of the Burnside Revetment Item, Ascension and St. James Parishes, Louisiana. Goodwin (R Christopher) and Associates Inc New Orleans La.
- Google. (2015). Google Search - Bang Neow Temple Phuket. Retrieved September 12, 2015, from <https://www.google.com/#q=Bang+Neow+Temple+Phuket>
- Google. (2015). Google Search – Hok Nguan Kung Temple Phuket. Retrieved September 12, 2015, from <https://www.google.com/#q=Hok+Nguan+Kung+Temple+Phuket>
- Google. (2015). Google Search – Jui Tui Temple Phuket. Retrieved September 12, 2015, from <https://www.google.com/#q=Jui+Tui+Temple+Phuket>
- Google. (2015). Google Search – Kathu Temple Phuket. Retrieved September 12, 2015, from <https://www.google.com/#q=Kathu+Temple+Phuket>
- Google. (2015). Google Search – Pud Jor Temple Phuket. Retrieved September 12, 2015, from <https://www.google.com/#q=Pud+Jor+Temple+Phuket>
- Google. (2015). Google Search – Saphan Hin Temple Phuket. Retrieved September 12, 2015, from <https://www.google.com/#q=Saphan+Hin+Temple+Phuket>
- Google. (2015). Google Search – Serene Light Temple Phuket. Retrieved September 12, 2015, from <https://www.google.com/#q=Serene+Light+Temple+Phuket>
- Goossaert, V. (2006). Resident specialists and temple managers in late Imperial China. *Min-su ch'ü-yi*, 153, 25-68.
- Greaves, N., & Skinner, H. (2010). The importance of destination image analysis to UK rural tourism. *Marketing Intelligence And Planning*, 28(4), 486-507. doi:10.1108/02634501011053586
- Grimwade, G. (2003). Gold, gardens, temples and feasts: Chinese temple, Croydon, Queensland.[Paper in issue entitled'Archaeology of the Overseas Chinese'.]. *Australasian Historical Archaeology*, 21(2003), 50.
- Groeppe-Klein, A., & Germelmann, C. C. (2003). 'Minding the Mall': Do We Remember What We See?. *NA-Advances in Consumer Research*, 30.
- Guha, A. (2012). Krishnalila in Terracotta Temples of Bengal. *Temples of Bengal*, 26.
- Gunn, C. (1972). *Vacationscape - Designing Tourist Regions*. Austin, Texas: University of Texas.
- Gunn, C. (1988). *Vacationscapes - Designing Tourist Regions*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold.

- Haiyan, H., & Jasper, C. R. (2007). A Qualitative Study of Mall Shopping Behaviors of Mature Consumers. *Journal of Shopping Center Research*, 14(1), 17-37.
- Hall, M. H. (2001). Measurement issues in surveys of giving and volunteering and strategies applied in the design of Canada's National Survey of Giving, Volunteering and Participating. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 30(3), 515-526.
- Hamilton, A. (2003). Kwan Im, nine emperor gods, and Chinese spirit in southern Thailand. S.l.: S.n. First date: 8th June 1999. Presented at: 7th International Conference on Thai Studies, Amsterdam, July 1999.
- Hanley, N. D. (1989). Valuing Rural Recreation Benefits: An Empirical Comparison of Two Approaches. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 40, 361–374. doi: 10.1111/j.1477-9552.1989.tb01117.x
- Hannapha, P., & Thonglert, G. (2011). The Integration of Image and Text for Communication in the Mural Paintings of Potharam Temple in Nadoon District, Maha Sarakham Province. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 53-57.
- Hartling, J. W., & Meier, I. (2010). Economic effects of geotourism in geopark TERRA. vita, Northern Germany. In *The George Wright Forum* (Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 29-39). George Wright Society.
- Hashim, N. H., Murphy, J., & Hashim, N. M. (2007). Islam and online imagery on Malaysian tourist destination websites. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 12(3), 1082-1102.
- He, G. (2009). English and Chinese cultural connotation of color words in comparison. *Asian Social Science*, 5(7), 160.
- Heinze, R. I. (1981). The Nine Imperial Gods in Singapore. *Asian Folklore Studies*, 151-171.
- Henkel, R., Henkel, P., Agrusa, W., Agrusa, J., & Tanner, J. (2006). Thailand as a tourist destination: Perceptions of international visitors and Thai residents. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 11(3), 269-287. doi:10.1080 / 10941660600753299
- Hidalgo, A. F., Hidalgo-Fernández, R. E., Madueño, J. A. C., & Arriaza, M. (2015). Approach To The Economic Value Generated In The Natural Parks Of Cordoba (Spain). *Holos*, 6, 16-36.
- Hidi, S. (2006). Interest: A unique motivational variable. *Educational Research Review*, 1(2), 69-82. doi:10.1016/j.edurev.2006.09.001
- Higginbottom, G. M. A. (2004). Sampling issues in qualitative research. *Nurse Researcher*, 12(1), 7.
- Hill, A. M. (1992). Chinese Funerals and Chinese Ethnicity in Chiang Mai, Thailand. *Ethnology*, 31(4), 315-330.

- Hirai, S., Kitama, H., & Nishimura, T. (2000). An Attempt of Valuation about the Linear Open Space Incorporated with River or Street by a Questionnaire Survey for Residents-Case Study for Shukugawa Park in Nishinomiya City. *Memoirs-Faculty of Engineering Osaka City University*, 41, 49-56.
- History of Phuket. (2015). Travel Phuket, History of Phuket. Retrieved April 17, 2015, from <http://www.travelphuket.com/history-of-phuket.html>
- History Tin and Colonization. (2014). Phuket-Oldtown-Hostel, History Tin and Colonization. Retrieved April 16, 2015, from <http://www.phuketoldtownhostel.com/history.html>
- Holton, J., A. (2007). Rehumanising Knowledge Work through Fluctuating Support Networks: A grounded theory. In B.G. Glaser, & J. Horton (Eds.). *The Grounded Theory Seminar Reader*. Mill Valley, CA: Sociology Press.
- Holtzhausen, S. (2001). Triangulation as a powerful tool to strengthen the qualitative research design: The Resource-based Learning Career Preparation Programme (RBLCPP) as a case study. Retrieved November 13, 2015, from <http://www.leeds.ac.uk/educol/documents/00001759.htm>
- Hong, Z., Yan, J., Hong, Z., & Yang, J. (2015). Quantitative Studies on the Historical Development of Chinese Taoist Temples since 1911. *Journal of Alternative Perspectives in the Social Sciences*, 6(4).
- Hong, Z., Yan, J., Zhaohui, H., & Jiamin, Y. (2015). Quantitative Studies on the Historical Development of Chinese Taoist Temples since 1911. *Journal Of Alternative Perspectives In The Social Sciences*, 6(4), 493-519.
- Hsu, C. H., & Huang, S. (2008). Travel motivation: A critical review of the concept's development. *Tourism management: Analysis, behaviour and strategy*, 14-27.
- Hsu, C. H., & Song, H. (2012). Projected images of major Chinese outbound destinations. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 17(5), 577-593.
- <http://www.acrwebsite.org/volumes/8737/volumes/v30/NA-30>
- [http://www.forestry.gov.uk/website/pdf.nsf/b591cb1aa3d9d9ac802570ec004f557d/4c928caff9ba80a1802575d100478d29/\\$file/active_england_great_western_site_report.pdf](http://www.forestry.gov.uk/website/pdf.nsf/b591cb1aa3d9d9ac802570ec004f557d/4c928caff9ba80a1802575d100478d29/$file/active_england_great_western_site_report.pdf)
- Huang, W., & Yeh, Y. (2015). Immigrant Mothers' Knowledge of Medication Safety and Administration for Young Children. *Asian Social Science*, 11(13), 276-288.
- Hung, W. (1988). From temple to tomb: Ancient Chinese art and religion in transition. *Early China*, 13, 78-115.
- Hunt, J.D. (1975). Image as a factor in tourism development. *Journal of Travel Research*, 13(3) (Winter), 1-7.

- Iazzi, A., Rosato, P., & Gravili, S. (2015). Competitive processes in tourism destinations: the role of intangible assets. *International Journal Of Management Cases*, 17(4), 134-148.
- ICOMOS. (2004). ICOMOS, Ename Charter for the Interpretation of Cultural Heritage Sites. http://www.enamecharter.org/downloads/archives/ICOMOS_Ename_Charter_%28Draft2%29_20-02-04.pdf
- International Business Times. (2013, October 14). Phuket Vegetarian Festival 2013: Where Self-Mutilation Brings Virtue. Retrieved June 6, 2015, from <http://www.ibtimes.com/phuket-vegetarian-festival-2013-where-self-mutilation-brings-virtue-1424088>
- Ismail, S., & Mohd-Ali, N. A. (2011). The Imaging of Heritage Conservation in Historic City of George Town for City Marketing. *Procedia Engineering*, 20, 339-345.
- Ivanovic, M. (2008). Defining Tourist Attractions. In *Cultural Tourism* (pp. 111-114). Cape Town, South Africa: Juta.
- Jacobs, K. W., & Hustmyer, F. E. (1974). Effects of four psychological primary colors on GSR, heart rate, and respiration rate. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 38, 763-766.
- Jenkins, O. (1999). Understanding and measuring tourist destination images. *The International Journal of Tourism Research*, 1, 1-15.
- Jenkins, O. H. (1999). Understanding and measuring tourist destination images. *The International Journal of Tourism Research*, 1(1), 1.
- Jensen, K., & Arens, E. (2005). Acoustical quality in office workstations, as assessed by occupant surveys. *Indoor Air 2005, Beijing, China*. UC Berkeley: Center for the Built Environment. Retrieved from: <http://eprints.cdlib.org/uc/item/0zm2z3jg>
- Jetter, J. J., Guo, Z., McBrian, J. A., & Flynn, M. R. (2002). Characterization of emissions from burning incense. *Science of the Total Environment*, 295(1), 51-67.
- Jian, W. A. N. G. (2009). Temple community of folk religion in Jiangnan since the Ming and Qing dynasties: Focus on Suzhou and Songjiang areas. *Frontiers of History in China*, 4(4), 537-578.
- Jiandong, B. U. (2007). Comparative Study of Chinese Temple Fair and Western Carnival [J]. *Southeast Culture*, 6, 015.
- Jianlin, Z. W. Z. (2007). The Exploration of Chinese Temple Gardens [J]. *South China Agriculture*, 1, 001.
- Jick, T. D. (1979). Mixing qualitative and quantitative methods: Triangulation in action. *Administrative science quarterly*, 602-611.

- Johnson, N. B. (1989). Geomancy, sacred geometry, and the idea of a garden: Tenryu-ji temple, Kyoto, Japan. *The Journal of Garden History*, 9(1), 1-19.
- Kagan, J., & Moss, H. (1960). The Stability of Passive and Dependent Behavior from Childhood Through Adulthood. *Child Development*, 31(3), 577-591. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1126051>
- Kaplan, U. (2010). Images of monasticism: The temple stay program and the re-branding of Korean Buddhist temples. *Korean Studies*, 34(1), 127-146.
- Kasikorn, Bank. (2014). Kasikorn Research Center - Phuket Tourism: Thriving in 1Q14, with 2014 Revenue at THB2.79 Billion. Retrieved May 7, 2015, from <https://www.kasikornresearch.com/en/K-EconAnalysis/Pages/ViewSummary.aspx?docid=33190>
- Kataoka, T. (2012). Religion as Non-religion: The Place of Chinese Temples in Phuket, Southern Thailand. *Southeast Asian Studies*, 1(3), 461-485.
- Keller, K. (1998). *Strategic brand management: Building, measuring, and managing brand equity*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Kemp, W. (2016). The secret of good composition. Retrieved September 14, 2016, from <http://willkempartschool.com/the-secret-of-good-composition/>
- Kesmanee, C., & Charoensri, K. (1995). Case study on the effects of tourism on culture and the environment Thailand. Bangkok: UNESCO Principal Regional Office for Asia and the Pacific.
- Kim, H., & Stepchenkova, S. (2015). Effect of tourist photographs on attitudes towards destination: Manifest and latent content. *Tourism Management*, 49, 29-41. doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2015.02.004
- Kobayashi, M., Pollack, P., & Pomerance, C. (2009). On the distribution of sociable numbers. *Journal of Number Theory*, 129(8), 1990-2009. doi:10.1016/j.jnt.2008.10.011
- Koc, E., & Boz, H. (2014). Triangulation in tourism research: A bibliometric study of top three tourism journals. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 12, 9-14. doi:10.1016/j.tmp.2014.06.003
- Kokkinos, C. M., Panayiotou, G., & Davazoglou, A. M. (2004). Perceived seriousness of pupils' undesirable behaviours: The student teachers' perspective. *Educational Psychology*, 24(1), 109-120. doi:10.1080/0144341032000146458
- Kontogeorgopoulos, N. (1998). Tourism in Thailand: Patterns, Trends and Limitations. *Pacific Tourism Review*, 2(3/4), 225-238.
- Korstanje, M. E. (2010). The Power of Projective Drawings: A New Method for Researching Tourist Experiences. *E-Review of Tourism Research*, 8(5), 85-101.

- Kotler, P. (1987). Semiotics of person and nation marketing. *Marketing and Semiotics. New directions in the study of signs for sale*, Berlin, Mouton de Gruyter, 3-12.
- Kress, G. (2001) 'Sociolinguistics and Social Semiotics', in Paul Cobley (ed.) *The Routledge Companion to Semiotics and Linguistics*. London: Routledge.
- Kress, G., & Leeuwen, T. (1996). *Reading Images. The Grammar of Visual Design* London: Routledge.
- Kuhn, P. (2003). Thematic Drawing and Focused, Episodic Interview upon the Drawing - A Method in Order to Approach to the Children's Point of View on Movement, Play and Sports at School [50 paragraphs]. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 4(1), Art. 8, <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:0114-fqs030187>
- Kurd, N. (2012). Sacred Manifestations: The Making and Meaning of Mosques in Canada. *Journal of Canadian Art History/Annales d'histoire de l'art Canadien*, 33(2), 148-169.
- Kustedja, S., Sudikno, A., & Salura, P. (2014). Local Deities as Symbol of Acculturated Chinese Diasporas Temples In Indonesia. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 6(4).
- Laing, J., Wheeler, F., Reeves, K., & Frost, W. (2014). Assessing the experiential value of heritage assets: A case study of a Chinese heritage precinct, Bendigo, Australia. *Tourism Management*, 40, 180-192.
- Landrum, R. E. (2011). Measuring Dispositional Humility: A First Approximation 1,2,3. *Psychological Reports*, 108(1), 217-228. doi:10.2466/02.07.09.pr0.108.1.217-228
- Lang, G., Chan, S. C., & Ragvald, L. (2005). Folk Temples and the Chinese Religious Economy. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Research on Religion*, 1.
- Law, R., & Chen, S. (2012). Representation of Destination Cultural Factors on Hotel Websites: Content Analysis of Beijing Hotel Websites. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 17(2), 1-20. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10941665.2011.616903>
- Learning Theories. (2014). Erikson's Stages of Development - Learning Theories. Retrieved May 13, 2016, from <http://www.learning-theories.com/eriksons-stages-of-development.html>
- Lee, G., & Lee, C. K. (2009). Cross-cultural comparison of the image of Guam perceived by Korean and Japanese leisure travelers: Importance–performance analysis. *Tourism Management*, 30(6), 922-931.
- Lee, W., & Gretzel, U. (2006). Tourism Students' differences In Mental Imagery Ability: Implications For Learning Environments. *Imagining the Future of Travel and Tourism Education*, 8, 101-116.
- Lei, W. (2007). Research on arrangement of landscape plants in Chinese temple areas. *Scientia Silvae Sinicae*, 43(1), 62.

- Levy, R. M. (2001). Temple Site at Phimai: modeling for the scholar and the tourist. In *Virtual Systems and Multimedia, 2001. Proceedings. Seventh International Conference on* (pp. 147-158). IEEE.
- Li, M., Wu, B., & Cai, L. (2008). Tourism development of World Heritage Sites in China: A geographic perspective. *Tourism Management, 29*(2), 308-319.
- Li, X. (2012). Examining the 'relative image' of tourism destinations: a case study. *Current Issues In Tourism, 15*(8), 741-757. doi:10.1080/13683500.2011.629721
- Li, X., Pan, B., Zhang, L., & Smith, W. (2009). The Effect of Online Information Search on Image Development: Insights from a Mixed-Methods Study. *Journal of Travel Research, 48*(1), 45-57. doi:10.1177/0047287508328659
- Lilienfeld, S., Wood, J., & Garb, H. (2000). The Scientific Status of Projective Techniques. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest, 1*(2), 27-66.
- Lin, T. C., Chang, F. H., Hsieh, J. H., Chao, H. R., & Chao, M. R. (2002). Characteristics of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and total suspended particulate in indoor and outdoor atmosphere of a Taiwanese temple. *Journal of hazardous materials, 95*(1), 1-12.
- Lin, T. C., Krishnaswamy, G., & Chi, D. S. (2008). Incense smoke: clinical, structural and molecular effects on airway disease. *Clinical and Molecular Allergy, 6*(1), 1.
- Lin, Y., Rau, K., Liu, Y., Lin, Y., Ying, J., & Kao, C. (2015). Development and validation of the Chinese Version of Spiritual Interests Related Illness Tool for patients with cancer in Taiwan. *European Journal of Oncology Nursing, 19*(5), 589-594. doi:10.1016/j.ejon.2015.03.005
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Beverly Hills: Sage.
- Loevinger, J. (1976). *Ego development: Conceptions and theories*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass
- Lonely Planet. (2015). Wat Mangkon Kamalawat - Lonely Planet - sights / Religious. Retrieved June 16, 2015, from <http://www.lonelyplanet.com/thailand/bangkok/sights/religious/wat-mangkon-kamalawat>
- Long, P. T., & Perdue, R. R. (1990). The economic impact of rural festivals and special events: Assessing the spatial distribution of expenditures. *Journal of Travel Research, 28*(4), 10-14.
- Lu, L., Chi, C. G., & Liu, Y. (2015). Authenticity, involvement, and image: Evaluating tourist experiences at historic districts. *Tourism Management, 50*, 85-96.
- Lucang, W. A. N. G., & Wei, L. I. (2013). Urban Space Ture under the Influence of Tourism: A Case Study of Langmusi Town, Gannan Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture. *Tourism Tribune/Lvyou Xuekan, 28*(12).
- Luscher, M., & Scott, I. (1969). *The Luscher Color Test*. NY: Washington Square Press.

- Ma, X., Sun, X., He, Y., & Chen, Y. (2013). Parking choice behavior investigation: A case study at Beijing Lama Temple. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 96, 2635-2642.
- Macarthur, J. (2002). The Look of the Object: Minimalism in Art and Architecture, Then and Now. *Architectural Theory Review*, 7(1), 137-148. doi:10.1080/13264820209478450
- Machover, K. (1949). *Personality projection in the drawing of the human figure*. Springfield, Ill.:
- Madden, T. J., Hewett, K., & Roth, M. S. (2000). Managing images in different cultures: A cross-national study of color meanings and preferences. *Journal of international marketing*, 8(4), 90-107.
- Mallapragada, M. (2010). Desktop deities: Hindu temples, online cultures and the politics of remediation. *South Asian Popular Culture*, 8(2), 109-121.
- Mann, S., & Thapar, R. (2015). *Awakening of The Buddhist Circuit* (pp. 2-8). Gurgaon, India: HSV.
- Marnat, G. (2003a). History and Development. In *Handbook of psychological assessment* (4th ed., pp. 103-107). Hoboken, N.J.: John Wiley & Sons.
- Marnat, G. (2003b). Issues Related to Reliability and Validity. In *Handbook of psychological assessment* (4th ed., pp. 107-110). Hoboken, N.J.: John Wiley & Sons.
- Marshall, B., Cardon, P., Poddar, A., & Fontenot, R. (2013). Does sample size matter in qualitative research?: A review of qualitative interviews in IS research. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 54(1), 11-22.
- Martin, R., & Randal, J. (2008). How is donation behaviour affected by the donations of others?. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 67(1), 228-238.
- Matlovičová, K., & Kolesárová, J. (2012). Destination Image and Possibilities of its Formation: A Case Study of the Image of Thailand as a Tourist Destination Perceived by Slovaks. *Central European Regional Policy and Human Geography*, 2(1), 5-20.
- Matzler, K., Strobl, A., Stokburger-Sauer, N., Bobovnický, A., & Bauer, F. (2016). Brand personality and culture: The role of cultural differences on the impact of brand personality perceptions on tourists' visit intentions. *Tourism Management*, 52, 507-520. doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2015.07.017
- Maud, J. (2007). *Monuments, Mediums & the Municipality: Constructing Chineseness and Sacred Space in Hat Yai*. In *The sacred borderland: A Buddhist saint, the state, and transnational religion in southern Thailand* (pp. 311-352). Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/1959.14/127455>
- Mcdonald, R. I., Fielding, K. S., & Louis, W. R. (2014). Conflicting social norms and community conservation compliance. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 22(3), 212-216. doi:10.1016/j.jnc.2013.11.005

- McKercher, B. (2004). A comparative study of international cultural tourists. *CAUTHE 2004: Creating Tourism Knowledge*, 498.
- McKercher, B., & Du Cros, H. (2002). A typology of cultural tourist: Recognizing different shades of cultural tourists. In *Cultural tourism: The partnership between tourism and cultural heritage management* (p. 140). New York: Haworth Hospitality Press.
- McKercher, B., & Ho, P. S. (2006). Assessing the tourism potential of smaller cultural and heritage attractions. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 14(5), 473-488.
- McKercher, B., Wong, C., & Lau, G. (2006). How tourists consume a destination. *Journal of Business Research*, 59(5), 647-652. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2006.01.009>
- McLeod, S. (2008). Erik Erikson. Retrieved May 13, 2016, from <http://www.simplypsychology.org/Erik-Erikson.html>
- Mengyuan, Q. I. U., Fang, W. A. N. G., Run, S. H. A., & Guolin, H. O. U. (2013). Tourists' Perception of and Satisfaction with Soundscape Properties in Tourist Areas: A Case Study of Nanjing Confucius Temple-Qinhuai Scenic Area. *Tourism Tribune/Lvyou Xuekan*, 28(1).
- Mocanu, R. (2014). Destination Branding through Experience and Authenticity. *Journal of Tourism Challenges and Trends*, 7(1), 89.
- Mohammad, B., & Som, A. (2010). An Analysis of Push and Pull Travel Motivations of Foreign Tourists to Jordan. *IJBM International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(12).
- Moore, A. M., & Barker, G. G. (2012). Confused or multicultural: Third culture individuals' cultural identity. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 36(4), 553-562.
doi:10.1016/j.ijintrel.2011.11.002
- Morgan, C.D., & Murray, H.A. (1935). A method for investigating fantasies. *Archives of Neurology and Psychiatry*, 34, 289-304.
- Morgan, W. (2002). "Origin and History of the Earliest Thematic Apperception test". *Journal of Personality Assessment* 79(3). 422-445
- Morrow, V. (2001). Using qualitative methods to elicit young people's perspectives on their environments: Some ideas for community health initiatives. *Health Education Research*, 16(3), 255-268.
- Moutinho, N., & Durão, M. (2013). Expanding the Senses of Drawing Through Colour. *Senses & Sensibility in Florianópolis: Advertising, Design, Fashion, Marketing, Photography and Visual Culture in the Right Place. Proceedings Book of the UNIDCOM/IADE's 7th International Conference*, 179-187.

- Murray, H. A. (1943). *Thematic Apperception Test manual*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Nasution, S. K. (2005). *Phuket Heritage: Phuket's Old Town Movement*. Retrieved April 16, 2015, from <http://lestariheritage.net/phuket/webpages/mov01.html>
- Navasumrit, P., Arayasiri, M., Hiang, O. M. T., Leechawengwongs, M., Promvijit, J., Choonvisase, S., Chantchaemsai, S., Nakngam, N., Mahidol, C., & Ruchirawat, M. (2008). Potential health effects of exposure to carcinogenic compounds in incense smoke in temple workers. *Chemico-biological interactions*, 173(1), 19-31.
- New Scientist. (2016). *Augmented reality set to overtake VR as new apps go live*. Retrieved December 21, 2016, from <https://www.newscientist.com/article/mg23231044-600-augmented-reality-set-to-overtake-vr-as-new-apps-go-live/>
- Nghiêm-Phú, B. (2014). A review of destination image studies from 2008 to 2012. *European Journal of Tourism Research*, 8, 35-65.
- Nicoletta, R., & Servidio, R. (2012). Tourists' opinions and their selection of tourism destination images: An affective and motivational evaluation. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 4, 19-27.
- Nisbett, R. E., & Miyamoto, Y. (2005). The influence of culture: Holistic versus analytic perception. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 9(10), 467-473. doi:10.1016/j.tics.2005.08.004
- NY Daily News. (2015). *The Phuket Vegetarian Festival - Photos - The Phuket Vegetarian Festival*. Retrieved June 6, 2015, from <http://www.nydailynews.com/news/phuket-vegetarian-festival-gallery-1.1957159>
- Nyaupane, G. P., Timothy, D. J., & Poudel, S. (2015). Understanding tourists in religious destinations: A social distance perspective. *Tourism Management*, 48, 343-353.
- O'Brien, L., & Morris, J. (2009). *Active England Great Woodland Community Forest Report*. Social and Economic Research Group. The Research Agency of the Forestry Commission.
- O'Toole, M. (1990). A Systemic-Functional Semiotics of Art. In *Semiotica*, 2(3/4), 185-209.
- O'Connor, Z. (2011). Colour psychology and colour therapy: Caveat emptor. *Color Research & Application*, 36(3), 229-234.
- OECD. (2009). *The Impact of Culture on Tourism, Chapter 7: The Vorarlberg Province, Austria*. OECD. Paris. (pp. 97-113).
- Olsen, J. (2015). *Shopping Mall Preferences Exploring consumers' preferences for shopping malls utilizing the Best-Worst scaling method*. Aarhus University. Master Thesis

- Onwuegbuzie, A., Leech, N., & Collins, K. (2012). Qualitative Analysis Techniques for the Review of the Literature. *The Qualitative Report* 2012, 17, 1-28.
<http://www.nova.edu/ssss/QR/QR17/onwuegbuzie.pdf>
- Oxford Dictionaries (2015). Definition of Taoism in English: Taoism. Retrieved July 5, 2015.
- Panagiotaki, G., Nobes, G., & Potton, A. (2009). Mental models and other misconceptions in children's understanding of the earth. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 104(1), 52-67.
- Parenteau, A. (1995). *Marketing Práctico del Turismo*. Madrid: Síntesis S.A.
- PATA (2010). Pacific Asia Travel Association and Visa and Survey: Mainland Chinese most frequent outbound travelers from Greater China. Hong Kong, 07 July 2010. Retrieved: http://www.visa-asia.com/ap/hk/en_US/mediacenter/pressrelease/hk_07072010PATASurvey.shtml
- Pattie, D. C., & J. Snyder. (1996). Using a Neural Network to Forecast Visitor Behavior. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 23(1), 151-64.
- Pearce, P. L. (1988). *The Ulysses factor: Evaluating visitors in tourist settings*. New York: Springer-Verlag.
- Pearce, P.L. (1982). Perceived changes in holiday destinations. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 9, 145-164.
- Petr, C. (2015). How heritage site tourists may become monument visitors. *Tourism Management*, 51, 247-262.
- Pettit, J. E. (2008). The Erotic Empress: Fantasy and Sovereignty in Chinese Temple Inscriptions. *Tang Studies*, 2008(26), 125-142. doi:10.1179/073750308790779341
- Phakdee-Auksorn, P. (2009). *Exploring destination image: A case study of British traveller to Phuket* (Doctoral dissertation, Nottingham Trent University).
- Phuket Gazette. (2016). South Korea supports Phuket's smart city endeavor. Retrieved December 21, 2016, from <http://www.phuketgazette.net/phuket-news/South-Korea-supports-Phukets-smart-city-endeavor/65555>
- Phuket History. (2015). Kophuket.com, Phuket History. Retrieved April 16, 2015, from <http://www.kophuket.com/phuket/info/phuket-history.html>
- Phuket Provincial. (2015). Phuket Provincial Governor's Office, Phuket History. Retrieved April 16, 2015, from http://www.phuket.go.th/webpk/contents.php?str=introduce_his
- Phuket Vegetarian Festival. (2015). Phuket Vegetarian Festival - Phuket Festivals and Events. Retrieved June 6, 2015, from <http://www.phuket.com/festival/vegetarian.htm>

- Phuket Vegetarian Festival History. (2015). Phuket Vegetarian Festival, History. Retrieved April 16, 2015, from <http://www.phuketvegetarian.com/phuketvegetarian-eng/phuketvegetarian-history.htm>
- Phuket Wats and Temples. (2015). Kophuket.com, Phuket Wats and Temples. Retrieved April 16, 2015, from <http://www.kophuket.com/phuket/attractions/phuket-temples.html>
- Piewdang, S., Mekkamol, P., & Untachai, S. (2013). Measuring Spiritual Tourism Management in Community: A Case Study of Sri Chom Phu Ongtu Temple, Thabo district, Nongkhai province, Thailand. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 88, 96-107.
- Pike, S. (2002). Destination image analysis—a review of 142 papers from 1973 to 2000. *Tourism Management*, 23, 541-549.
- Pike, S., & Ryan, C. (2004). Destination Positioning Analysis through a Comparison of Cognitive, Affective, and Conative Perceptions. *Journal of Travel Research*, 42(4), 333-342. doi:10.1177/0047287504263029
- Pizam, A., & Jeong, G. H. (1996). Cross-cultural tourist behavior: Perceptions of Korean tour-guides. *Tourism Management*, 17(4), 277-286.
- Places of Worship. (2015). Tourism Authority of Thailand. Retrieved April 15, 2015, from <http://www.tourismthailand.org/See-and-Do/Sights-and-Attractions/Places-of-Worship>
- Porcu, E. (2014). Pop religion in Japan: Buddhist temples, icons, and branding. *The Journal of Religion and Popular Culture*, 26(2), 157-172.
- Poria, Y., Butler, R., & Airey, D. (2004). Links between tourists, heritage, and reasons for visiting heritage sites. *Journal of Travel Research*, 43(1), 19-28.
- Prayag, G. (2007a). Exploring the relationship between destination image and brand personality of a tourist destination: An application of projective techniques. *Journal of Travel and Tourism Research*, 2(Fall 2007), 111-130.
- Prayag, G. (2007b). Positioning the city product as an international tourist destination: Evidence from South Africa. *Turizam: znanstveno-stručni časopis*, 55(2), 139-155.
- Prayag, G., & Ryan, C. (2011). The relationship between the 'push' and 'pull' factors of a tourist destination: the role of nationality - an analytical qualitative research approach. *Current Issues In Tourism*, 14(2), 121-143. doi:10.1080/13683501003623802
- Prebensen, N. (2007). Exploring tourists' images of a distant destination. *Tourism Management*, 28, 747-756. doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2006.05.005

- Psychology Charts. (2016). Erikson's Stages of Development Chart. Retrieved May 13, 2016, from <http://www.psychologycharts.com/erikson-stages-of-development-chart.html>
- Purchase, C. (2014). Subjective emotion and colour use in drawings. Undergraduate Honors Theses.
- Qu, H., Kim, L., & Im, H. (2011). A model of destination branding: Integrating the concepts of the branding and destination image. *Tourism Management*, 32, 465-476.
doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2010.03.014
- Rakić, T., & Chambers, D. (Eds.). (2011). *An introduction to visual research methods in tourism* (Vol. 9). Routledge.
- Ramkissoon, H., & Uysal, M. S. (2011). The effects of perceived authenticity, information search behaviour, motivation and destination imagery on cultural behavioural intentions of tourists. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 14(6), 537-562.
- Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011a). A cross-cultural comparison of tourists' cultural behavioural intentions. *E-Review of Tourism Research*, 9(5), P190.
- Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011a). Relationship Between Destination Image and Behavioral Intentions of Tourists to Consume Cultural Attractions. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 20, 575-595. doi:10.1080/19368623.2011.570648
- Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b). A cross-cultural comparison of tourists' cultural behavioural intentions. *E-Review Of Tourism Research*, 9(5), 190-219.
- Ramkissoon, H., Uysal, M., & Brown, K. (2011b). Relationship between destination image and behavioral intentions of tourists to consume cultural attractions. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 20(5), 575-595.
- Ramsey, E., Ibbotson, P., & McCole, P. (2006). Application of projective techniques in an e-business context. *International Journal of Market Research*, 48(5): 551-573.
- Reilly, M. D. (1990). Free Elicitation of Descriptive Adjectives for Tourism Image Assessment. *Journal of Travel Research*, 28(4), 21-26.
- Remoaldo, P. C., Ribeiro, J. C., Vareiro, L., & Santos, J. F. (2014). Tourists' perceptions of world heritage destinations: The case of Guimarães (Portugal). *Tourism & Hospitality Research*, 14(4), 206-218.
doi:10.1177/1467358414541457
- Renata, R. (2011, May 25). Advantages & Disadvantages of a Projective Test. Retrieved July 28, 2015, from http://www.ehow.com/info_8489584_advantages-disadvantages-projective-test.html

- Reynolds, W. H. (1965). The role of the consumer in image building. *California Management Review*, Spring, 69-76.
- Richards, G. (1996). *Cultural tourism in Europe* (1st ed.). Wallingford, UK: CAB International.
- Richards, G. (2011). Tourism trends: tourism, culture and cultural routes. *Cultural tourism trends in Europe: a context for the development of Cultural Routes*. In: Khovanova-Rubicondo, K. (ed.) *Impact of European Cultural Routes on SMEs' innovation and competitiveness*, Strasbourg: Council of Europe Publishing, 21-39.
- Richards, G. (2014). *Tourism trends: The convergence of culture and tourism*.
https://www.academia.edu/9491857/Tourism_trends_The_convergence_of_culture_and_tourism
- Riley, H. (2001). *The Intelligence of Seeing. An Inquiry into the Relationships between Perception Theory, Communication Theory and the Practice and Teaching of Drawing*. PhD thesis, University of Wales. 2001.
- Riley, H. (2004). Perceptual modes, semiotic codes, social mores: A contribution towards a social semiotics of drawing. *Visual communication*, 3(3), 294-315.
- Ritchie, J., & Lewis, J. (2003). Chapter 5, *Designing Fieldwork Strategies and Materials*. In *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers*. London: Sage Publications.
- Rittichainuwat, B., & Rattanaphinanchai, S. (2015). Applying a mixed method of quantitative and qualitative design in explaining the travel motivation of film tourists in visiting a film-shooting destination. *Tourism Management*, 46136-147. doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2014.06.005
- Rorschach, H. (1921). *Psychodiagnostics: A diagnostic test based on perception*. NY: Grune & Stratton.
- Ross, M., & Wang, Q. (2010). Why We Remember and What We Remember Culture and Autobiographical Memory. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 5(4), 401-409.
- Rouse, L. (2013). *Visual and arts-based methods in social sciences: an interview with Dr Anna Bagnoli*. News & Views, The Open University Psychological Society.
- Ryan, C., & Cave, J. (2005). Structuring destination image: A qualitative approach. *Journal of travel research*, 44(2), 143-150.
- Sakolnakorn, T., Naipinit, A., & Kroeksakul, P. (2013). Sustainable Tourism Development and Management in the Phuket Province, Thailand. *Asian Social Science*, 9(7), 75.
- Saldana, J. (2009). *An introduction to codes and coding. The coding manual for qualitative researchers*, 1-31.

- San Martín, H., & Rodríguez del Bosque, I. A. (2008). Exploring the cognitive–affective nature of destination image and the role of psychological factors in its formation. *Tourism Management*, 29(2), 263-277. doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2007.03.012
- Sánchez-Rivero, M., & Pulido-Fernández, J. (2011). Testing Heterogeneous Image in Cultural/Non-cultural Tourism Markets: A Latent Model Approach. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 25(2), 250-268. doi:10.1002/jtr.850
- Sathpathy, B., & Mahalik, D. (2010). A study on spiritual tourist site selection under multi-criteria. *South Asian Journal of Tourism and Heritage*, 3(1), 107-117.
- Schenk, K. L. (2010). Temple, Community, and Sacred Narrative in the Dura-Europos Synagogue. *AJS review*, 34(2), 195-229.
- Schmitt, B. H. (1996). Language and visual imagery: Issues of corporate identity in East Asia. *The Columbia Journal of World Business*, 30(4), 28-36.
- Schmitt, B. H., Pan, Y., & Tavassoli, N. T. (1994). Language and consumer memory: The impact of linguistic differences between Chinese and English. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 21(3), 419-431.
- Schnore, L. F. (1961). The statistical measurement of urbanization and economic development. *Land Economics*, 37(3), 229-245.
- Scott, H. (2007). The Temporal Integration of Connected Study into a Structured Life: A Grounded Theory. In B.G. Glaser, & J. Horton (Eds.). *The Grounded Theory Seminar Reader*. Mill Valley, CA: Sociology Press.
- Scott, H. (2009). What is Grounded Theory? Grounded Theory Online; supporting GT researchers. Retrieved August 6, 2015. <http://www.groundedtheoryonline.com/what-is-grounded-theory>
- Shao, Y., & Lu, J. G. (2008). The Planting Landscape Artistic of Chinese Temple Garden [J]. *Guangdong Landscape Architecture*, 1, 006.
- Shein, P., Li, Y., & Huang, C. (2014). Relationship between scientific knowledge and fortune-telling. *Public Understanding of Science*, 23(7). doi: 10.1177/0963662514522169.
- Sherker, S., Williamson, A., Hatfield, J., Brander, R., & Hayen, A. (2010). Beachgoers' beliefs and behaviours in relation to beach flags and rip currents. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 42(6), 1785-1804. doi:10.1016/j.aap.2010.04.020
- Shih, N. J., Wang, H. J., Lin, C. Y., & Liao, C. Y. (2007). 3D scan for the digital preservation of a historical temple in Taiwan. *Advances in engineering software*, 38(7), 501-512.

- Shrines in Phuket. (2016). Chinese Temples in Phuket - Phuket Attractions. Retrieved June 7, 2016, from <http://www.phuket.com/island/chinese-shrines.htm>
- Shuo, Y., Ryan, C., & Liu, G. (2009). Taoism, Temples and Tourists: The Case of Mazu Pilgrimage Tourism. *Tourism Management*, 30(4), 581-588. doi: 10.1016/j.tourman.2008.08.008
- Sirakaya, E., & Woodside, A. (2005). Building and testing theories of decision making by travellers. *Tourism Management*, 26, 815-832. doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2004.05.004
- Solomon, M. R. (1994). *Consumer behaviour. Buying, having and being*. 2nd ed. Boston. Allyn & Bacon. pp25.
- Sonmez, S., & Sirakaya, E. (2002). A Distorted Destination Image? The Case of Turkey. *Journal of Travel Research*, 41(2), 185-196.
- Sonnleitner, K. (2011). *Destination image and its effects on tourism marketing and branding: A case study about the Austrian National Tourist Office - with a special focus on the market Sweden (Unpublished master's thesis)*. Diss. Stockholm: Södertörn University College.
- Soto, D., Hodsoll, J., Rotshtein, P., & Humphreys, G. W. (2008). Automatic guidance of attention from working memory. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 12(9), 342-348.
- Spielberger, C. D., Gorsuch, R. L., & Lushene, R. E. (1970). *Manual for the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory*. Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press.
- Stabler, M. J. (1988). The image of destination regions: theoretical and empirical aspects. *Marketing in the tourism industry*, 133-161.
- Stedman, R., Beckley, T., Wallace, S., & Ambard, M. (2004). A picture and 1000 words: Using resident-employed photography to understand attachment to high amenity places. *Journal of Leisure Research*, 36(4), 580.
- Stirling, W. G. (1924). Chinese exorcists. *Journal of the Malayan Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 2(1 (90)), 41-47.
- Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1994). Handbook of qualitative research. In *Grounded theory methodology* (p. 273-285).
- Suminski, R. R., Poston, W. S., Petosa, R. L., Stevens, E., & Katzenmoyer, L. M. (2005). Features of the neighborhood environment and walking by U.S. adults. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 28(2), 149-155. doi:10.1016/j.amepre.2004.09.009
- Tapachai, N., & Waryszak, R. (2000). An examination of the role of beneficial image in tourist destination selection. *Journal of Travel Research*, 39, 37-44.

- Tapanes, M., Smith, G., & White, J. (2009). Cultural diversity in online learning: A study of the perceived effects of dissonance in levels of individualism/collectivism and tolerance of ambiguity. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 12(1), 26-34.
- Tasci, A. D. A. (2007). Assessment of destination image determinants using a multiple regression model. *Tourism Review*, 62(2): 23-30.
- Tasci, A. D. A., & Gartner, W. C. (2007). Destination image and its functional relationships. *Journal of Travel Research*, 45(4), 413-425.
- Tasci, A. D., Gartner, W. C. & Cavusgil, S. T. (2007). Conceptualization and operationalization of destination image. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 31(2), 194-223.
- TAT Phuket Vegetarian Festival. (2015). Tourism Authority of Thailand, Events & Festivals, Phuket Vegetarian Festival. Retrieved April 16, 2015, from <http://www.tourismthailand.org/See-and-Do/Events-and-Festivals/Phuket-Vegetarian-Festival--6350>
- Taylor, R. (1997). Official Altars, Temples and Shrines Mandated for All Counties in Ming and Qing. *T'oung Pao*, 83(1), 93-125.
- Teas, J. (1988). "I'm Studying Monkeys: What do You Do?": Youth and Travelers in Nepal. *Kroeber Anthropological Society Papers*, 67(8), 35-41.
- Temple of Heaven. (2016). Temple of Heaven. Retrieved December 22, 2016, from <http://en.tiantanpark.com/default.aspx>
- Thailand's Department of Tourism. (2015). Internal tourism in Phuket. Retrieved October 5, 2016, from <http://www.tourism.go.th/home/details/11/221/25767>
- Thai-Malaysian legacy. (2013). *Phuket Gazette*, Recalling a Thai-Malaysian legacy, Phuket History. Retrieved April 17, 2015, from <http://www.phuketgazette.net/phuket-lifestyle/Phuket-History-Recalling-a-Thai-Malaysian-legacy/21254#ad-image-0>
- The Independent. (2014, October 1). Phuket Vegetarian Festival 2014: Devotees perform extreme body piercing. Retrieved June 6, 2015, from <http://www.independent.co.uk/news/pictures/phuket-vegetarian-festival-2014-devotees-perform-extreme-body-piercing-9766820.html>
- The Nation. (2016). Innovation park helps turn Phuket into a smart city. Retrieved December 21, 2016, from http://www.nationmultimedia.com/news/Startup_and_IT/30295473
- Tomljenovic, R., & Kunst, I. (2014). From sun and sea tourism to cultural tourism-the case of Split-Dalmatia county. *European Journal of Tourism Research*, 8, 83.
- Tran, L. (2013). Measuring the perceived destination image of Vietnam in Finland. Master Thesis

- TripAdvisor Phuket History. (2013). TripAdvisor Phuket History. Retrieved April 17, 2015, from <http://www.tripadvisor.com/Travel-g293920-s203/Phuket:Thailand:History.html>
- TripAdvisor. (2015a). 4 Phuket Town, Thailand - Best Destinations in Thailand - Travelers' Choice Awards - TripAdvisor. Retrieved June 5, 2015, from <http://www.tripadvisor.com/TravelersChoice-Destinations-cTop-g293915>
- TripAdvisor. (2015b). Wat Mangkon Kamalawat, (Bangkok, Thailand) on TripAdvisor Review. Retrieved June 16, 2015, from http://www.tripadvisor.com/Attraction_Review-g293916-d2513887-Reviews-Wat_Mangkon_Kamalawat-Bangkok.html
- TripAdvisor. (2015c). Temple of Heaven (Tiantan Park), Beijing, China. Hours, Address, Tickets & Tours, Reviews. Retrieved June 7, 2015, from http://www.tripadvisor.com/Attraction_Review-g294212-d311534-Reviews-Temple_of_Heaven_Tiantan_Park-Beijing.html
- Trivourea, M. N., Karamanlidis, A. A., Tounta, E., Dendrinis, P., & Kotomatas, S. (2011). People and the Mediterranean Monk Seal (*Monachus monachus*): A Study of the Socioeconomic Impacts of the National Marine Park of Alonissos, Northern Sporades, Greece. *Aquatic Mammals*, 37(3), 305.
- UNEP. (2013). Chapter 7: Tourism. In UNEP. *Green Economy and Trade – Trends, Challenges and Opportunities* (pp. 259-285). Geneva, Switzerland: United Nations Environment Programme.
- UNESCO. (2015a). World Heritage Centre - Temple of Heaven: an Imperial Sacrificial Altar in Beijing. (2015). Retrieved May 3, 2015, from <http://whc.unesco.org/en/list/881>
- UNESCO. (2015b). World Heritage Centre - Ancient Building Complex in the Wudang Mountains. (2015). Retrieved May 3, 2015, <http://whc.unesco.org/en/list/705>
- UNWTO, (2014). UNWTO Tourism Highlights, 2014 edition World. (pp.3).
- UNWTO. (2016). UNWTO Tourism highlights, 2016 Edition, World's Top Tourist Destination Madrid, Spain: UNWTO. (pp. 6).
- Vaismoradi, M., Turunen, H., & Bondas, T. (2013). Content analysis and thematic analysis: Implications for conducting a qualitative descriptive study. *Nursing & health sciences*, 15(3), 398-405.
- Valdez, P., & Mehrabian, A. (1994). Effects of color on emotions. *Journal of experimental psychology: General*, 123(4), 394.
- Vazire, S., & Carlson, E. N. (2011). Others sometimes know us better than we know ourselves. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 20(2), 104-108.
- Ventura, M., Wade, R., & Bates, J. (2015). A Quiet Environment is a Healing Environment. *Journal of Peri Anesthesia Nursing*, 30(4), e2. doi:10.1016/j.jopan.2015.05.013

- Verellen, F. (1995). The Beyond Within: Grotto-Heavens (dongtian) in Taoist Ritual and Cosmology. *Cahiers d'Extrême-Asie*, 8(1), 265-290.
- Verwiebe, R. (2011). Why do Europeans Migrate to Berlin? Social-Structural Differences for Italian, British, French and Polish Nationals in the Period between 1980 and 2002*. *International Migration Int Migr*, 52(4), 209-230. doi:10.1111/j.1468-2435.2010.00663.x
- Virdee, I. (2017). Photographic Tourism Research: Literature Review. Unpublished manuscript. Retrieved August 29, 2017, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319271391_Photographic_Tourism_Research_Literature_Review
- Walker, K., Hall, D., & Hurst, W. (1990). Chapter 208 Frequently Performed Psychological Tests. In *Clinical methods: The history, physical, and laboratory examinations* (3 ed.). Boston: Butterworths.
- Walton, J. (1955). 30. Iron Gongs from the Congo and Southern Rhodesia. *Man*, 55, 20-23.
- Walton, J. (2014). Old-Time Religion in New New China: Alternative Religious Movements in the Post-Mao Era. *CrossCurrents*, 64(2), 262-281.
- Wang, K. Y. (2014). When a Taoist Temple Serves as a Seller and Believer Becomes a Buyer. *Review of Religious Research*, 56(2), 341-342.
- Wang, K. Y. (2015). Live with the Deity: Presence and Significance of Taiwanese Taoist Temple Affiliated Pilgrim Accommodation. *Review of Religious Research*, 57(1), 157-158.
- Wang, W. (2011). Explore the Phenomenon of Buddhist Temple Stay in South Korea for Tourists.
- Watters, T. (1899). *The Eighteen Lohan of Chinese Buddhist Temples*. Kelly and Walsh, limited.
- Webb, E. J., Campbell, D. T., Schwartz, R. D., & Sechrest, L. (1966). *Unobtrusive measures: Nonreactive research in the social sciences* (Vol. 111). Chicago: Rand McNally.
- Wei, G., Zhang, H., Wang, H., Fang, S., Zhang, B., & Yang, F. (2012). An experimental study on application of sticky rice-lime mortar in conservation of the stone tower in the Xiangji Temple. *Construction and Building Materials*, 28(1), 624-632.
- Wei, Z. H. O. U., Zhenfang, H. U. A. N. G., Wenyue, T. A. N. G., & Suyan, S. H. E. N. (2014). Research on the Differentiation of Perceived Dimensions after the Trip of the Cultural Tourism Destination based on the Urban Memory: A Case Study of Confucius Temple-Qinhuai River Scenic Area of Nanjing. *Tourism Tribune/Lvyou Xuekan*, 29(3).

- Westwood, S. (2007). What lies beneath? Using creative, projective and participatory techniques in qualitative tourism inquiry. *The Critical Turn in Tourism Studies: Innovative Methodologies*, Elsevier, Oxford, 293-316.
- Widiastuti, R., Rahmat, A., & Aseani, W. (2015). Conservation and Revitalitation in Semarang Chinatown (Klenteng "Chinese Shrine" as Physical Characteristic in Semarang Chinatown). *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 28, 549-556. doi:10.1016/j.proenv.2015.07.065
- Wilhelm, R., & Baynes, C. F. (1951). *The I Ching or book of changes*.
- Wilkerson, J. (2007). Negotiating local tradition with Taoism: Female ritual specialists in the Zhuang religion. *Religion*, 37(2), 150-163.
- Williams, H. C. (2002). Drawing as a sacred activity: Simple steps to explore your feelings and heal your consciousness. *New World Library*. pp 3-4.
- Wilson, G. D. (1966). Arousal properties of red versus green. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 23, 942-949.
- Winston, A. S., Kenyon, B., Stewardson, J. & Lepine, T. (1995). Children's sensitivity to expression of emotion in drawings. *Visual Arts Research*, 21, 1-14.
- Xu, Y., & McGehee, N. G. (2012). Shopping behavior of Chinese tourists visiting the United States: Letting the shoppers do the talking. *Tourism Management*, 33(2), 427-430.
- Xu, Z., & Zhang, J. (2016). Antecedents and consequences of place attachment: A comparison of Chinese and Western urban tourists in Hangzhou, China. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 5(2), 86-96.
- Yang, F. (2005). Between Secularist Ideology and Desecularizing Reality: The Birth and Growth of Religious Research in Communist China. *Religion and the Social Order*, 11, 19.
- Yang, F., & Hu, A. (2012). Mapping Chinese folk religion in mainland China and Taiwan. *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 51(3), 505-521.
- Yang, L., Gao, X., Wang, X., Nie, W., Wang, J., Gao, R., Xu, P., Shou, Y., Qingzhu Zhang, Q., & Wang, W. (2014). Impacts of firecracker burning on aerosol chemical characteristics and human health risk levels during the Chinese New Year Celebration in Jinan, China. *Science of The Total Environment*, 476-477, 57-64. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.12.110
- Yfantidou, G. (2008). Tourist Roles, Gender and Age in Greece: A Study of Tourists in Greece Georgia Yfantidou, George Costa, Maria Michalopoulos. *International Journal of Sport Management, Recreation & Tourism*, 1(1), 14-30.

- Zentner, M., Grandjean, D., & Scherer, K. R. (2008). Emotions evoked by the sound of music: characterization, classification, and measurement. *Emotion*, 8(4), 494.
- Zhang, B., Song, Y., Guan, S., & Zhang, Y. (2010). Historic Chinese Architectures Image Retrieval by SVM and Pyramid Histogram of Oriented Gradients Features. *International Journal of Soft Computing*, 5(2), 19-28. doi:10.3923/ijscmp.2010.19.28
- Zhang, G. (2013). Translation of the Names of Chinese Temples from the Perspective of Culture. *Studies in Asian Social Science*, 1(1), p6.
- Zhang, S., & Lu, R. (2012). ICA 3 D–Intelligent computer-aided ancient Chinese architecture design. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 26(4), 705-715.
- Zhou, Q. B., Zhang, J., & Edelheim, J. R. (2013). Rethinking traditional Chinese culture: A consumer-based model regarding the authenticity of Chinese calligraphic landscape. *Tourism Management*, 36, 99-112.
- Zweifel, C., & Wezemaal, J. (2012). Drawing as a qualitative research tool: An approach to field work from a social complexity perspective'. *Tracey Journal: Drawing Knowledge*, 05, 1-16.

TABLES & FIGURES

Table 9.1.1 Chinese (Taoist/Daoist) temple and shrine studies from 1898 to 2015

No	Author	Year	Title	Context	Location
1	Watters, T.	1898	The Eighteen Lohan of Chinese Buddhist Temples	Figures images	China
2	Eberhard, W.	1962	Economic Activities of a Chinese Temple in California	Economic activities, education and religion	USA
3	Eberhard, W.	1967	Topics and Moral Values in Chinese Temple Decorations	Socio-economic values and art	Unknown
4	Cohen, A., Jaw, Y.	1977	A Chinese Temple Keeper Talks about Chinese Folk Religion	Folk religion	China
5	Hung, W.	1988	From Temple To Tomb: Ancient Chinese Art and Religion in Transition	Worship, ceremonies and politics	China
6	Hill, A.	1992	Chinese Funerals and Chinese Ethnicity in Chiang Mai, Thailand	Ceremonies, ethnicity and culture	Thailand
7	Formoso, B.	1996	Chinese Temples and Philanthropic Associations in Thailand	Cultural and political	Thailand
8	Gao, M. C. F.	2000	Jun Jing: The Temple of Memories: history, power and morality in a Chinese village.	History, political, and ethical	China
9	Fang, G., et al.,	2002	Suspended particulate variations and mass size distributions of incense burning at Tzu Yun Yen temple in Taiwan, Taichung	Environmental science, health and safety and pilgrim's behaviour	Taiwan
10	Lin, T., et al.,	2002	Characteristics of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and total suspended particulate in indoor and outdoor atmosphere of a Taiwanese temple	Environmental science and health and safety	Taiwan
11	Grimwade, G.	2003	Gold, gardens, temples and feasts: Chinese temple, Croydon, Queensland. [Paper in issue entitled 'Archaeology of the Overseas Chinese'.]	Gardens and temple feasts	Australia

12	Chang, Y. M., Lu, N. H., & Wu, T. C.	2005	Application of 3D laser scanning technology in historical building preservation: a case study of a Chinese temple	Technology and historical heritage measurement	Taiwan
13	Chan, S.	2005	Temple-Building and Heritage in China	Cultural heritage, religious activities and tourism	China
14	Lang, G., Chan, S. C., & Ragvald, L.	2005	Folk Temples and the Chinese Religious Economy	Folk Temples and Chinese Religious Economy	China
15	Goossaert, V.	2006	Resident Specialists and Temple Managers in Late Imperial China	History, management and rituals	China
16	Jianlin, Z.	2007	The Exploration of Chinese Temple Gardens	Religion, humanities, landscape and nature	China
17	Jiandong, B.	2007	Comparative Study of Chinese Temple Fair and Western Carnival	Cultural comparison, folklore and entertainment	Unknown
18	Lei, W.	2007	Research on Arrangement of Landscape Plants in Chinese Temple Areas	History and landscape	China
19	Wilkerson, J.	2007	Negotiating local tradition with Taoism: Female ritual specialists in the Zhuang religion	Religion, gender roles and rituals	China
20	Fisher, G.	2008	The Spiritual Land Rush: Merit and Morality in New Chinese Buddhist Temple Construction	Cultural, management and political	China
21	Shao, Y., & Lu, J. G.	2008	The Planting Landscape Artistic of Chinese Temple Garden	Landscape and customs	China
22	Navasumrit, P., et al.,	2008	Potential health effects of exposure to carcinogenic compounds in incense smoke in temple workers	Environmental science and health and safety	Thailand
23	Jian, W. A. N. G.	2009	Temple community of folk religion in Jiangnan since the Ming and Qing dynasties: Focus on Suzhou and Songjiang areas	Management, communities and religious activities	China

24	Chang, L., & Liu, W.	2009	Temple fairs in Taiwan: Environmental strategies and competitive advantage for cultural tourism	Cultural tourism and temple cultural	Taiwan
25	Shuo, Y., Ryan, C., & Liu, G.	2009	Taoism, Temples And Tourists: The Case Of Mazu Pilgrimage Tourism	Religious tourism and worship	Taiwan
26	Ismail, S., & Mohd-Ali, N.	2011	The Imaging of Heritage Conservation in Historic City of George Town for City Marketing	Marketing, image and heritage tourism	Malaysia
27	Yang, F., & Hu, A.	2012	Mapping Chinese Folk Religion in Mainland China and Taiwan	Folk rituals in the temple	China and Taiwan
28	Nadeau, R., & Meulenbeld, M.	2012	Chinese Religion in the Ming and Qing Dynasties	Temple gods, religion, religious activity and culture	China
29	Zhou, Q., Zhang, J., & Edelheim, J.	2012	Rethinking traditional Chinese culture: A consumer-based model regarding the authenticity of Chinese calligraphic landscape	Temple art, cultural, perceptions and attraction	China
30	Zhang, S., & Lu, R.	2012	ICA3D – Intelligent computer-aided ancient Chinese architecture design	Temple architecture, engineering and technology	China
31	Wei, G., et al.,	2012	An experimental study on application of sticky rice–lime mortar in conservation of the stone tower in the Xiangji Temple	Cultural heritage, chemical engineering and materials	China
32	Kataoka, T.	2012	Religion as Non-religion: The Place of Chinese Temples in Phuket, Southern Thailand	Politics, religious culture, management	Thailand
33	Chang, S., et al.,	2012	Deep sole burns in several participants in a traditional festival of the firewalking ceremony in Kee-lung, Taiwan—Clinical experiences and prevention strategies	Ceremony and health and safety	Taiwan
34	Brown, D., & Cheng, T.	2012	Religious Relations across the Taiwan Strait: Patterns, Alignments, and Political Effects	historical, religious and political	Taiwan
35	Ma, X., Sun, X., He, Y., & Chen, Y.	2013	Parking Choice Behavior Investigation: A Case Study at Beijing Lama Temple	Tourist behaviour	China

36	Walton, J.	2014	Old-Time Religion in New New China: Alternative Religious Movements in the Post-Mao Era	Government policies, religious institutions, social and economic activities	China
37	Kustedja, S., Sudikno, A., & Salura, P.	2014	Local deities as symbol of acculturated Chinese diasporas temples in Indonesia	Attitudes of acculturation and worship local symbols	Indonesia
38	Laing, J., Wheeler, F., Reeves, K., & Frost, W.	2014	Assessing the experiential value of heritage assets: A case study of a Chinese heritage precinct, Bendigo, Australia	Cultural heritage, tourism management and visitor experience	Australia
39	Wang, K.	2014	When a Taoist Temple Serves as a Seller and Believer Becomes a Buyer	Lamp lighting, worshipper attitudes, religion and profit	Taiwan
40	Hong, Z., & Yan, J.	2015	Quantitative Studies on the Historical Development of Chinese Taoist Temples since 1911	Spatial, comparative, historical and religious perspectives	China
41	Deng, Z., Lin, Y., Zhao, M., & Wang, S.	2015	Collaborative planning in the new media age: The Dafo Temple controversy, China	Social media, collaborative planning	China
42	Wang, K.	2015	Live with the Deity: Presence and Significance of Taiwanese Taoist Temple Affiliated Pilgrim Accommodation	Temple hostel	Taiwan

Table 9.1.2 Religious temples and shrine studies concentrating on temple tourism, temple image, temple attraction, temple attitudes and temple behaviour

No	Author	Year	Title	Context	Location	Temple
1	Farquhar, J.	1928	Temple-and-Image Worship in Hinduism	Temple image	India	Unknown
2	Fleischer, A.	2000	The tourist behind the pilgrim in the Holy Land	Characteristics and behaviour of pilgrims and tourists	Israel	Not specified
3	Baedcharoen, I.	2000	Impacts of religious tourism in Thailand	Residents' attitudes	Thailand	Multiple
4	Levy, R.	2001	Temple Site at Phimai: Modeling for the Scholar and the Tourist	Tourist image	Thailand	Phimai temple
5	Gatrell, J., & Collins-Kreiner, N.	2006	Negotiated space: Tourists, pilgrims, and the Bahá'í terraced gardens in Haifa	Tourist and pilgrim experience	Israeli	Shrine of the Bab and surrounding area
6	Mckercher, B., & Ho, P.	2006	Assessing the Tourism Potential of Smaller Cultural and Heritage Attractions	Tourist experience and management	China	Multiple
7	Hashim, N. H., Murphy, J. and Hashim, N. M.	2007	Islam and Online Imagery on Malaysian Tourist Destination Websites	Religious destination imagery online	Malaysia	Multiple
8	Chang, L., & Liu, W.	2009	Temple fairs in Taiwan: Environmental strategies and competitive advantage for cultural tourism	Temple marketing and activities	Taiwan	Multiple
9	Kaplan, U.	2010	Images of Monasticism: The Temple Stay Program and the Re-branding of Korean Buddhist Temples	Temple Identity and branding	Korea	Not specified
10	Mallapragada, M.	2010	Desktop deities: Hindu temples, online cultures and the politics of remediation	Temples and new media	India	Unknown

11	Schenk, K.	2010	Temple, Community, and Sacred Narrative in the Dura-Europos Synagogue	Temple image	Syria	Dura-Europos synagogue
12	Hannapha, P., & Thonglert, G.	2011	The Integration of Image and Text for Communication in the Mural Paintings of Potharam Temple in Nadoon District, Maha Sarakham Province	Storytelling and temple image and text	Thailand	Potharam Temple
13	Guha, A.	2012	Krishnalila in Terracotta Temples of Bengal	Storytelling and temple image	India	Raghnatha temple
14	Della Dora, V.	2012	Setting and Blurring Boundaries: Pilgrims, Tourists, and Landscape in Mount Athos and Meteora	Tourists attraction and pilgrims' experience	Greece	Mount Athos and Meteora monasteries
15	Kurd, N.	2012	Sacred Manifestations: The Making and Meaning of Mosques in Canada.	Temple image	Canada	Multiple
16	Zhou, Q., Zhang, J., & Edelheim, J.	2012	Rethinking traditional Chinese culture: A consumer-based model regarding the authenticity of Chinese calligraphic landscape.	Temple art, cultural, perceptions and attraction	China	Hantai and Mianxian Wuhou Temples
17	Chen, C., & Phou, S.	2013	A closer look at destination: Image, personality, relationship and loyalty	Temple image and personality	Cambodia	Angkor Wat
18	Choe, J., Dong, E., Chick, G., Wright, A., & Zhang, L.	2013	Turner's communitas and non-Buddhists who visit Buddhist temples	Tourism motivations	USA	Chua Ba Thien Hau Buddhist temple

19	Canny, I.	2013	An Empirical Investigation of Service Quality, Tourist Satisfaction and Future Behavioral Intentions among Domestic Local Tourist at Borobudur Temple	Temple service quality, tourist satisfaction and behaviour	Indonesian	Borobudur Temple
20	Piewdang, S., Mekkamol, P., & Untachai, S.	2013	Measuring Spiritual Tourism Management in Community: A Case Study of Sri Chom Phu Ongtu Temple, Thabo district, Nongkhai Province, Thailand	Temple attraction potential	Thailand	Sri Chom Phu Ongtu Temple
21	Lucang, W. A. N. G., & Wei, L. I.	2013	Urban Space Ture under the Influence of Tourism: A Case Study of Langmusi Town, Gannan Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture	Temple space and tourism	Tibetan	Buddhist temple
22	Mengyuan, Q. I. U., Fang, W. A. N. G., Run, S. H. A., & Guolin, H. O. U.	2013	Tourists' Perception of and Satisfaction with Soundscape Properties in Tourist Areas: A Case Study of Nanjing Confucius Temple-Qinhuai Scenic Area	Tourists' perception of and satisfaction	China	Nanjing Confucius Temple-Qinhuai Scenic Area
23	Ma, X., Sun, X., He, Y., & Chen, Y.	2013	Parking Choice Behavior Investigation: A Case Study at Beijing Lama Temple	Tourist behaviour	China	Beijing Lama Temple
24	Choe, J., Blazey, M., & Mitas, O.	2014	Motivations of non-Buddhists visiting Buddhist temples	Tourists motivation and spiritual activities	USA	Multiple
25	Zhou, W., Huang, Z., Tang, W., & Shen, S.	2014	Research on the Differentiation of Perceived Dimensions after the Trip of the Cultural Tourism Destination based on the Urban Memory: A Case Study of Confucius Temple-Qinhuai River Scenic Area of Nanjing	Tourist and residents' perceptions and marketing	China	Confucius Temple in the Qinhuai River Scenic Area

26	Wang, K.	2014	When a Taoist Temple Serves as a Seller and Believer Becomes a Buyer	Attitudes and marketing	Taiwan	Multiple
27	Porcu, E.	2014	Pop Religion in Japan: Buddhist Temples, Icons, and Branding	Brand image	Japan	Ryōhōji temple
28	Nyaupane, G., Timothy, D., Poudel, S.	2015	Understanding tourists in religious destinations: A social distance perspective	Pilgrim and tourist motivation	Nepal	Lumbini temple complex and local area
29	Lu, L., Chi, C., & Liu, Y.	2015	Authenticity, involvement, and image: Evaluating tourist experiences at historic districts	Authenticity, Tourist involvement, image, Satisfaction	China	Renwei temple

Figure 9.2.1 McKercher & Du Cros, (2002). A Cultural Tourist Typology

Table 9.3.1 Themes used for thematic analysis including references

No.	Theme	Reference
1.	abundant	Kobayashi, Pollack, & Pomerance, (2009)
2.	adequate	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007); Chang, Lu, & Wu, (2005)
3.	aged	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003)
4.	altar	Taylor, (1997)
5.	animals	Hung, (1988)
6.	architecture	Shih, Wang, Lin, & Liao, (2007); Chang, Lu, & Wu, (2005)
7.	artwork	Hung, (1988)
8.	Asian	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003); Jenkins (1999)
9.	atmosphere	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003)
10.	attractive	Desmet, (2012)
11.	background noise	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
12.	banners	Chia-chü, (1981); Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
13.	bell	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007); Hung, (1988)
14.	beneficial	Lin, Rau, Liu, Lin, Ying, & Kao, (2015)
15.	breeze	Jenkins (1999)
16.	brisk	Jenkins (1999)
17.	Buddhist	Lin, Rau, Liu, Lin, Ying, & Kao, (2015); Jenkins (1999)
18.	burning paper	Hung, (1988)
19.	burnt offerings	Hung, (1988)
20.	busy	Jenkins (1999); Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
21.	calligraphy	Zhou, Zhang, & Edelheim, (2012)
22.	carvings	Hung, (1988)
23.	chimney	Hung, (1988)
24.	Chinese	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003); Jenkins (1999)
25.	clean	Jenkins (1999)
26.	clear skies	Jenkins (1999)
27.	cloudy	Jenkins (1999)
28.	colourful	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
29.	columns	Zhang, & Chen, (2013); Chang, Lu, & Wu, (2005)
30.	commercial	Jenkins (1999)
31.	confined	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
32.	conflicting	Mcdonald, Fielding, & Louis, (2014)
33.	confusing	Moore, & Barker, (2012)

No.	Theme	Reference
34.	convenient	Suminski, Poston, Petosa, Stevens, & Katzenmoyer, (2005)
35.	cool	Jenkins (1999)
36.	cultural	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003)
37.	cultural attraction	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003); Jenkins (1999)
38.	dangerous	Jenkins (1999)
39.	decorated	Hung, (1988); Chang, Lu, & Wu, (2005)
40.	detailed	Chang, Lu, & Wu, (2005)
41.	ding/pot/cauldron	Hung, (1988)
42.	dirty	Jenkins (1999)
43.	disappointing	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
44.	divination	Shein, Li, & Huang, (2014)
45.	donating	Hall, (2001)
46.	donation box	Martin, & Randal, (2008)
47.	dragons	Shih, Wang, Lin, & Liao, (2007)
48.	drum	Hung, (1988)
49.	eating	Jenkins (1999)
50.	educational	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
51.	elevated	Hung, (1988)
52.	entrance fee	Hirai, Kitama, & Nishimura, (2000)
53.	exciting	Jenkins (1999)
54.	experienced	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
55.	extreme	Cohen, (2001)
56.	fame	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003)
57.	famous	Jenkins (1999), Echtner and Ritchie's (2003)
58.	fascinating	Degen, (2012); Hidi, S. (2006)
59.	firecrackers	Yang, Gao, Wang, Nie, Wang, Gao, Xu, Shou, Qingzhu Zhang, & Wang (2014)
60.	flags	Sherker, Williamson, A. Hatfield, Brander, & Hayen, (2010)
61.	food	Jenkins (1999); Echtner and Ritchie's (2003)
62.	food stalls	Jenkins (1999); Echtner and Ritchie's (2003)
63.	friendly	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
64.	functional	Jenkins (1999)
65.	gate	Zhang, Song, Guan, & Zhang, (2010)
66.	geometric	Chang, Lu, & Wu, (2005)
67.	gong	Walton, (1955)

No.	Theme	Reference
68.	hidden	Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
69.	hot	Hung, (1988), Jenkins (1999)
70.	humbling	Landrum, (2011)
71.	humid	Jenkins, (1999)
72.	intense	Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
73.	intoxicating	Fang, Chang, Wu, Yang, Chang, & Yang, (2002)
74.	inviting	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
75.	kneeler pads	Crowe, (2011)
76.	lanterns	Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
77.	looking around	Nyaupane, Timothy, & Poudel, (2015)
78.	loud	Gomez & Danuser, (2004)
79.	lucky	Widiastuti, Rahmat, & Aseani, (2015)
80.	making an offering	Hung, (1988)
81.	meditating	Zentner, Grandjean, & Scherer, (2008)
82.	men	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
83.	mild	Jenkins (1999)
84.	minimalistic	Macarthur, (2002)
85.	mixture of beliefs	Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
86.	mixture of cultures	Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
87.	musical	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
88.	mysterious	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003); Buzinde, Choi, & Wang, (2012)
89.	natural	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003)
90.	neutral	Bettencourt, Talley, Benjamin, & Valentine, (2006)
91.	new	Hong, Yan, Zhaohui, & Jiamin, (2015)
92.	noisy	Gomez & Danuser, (2004);
93.	none	Bettencourt, Talley, Benjamin, & Valentine, (2006)
94.	none/silence	Jenkins (1999)
95.	numerous	Kobayashi, Pollack, & Pomerance, (2009)
96.	of incense pot	Hung, (1988); Fang, Chang, Wu, Yang, Chang, & Yang, (2002)
97.	offerings	Hung, (1988)
98.	oil lamp	Heinze, (1981)
99.	ordered	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
100.	ordinary	Jenkins (1999)
101.	organised	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)

No.	Theme	Reference
102.	palanquin	Stirling, (1924)
103.	passive	Kagan & Moss, (1960)
104.	pathway	Hung, (1988)
105.	peaceful	Lin, Rau, Liu, Lin, Ying, & Kao, (2015)
106.	people talking	Jensen & Arens, (2005); Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
107.	pictures	Hung, (1988)
108.	placard/plate/sign	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
109.	pleasant	Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
110.	powerful	Zentner, Grandjean, & Scherer, (2008)
111.	protection	Jenkins (1999); Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
112.	quiet	Ventura, Wade, & Bates, (2015)
113.	rejuvenating	Jenkins (1999)
114.	relaxing	Jenkins (1999)
115.	religious	Lin, Rau, Liu, Lin, Ying, & Kao, (2015); Hung, (1988)
116.	reserved	Kokkinos, Panayiotou, & Davazoglou, (2004)
117.	respect	Hung, (1988); Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
118.	roof	Zhang, & Chen, (2013); Shih, Wang, Lin, & Liau, (2007)
119.	sacred	Buzinde, Choi, & Wang, (2012)
120.	safe	Jenkins (1999)
121.	scary	Bennett, (2007)
122.	shop	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003)
123.	smoky	Fang, Chang, Wu, Yang, Chang, & Yang, (2002)
124.	sophisticated	Jenkins (1999)
125.	spacious	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
126.	spiritual	Lin, Rau, Liu, Lin, Ying, & Kao, (2015)
127.	stairs/steps/ramp	Pettit, (2008)
128.	statues/figures	Hung, (1988); Chang, Lu, & Wu, (2005)
129.	stone	Zhang, & Chen, (2013); Hung, (1988)
130.	suffocating	Fang, Chang, Wu, Yang, Chang, & Yang, (2002)
131.	sunny	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003); Jenkins (1999)
132.	surrounded by buildings	Chang, Lu, & Wu, (2005)
133.	symbolic	Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014); Hung, (1988)
134.	taking photos	Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
135.	Taoist	Lin, Rau, Liu, Lin, Ying, & Kao, (2015); Jenkins (1999)

No.	Theme	Reference
136.	Thai	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003); Jenkins (1999)
137.	the wall	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
138.	traditional	Jenkins (1999)
139.	undecorated	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
140.	unease	Zentner, Grandjean, & Scherer, (2008)
141.	unfriendly	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
142.	unidentifiable	Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
143.	unique	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003); Jenkins (1999)
144.	unorganised	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
145.	unusual	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003); Jenkins (1999)
146.	vegetarian	Echtner and Ritchie's (2003); Jenkins (1999)
147.	warm	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
148.	weapons	Boretz,(1995); Laing, Wheeler, Reeves, & Frost, (2014)
149.	women	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)
150.	working	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007); Jenkins (1999)
151.	worthwhile	Bonn, Joseph-Mathews, Dai, Hayes, & Cave, (2007)

Table 9.4.1 Number of respondents at Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket

Location	Frequency	%
Chinese Temples in Phuket		
Bang Neow	22	14.4
Hok Nguan Kung	22	14.4
Jui Tui	21	13.7
Kathu	21	13.7
Pud Jor	20	13.1
Saphan Hin	24	15.7
Serene Light	23	15.0
Total	153	100.0

Table 9.4.2 Respondent's socio-demographic profile

Category	Frequency	%
Gender		
Female	74	48.4
Male	79	51.6
Total	153	100
Age Range		
13 – 19	3	2.0
20 – 39	115	75.2
40 – 64	34	22.1
65+	1	0.7
Total	153	100
Education Level		
College Level	13	8.5
Bachelor's Degree	124	81.0
Master's Degree	16	10.5
Total	153	100
Income (in USD per month)		
\$1000 and below	22	14.4
\$1001–3000	82	53.6
\$3001–5000	43	28.0
\$5001–10,000	5	3.3
\$10,000 and above	1	0.7
Total	153	100
Marital Status		
Single	114	74.5
Married	36	23.5
Divorced	3	2.0
Total	153	100

Region		
Africa	4	2.6
Asia	56	36.6
Australia	10	6.5
Europe	65	42.5
North America	17	11.1
South America	1	0.7
Total	153	100

Religion/Belief		
Agnostic	14	9.2
Buddhist	21	13.7
Christian	48	31.4
Hindu	2	1.3
Jewish	2	1.3
Muslim	3	2.0
None	53	34.6
Shinto	1	0.7
Spiritual	6	3.8
Taoist	3	2.0
Total	153	100

Table 9.4.2 Respondents' nationalities and regional classifications

Region	Country	Total	%
Africa	South Africa (4).	4	2.6
Asian	Cambodia (1), China (17), India (1), Japan (8), Malaysia (3), Russia (12), Singapore (4), South Korea (10).	56	36.6
Australia	Australia (8), New Zealand (2).	10	6.5
Europe	Austria (2), Belgium (1), Britain (14), Netherlands (2), Finland (2), France (10), Germany (9), Greece (2), Ireland (3), Italy (3), Norway (2), Poland (1), Portugal (1), Spain (3), Sweden (6), Switzerland (3), Turkey (1).	65	42.5
North America	Canada (3), United States (14).	17	11.1
South America	Mexico (1).	1	0.7
Total		153	100

Table 9.4.3 Travel behaviour of tourists who visit Chinese temples in Phuket

Category	Frequency	%
Type of Visit to Phuket		
Holiday	153	100
Total	153	100
Time in Phuket		
1 Week	1	0.7
2 Weeks	19	12.4
3 Weeks	82	53.6
1 Month	17	11.1
2 Months	11	7.2
3 Months	6	3.9
4 Months	8	5.2
5 Months	6	3.9
6 Months	3	2.0
Total	153	100
Type of Tourist		
Adventurer	5	3.3
Backpacker	16	10.5
Cultural	74	48.4
Explorer	8	5.2
Leisure	48	31.4
Traveller	2	1.3
Total	153	100

Table 9.4.2.1 Details of respondent's experience at Chinese temples in Phuket

Category	Frequency	%
Experience of a Chinese Temple in Phuket		
Previous experience	102	66.7
First experience	51	33.3
Total	153	100
Planned Visit to a Chinese Temple in Phuket		
No	111	72.5
Yes	42	27.5
Total	153	100
Time of Visit		
Morning – 08:00-12:00	12	7.8
Afternoon – 12:01-18:00	122	79.7
Evening – 18:01-20:00	19	12.4
Total	153	100
Length of Temple Visit		
Less than 30 minutes	108	70.6
About 31 – 60 minutes	41	26.8
About 61 – 90 minutes	4	2.6
Total	153	100
Travel Accompaniment		
None	41	26.8
Friend(s)	76	49.7
Family member(s)	31	20.3
Personal tour guide	5	3.3
Total	153	100

Number of Temples Visited		
0	51	33.3
1	27	17.6
2	27	17.6
3	24	15.7
5	10	6.5
4	9	5.9
6	3	2.0
9	1	0.7
10	1	0.7
Total	153	100

Table 9.4.5 Factors affecting a Chinese Temple visitation in Phuket

Category	Frequency	%
Respondents Influence to Visit		
Guidebook	2	1.3
Internet	20	13.1
Tour guide	1	0.7
Past experience	1	0.7
Repeat visit	1	0.7
TV	5	3.3
Walking past	43	28.1
Word of mouth	80	52.3
Total	153	100

Table 9.4.6 Respondents' expectations before visiting a Chinese temple in Phuket

Theme	Frequency	%
Respondents Expectations		
no expectations	76	46.3
thought it would be bigger	23	14.0
thought it would be smaller	8	4.9
thought there would be more information	7	4.3
thought it would be peaceful	5	3.0
other expectations	45	27.5
Total	164	100

Table 9.4.7 Provision of information at Chinese temples in Phuket

Category	Frequency	%
Information Available		
Excellent	2	1.3
Good	7	4.6
Fair	63	41.2
Poor	50	32.7
Very Poor	31	20.3

Mean = 2.34 | Std. Deviation = 0.897

Table 9.4.8 Level of visitor satisfaction at Chinese temples in Phuket

Category	Frequency	%
Organisational Satisfaction		
Very satisfied	38	24.8
Satisfied	68	44.4
Neither	43	28.1
Dissatisfied	4	2.6
Total	153	100

Mean = 3.92 | Std. Deviation = 0.794

Table 9.4.9 Activities engaged at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket

Category	Frequency	%
Respondents Activities		
Asking for advice	7	2.2
Burning offerings	50	15.7
Buying a souvenir	1	0.3
Divination	10	3.1
Eating food	2	0.6
Learning about the culture	2	0.6
Looking around	92	28.9
Praying	49	15.4
Ringling the bell	12	3.8
Taking photos	93	29.2
Total	318	100

Table 9.4.10 Respondents spending behaviour at Chinese temples in Phuket

Category	Frequency	%
Money Spent (in THB)		
0	94	61.4
1 – 100	49	32.0
101 – 200	7	4.6
301 – 400	2	1.3
401 or more	1	0.7
Total	153	100
Item Bought		
Buddha Statue	1	0.7
Firecrackers	3	2.0
Incense	54	35.3
Nothing	94	61.4
Oil	1	0.7
Total	153	100
Donation		
No	89	58.2
Yes	64	41.8
Total	153	100

Table 9.4.11 The reasons that international tourists visited Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket

Theme	Frequency	%
Why Tourists Visited		
Fascinating	74	35.6
Cultural activity	69	33.2
Recommended	28	13.5
Passing by	14	6.7
Important temple	11	5.3
Location	5	2.4
Education	3	1.4
Spiritual feeling	3	1.4
Eat food	1	0.5
Total	208	100.0

Table 9.4.12 First images that come to mind when thinking of a Chinese temple overall

Overall Themes	Frequency	%
First image that comes to mind?		
statues/figures/gods	136	21.2
religion/tradition	124	19.3
decorations	105	16.4
religious ornaments	88	13.7
building features	59	9.2
atmosphere	47	7.3
architecture	21	3.3
offerings	15	2.3
education	10	1.6
attractive	9	1.4
divination	9	1.4
the location	8	1.2
fame	5	0.8
organisation	3	0.5
music	2	0.3
Total	641	100.0

Table 9.4.13 First images that came to mind when thinking of a Chinese temple for Asians

Asian Themes	Frequency	%
First image that comes to mind?		
religion/tradition	45	21.4
statues/figures/gods	42	20.0
building features	25	11.9
decorations	25	11.9
religious ornaments	25	11.9
atmosphere	21	10.0
architecture	5	2.4
divination	5	2.4
offerings	5	2.4
fame	4	1.9
education	3	1.4
organisation	3	1.4
attractive	2	1.0
Total	210	100

Table 9.4.14 First images that came to mind when thinking of a Chinese temple for Europeans

European Themes	Frequency	%
First image that comes to mind?		
statues/figures/gods	28	26.9
decorations	22	21.2
religion/tradition	22	21.2
religious ornaments	21	20.2
atmosphere	6	5.8
building features	4	3.8
attractive	1	1.0
Total	104	100

Table 9.4.15 The distinctive features of Chinese temple in Phuket overall

Overall Themes	Frequency	%
The distinctive features		
decorations	170	24.3
religious ornaments	131	18.7
statues/figures/gods	119	17.0
religion/tradition	82	11.7
building features	53	7.6
architecture	35	5.0
donation box	33	4.7
offerings	25	3.6
the location	18	2.6
smell	11	1.6
atmosphere	8	1.2
fame	8	1.2
attractive	3	0.4
music	2	0.3
no entrance fee	1	0.1
Total	699	100.0

Table 9.4.16 The distinctive features of Chinese temple in Phuket for Asian

Asian Themes	Frequency	%
The distinctive features		
decorations	60	26.5
religious ornaments	39	17.3
statues/figures/gods	34	15.0
religion/tradition	29	12.8
building features	14	6.2
architecture	13	5.8
donation box	12	5.3
offerings	7	3.1
fame	6	2.7
smell	5	2.2
the location	3	1.3
attractive	2	0.9
atmosphere	1	0.4
music	1	0.4
Total	226	100

Table 9.4.17 The distinctive features of Chinese temple in Phuket for Europeans

European Themes	Frequency	%
The distinctive features		
statues/figures/gods	33	24.8
decorations	31	23.3
religion/tradition	22	16.5
religious ornaments	21	15.8
building features	10	7.5
donation box	9	6.8
offerings	3	2.3
the location	2	1.5
architecture	1	0.8
fame	1	0.8
Total	133	100

Table 9.4.18 Overall respondents first impressions when entering a Chinese temple in Phuket

Overall Themes	Frequency	%
The first impression/feeling		
religion/tradition	83	16.1
fascinating	60	11.6
peaceful	51	9.9
respect	50	9.7
spiritual	39	7.5
uniqueness	38	7.4
mysterious	37	7.2
attraction	26	5.0
decorative	22	4.3
architecture	17	3.3
joy	13	2.5
energy	11	2.1
inviting	11	2.1
organisation	11	2.1
nature	10	1.9
others	38	7.3
Total	517	100.0

Table 9.4.19 Asian tourist's first impressions when entering a Chinese temple in Phuket

Asian Themes	Frequency	%
The first impression/feeling		
religion/tradition	29	17.9
fascinating	18	11.1
uniqueness	16	9.9
peaceful	15	9.3
respect	11	6.8
spiritual	11	6.8
architecture	8	4.9
attraction	8	4.9
joy	7	4.3
mysterious	7	4.3
busy	6	3.7
organisation	5	3.1
confusion	4	2.5
decorative	4	2.5
energy	3	1.9
others	10	6.1
Total	162	100.0

Table 9.4.20 European tourist's first impression when entering a Chinese temple in Phuket

European Themes	Frequency	%
The first impression/feeling		
religion/tradition	36	15.6
fascinating	25	10.8
peaceful	25	10.8
respect	24	10.4
mysterious	19	8.2
spiritual	18	7.8
decorative	14	6.1
attraction	12	5.2
uniqueness	12	5.2
inviting	9	3.9
architecture	7	3.0
energy	6	2.6
confusion	4	1.7
nature	4	1.7
organisation	4	1.7
others	12	5.3
Total	231	100.0

Table 9.4.21 Frequency of responses for projective questions

Question	Frequency	%
The Chinese temple or shrine is...	295	6.3
The layout of the temple is...	191	4.0
The space is...	195	4.1
The area around the temple is...	246	5.2
The view from the outside is...	249	5.3
The view from the inside is...	250	5.3
The architecture is...	257	5.4
The decorations are...	392	8.3
The staff or keepers are...	185	3.9
The climate is...	174	3.7
The feeling I get at this location is...	238	5.0
The smell is...	209	4.4
The environment is...	253	5.4
The sounds are...	210	4.5
The atmosphere is...	188	4.0
The activities are...	301	6.4
The religion is...	201	4.3
The culture is...	312	6.6
The experience is...	371	7.9
Total	4717	100.0

Table 9.4.22 The overall image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using projective questions

Question	1st Theme (%)	2nd Theme (%)	3rd Theme (%)	4th Theme (%)	5th Theme (%)
The Chinese temple or shrine is...	religious 34.9	attractive 7.8	cultural attraction 7.8	colourful 7.5	unique 7.1
The layout of the temple is...	confined 24.1	organised 22.5	spacious 20.9	geometric 8.4	mysterious 6.8
The space is...	confined 41.0	spacious 32.8	adequate 9.2	religious 5.1	geometric 3.6
The area around the temple is...	busy 26.8	commercial 17.5	a street 13.4	sur. by nature 12.6	sur. by buildings 8.9
The view from the outside is...	the gate 14.5	hidden 10.8	attractive 9.2	walled 7.6	colourful 7.2
The view from the inside is...	religious 13.2	attractive 10.4	colourful 10.0	mysterious 10.0	statues/figures 7.6
The architecture is...	traditional 30.5	unique 9.8	colourful 9.4	of stone 9.4	aged 7.0
The decorations are...	colourful 18.4	statues/figures 16.8	religious 12.8	detailed 12.5	aged 5.9
The staff or keepers are...	friendly 33.0	unidentifiable 15.1	reserved 14.1	working 14.1	relaxing 9.2
The climate is...	hot 61.5	humid 13.2	warm 9.2	breeze 2.9	cool 2.3
The feeling I get at this location is...	religious 19.7	peaceful 18.9	fascinating 15.1	friendly 7.6	respect 6.7
The smell is...	religious 56.0	intoxicating 26.8	none 8.1	food 2.9	natural 2.9
The environment is...	organised 23.3	unorganised 23.3	natural 6.3	attractive 4.7	peaceful 4.7
The sounds are...	none/silence 29.0	musical 23.3	firecrackers 11.9	people talking 11.9	bells 7.6
The atmosphere is...	peaceful 25.0	religious 14.9	humid 13.8	mysterious 10.6	hot 4.8
The activities are...	religious 50.8	looking around 19.9	taking photos 7.0	meditative 6.3	making a wish 4.0
The religion is...	Taoist 31.3	Chinese 29.9	Buddhist 9.5	spiritual 5.0	traditional 5.0
The culture is...	Chinese 17.9	inviting 11.5	traditional 10.3	mysterious 9.6	spiritual 8.7
The experience is...	unique 18.9	pleasant 17.0	fascinating 13.7	worthwhile 9.4	religious 9.2

Note. sur. = surrounded.

Table 9.4.23 Top 6 overall themes of Chinese temples in Phuket using projective questions

Themes	Frequency	%
Religious	8	13.6
Colourful	5	8.5
Attractive	4	6.8
Mysterious	4	6.8
Peaceful	3	5.1
Traditional	3	5.1
Unique	3	5.1

Figure 9.4.1 The overall image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using Echtner and Ritchie (2003) Components of Destination Image Model.

Table 9.4.23 Comparison of Asian and European image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using projective questions

Question	Overall	Asian	European
	1st Theme	1st Theme (%)	1st Theme (%)
1. The Chinese temple or shrine is...	religious	religious 36.2	religious 36.5
2. The layout of the temple is...	confined	confined 27.0	confined 28.6
3. The space is...	confined	confined 46.9	confined 46.8
4. The area around the temple is...	busy	busy 31.7	busy 24.3
5. The view from the outside is...	the gate	the gate 20.5	the gate 14.0
6. The view from the inside is...	religious	religious 12.2	religious 16.8
7. The architecture is...	traditional	traditional 48.8	traditional 21.5
8. The decorations are...	colourful	of statues 20.9	colourful 18.7
9. The staff or keepers are...	friendly	friendly 38.7	friendly 27.2
10. The climate is...	hot	hot 76.7	hot 51.3
11. The feeling I get at this location is...	religious	religious 21.1	peaceful 21.8
12. The smell is...	religious	religious 50.0	religious 62.2
13. The environment is...	organised	unorganised 37.0	organised 26.1
14. The sounds are...	none/silence	musical 24.7	none/silence 42.0
15. The atmosphere is...	peaceful	humid 24.2	peaceful 32.1
16. The activities are...	religious	religious 63.0	religious 45.9
17. The religion is...	Taoist	Taoist 37.7	Chinese 31.8
18. The culture is...	Chinese	Chinese 34.1	traditional 14.6
19. The experience is...	unique	pleasant 20.6	unique 18.8

Figure 9.4.2 The Asian respondents image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using Echtner and Ritchie (2003) Components of Destination Image Model.

<p>COMMON</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious smell • Musical sounds • Hot climate • Statue decorations 	<p>FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious smell • Musical sounds 	<p>FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional architecture • Confined space 	
<p>FUNCTIONAL ATTRIBUTES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hot climate • Statue decorations 	<p>The diagram illustrates the Destination Image Model with a central point. Four arrows radiate from this point to four quadrants: 'FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS' at the top, 'PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS' at the bottom, 'COMMON ATTRIBUTES' on the left, and 'HOLISTIC (Imagery) UNIQUE' on the right.</p>		<p>FUNCTIONAL HOLISTIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confined layout • Religious view inside • Gated view outside • Religious activities
<p>PSYCHOLOGICAL ATTRIBUTES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unorganised environment • Busy area 	<p>PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Friendly staff • Humid atmosphere 	<p>PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious Shrine • Taoist religion • Chinese culture 	<p>PSYCHOLOGICAL HOLISTIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious feeling • Pleasant experience
		<p>UNIQUE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taoist religion • Chinese culture • Religious feeling • Pleasant Experience 	

Figure 9.4.3 The European respondents image of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket using Echtner and Ritchie (2003) Components of Destination Image Model.

<p>COMMON</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious smell • Silence • Hot climate • Colourful decorations 	<p>FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious smell • Silence 	<p>FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional architecture • Confined space 	
<p>FUNCTIONAL ATTRIBUTES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hot climate • Colourful decorations 			<p>FUNCTIONAL HOLISTIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confined layout • Religious view inside • Gated view outside • Religious activities
<p>PSYCHOLOGICAL ATTRIBUTES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organised environment • Busy area 			<p>PSYCHOLOGICAL HOLISTIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peaceful feeling • Unique experience
<p>PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Friendly staff • Peaceful atmosphere 		<p>PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious Shrine • Chinese religion • Traditional culture 	<p>UNIQUE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chinese religion • Traditional culture • Peaceful feeling • Unique Experience

Table 9.4.24 The drawn categories and elements of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket

No.	Drawing Category	Drawing Element/Code
1	Burnt offering (911)	incense stick (602), firecracker (142), candle with a flame (54), oil lamp (24), candle holder with a candle and flame (23), incense stick wrapped (22), candle (18), candle holder (8), incense stick smoking (7), incense sticks in a box (4), oil bottle (4), ghost money (2), oil bottle with calligraphy (1)
2	Statue/Figure/God (491)	unknown statue/figure (132), genderless god (103), genderless god sitting (75), lion (52), genderless god standing (44), dragon (29), male god standing (21), female goddess standing (16), animal god (8), male god sitting (4), female goddess sitting (2), male god (2), female goddess (1), female goddess standing on a platform (1), genderless god standing on a platform (1)
3	Lantern (346)	lantern hanging (259), lantern (50), lantern with calligraphy (28), lantern hanging with calligraphy (9)
4	Calligraphy (342)	calligraphy impression (147), Chinese calligraphy (111), English calligraphy (83), Thai calligraphy (1)
5	Offering (295)	offerings - unknown objects (51), tea cups (49), fruit – apple on a plate (32), offerings on a plate (31), tea cups in a tray (23), fruit – pineapple on a plate (22), fruit – pineapple (21), fruit – orange (19), fruit – apple (14), fruit – orange on a plate (10), fruit – banana (8), balls in a small shrine (4), plate (3), fruit – dragon fruit on a plate (2), fruit – watermelon (2), fruit – banana on a plate (1), fruit – pear on a plate (1), garland (1), offering in a bottle (1)
6	Column (241)	column/pillar (163), column/pillar with a dragon (63), column/pillar with calligraphy (13), column/pillar with a dragon and calligraphy (2),
7	Ding/Pot/Cauldron (230)	ding/pot/cauldron with legs or base and incense and smoke (49), ding/pot/cauldron with incense and smoke (43), ding/pot/cauldron with incense (42), ding/pot/cauldron on the table with incense (29), ding/pot/cauldron on the table with incense and smoke (26), ding/pot/cauldron (20), ding/pot/cauldron with legs or base and incense (16), ding/pot/cauldron with legs or base and smoke but no incense (1), ding/pot/cauldron on the alter with incense (1), ding/pot/cauldron on the alter with incense and smoke (1), ding/pot/cauldron with incense and smoke with calligraphy (1), ding/pot/cauldron with incense and calligraphy (1)
8	Flag (197)	flag (109), flag with calligraphy (72), flag stand with flags (8), flag stand with flags and calligraphy (7), flag post (1)
9	Architecture (188)	main building (121), other buildings (24), smaller shrine (21), side building (19), pagoda (3)

10	Altar (166)	solid alter (98), table altar (68)
11	Doorway/Archway (158)	doorway/archway (86), door (53), door handle (19)
12	Roof (137)	roof (107), roof with dragons and objects (16), roof with dragons (10), roof with objects (4)
13	Nature (133)	bush/hedge (37), tree (33), clouds (18), grass (17), potted plants (11), sky (7), flowers (6), sun (4)
14	Artwork (107)	decorations (26), curtains/drapes (18), wall carving (14), vase (12), flower pattern (9), Sanskrit swastika (5), vase with flower (5), cultural story on the wall (4), door guardian (4), sacred spiral (4), carpet (2), framed picture (1), framed picture with calligraphy (1), lotus flower (1), yin yang (1)
15	Placard/Plate/Sign (103)	placard/plate/sign with calligraphy (70), placard/plate/sign (32), notice board (2)
16	Religious artefact (58)	artefacts (35), palanquin (10), wooden pole with gold leaf (6), boat (2), book - religious (2), blind (1), book - religious with calligraphy (1), gold leaf (1)
17	Stairs/Steps/Ramp (81)	stairs/steps (62), ramp (11), stairs/steps with railings (8)
18	Weapon (74)	weapon (43), weapons in a stand (31)
19	Gate (69)	outside gate (44), outside gate with dragons (24), outside gate with calligraphy (1)
20	Public Infrastructure (67)	curb (28), pavement (20), road/street with lines (10), road/street (5), electric post with wires (2), pool (1), road barrier (1)
21	Outside wall (66)	outside wall (66)
22	Divination (58)	Moon Blocks / Jiaobei Blocks (26), yarrow sticks in a box (26), cabinet with fortune telling papers (4), yarrow sticks in a box with calligraphy (2)
23	Musical instrument (55)	drum (20), bell hanging (15), bell on a stand (8), bell (7), gong (4), musical notes (1)
24	Ornament (52)	table (22), chair/seat (15), tent (8), chair/seat with calligraphy (3), calendar (1), calendar with calligraphy (1), wall clock (1)
25	Window (54)	window (54)
26	Banner (44)	ceiling banner (21), ceiling banner with calligraphy (12), wall banner with calligraphy (6), wall banner (5)
27	Donation safe/box (44)	donation safe/box (35), donation safe/box with calligraphy (9)
28	General public (42)	person (17), people (10), people praying (9), people's shoes (6)
29	Chimney (41)	chimney (39), chimney with calligraphy (2)
30	Pathway (39)	pathway (39)

31	Courtyard (28)	courtyard (19), floor tiles/stones (9)
32	Vehicles (25)	car (15), motorbike (10)
33	Prayer kneeler rest (23)	prayer kneeler rests (23)
34	Animal (13)	live bird (9), live cat (2), live dog (2)
35	Firecracker room (13)	firecracker cage (8), firecracker room (5)
36	Shop (3)	shop (2), shop counter (1)
37	Staff (2)	staff (2)

Table 9.4.25 The drawn descriptive themes of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket

Themes	Frequency	%
Drawn Descriptions		
Unique	306	10.16
Dimensions	288	9.56
Fascinating	247	8.20
Attractive	230	7.63
Religious	203	6.74
Colourful	200	6.64
Decorative	174	5.77
Traditional	163	5.41
Mysterious	118	3.92
Aged	101	3.35
Respect	101	3.35
Fame	93	3.09
Quantity	90	2.99
Spiritual	83	2.75
Unusual	83	2.75
Peaceful	68	2.26
Natural	44	1.46
Smoky	37	1.23
Location	36	1.19
Offerings	35	1.16
Ascending	34	1.13
Ordinary	33	1.10
Smell	33	1.10
Organised	29	0.96
Unease	25	0.83
Education	23	0.76
Hidden	21	0.70
Noisy	18	0.60
Busy	17	0.56
Inviting	16	0.53
Material	10	0.33
Joy	8	0.27
Confusing	7	0.23

Elevated	7	0.23
Energised	6	0.20
Hot	6	0.20
Unorganised	6	0.20
Commercial	5	0.17
Warm	4	0.13
New	2	0.07
Descending	1	0.03
Food	1	0.03
Memorable	1	0.03
Total	3013	100.0

Table 9.4.26 The overall results of the drawn elements and themes by respondents

No. Drawn Element	1st Theme	2nd Theme	3rd Theme	4th Theme	5th Theme
1. Altar	unique 9.7	attractive 9.1	colourful 8.6	religious 8.0	dimensions 7.4
2. Animal	-	-	-	-	-
3. Architecture	fascinating 12.3	dimensions 11.8	unique 10.5	attractive 8.2	decorative 6.4
4. Artwork	colourful 10.7	attractive 9.5	unique 9.5	dimensions 8.3	mysterious 7.1
5. Banner	fascinating 12.8	unique 10.3	attractive 7.7	colourful 7.7	religious 7.7
6. Burnt Offering	attractive 14.6	dimensions 11.7	unique 11.7	fascinating 8.0	traditional 6.6
7. Calligraphy	unique 9.0	decorative 8.5	dimensions 8.5	attractive 7.4	fascinating 7.4
8. Chimney	fascinating 12.7	unique 11.1	attractive 7.9	fame 7.9	dimensions 7.9
9. Column	unique 10.7	colourful 9.7	decorative 7.8	fascinating 7.8	religious 7.8
10. Courtyard	religious 14.3	unique 13.7	fame 9.5	fascinating 9.5	traditional 9.5
11. Ding/Pot/Cauldron	unique 9.4	dimensions 9.4	religious 8.2	colourful 6.6	traditional 6.6
12. Divination	unique 17.1	dimensions 14.3	decorative 8.6	religious 8.6	respect 8.6
13. Donation Safe/Box	unique 11.6	fascinating 9.3	attractive 7.0	fame 7.0	dimensions 7.0
14. Doorway/Archway	dimensions 15.5	colourful 11.2	religious 11.2	attractive 10.3	fascinating 10.3
15. Firecracker Room	unique 16.7	colourful 11.1	noisy 11.1	aged 5.6	ascending 5.6
16. Flag	colourful 13.2	attractive 11.8	fascinating 9.2	unique 7.9	decorative 6.6
17. Gate	dimensions 14.6	unique 8.3	attractive 7.3	traditional 7.3	fascinating 6.3
18. General Public	attractive 17.6	friendly 11.8	unease 11.8	aged 5.9	colourful 5.9
19. Prayer Kneeler Rest	dimensions 30.8	unique 23.1	fascinating 15.4	hidden 7.7	mysterious 7.7
20. Lantern	unique 12.7	religious 11.1	colourful 10.3	dimensions 7.1	decorative 5.6
21. Musical Instruments	aged 9.8	fascinating 9.8	colourful 7.8	traditional 7.8	unique 7.8
22. Nature	unique 13.6	dimensions 12.3	attractive 8.6	fascinating 8.6	decorative 6.2
23. Offerings	religious 11.0	unique 11.0	attractive 8.5	dimensions 7.6	colourful 6.8
24. Ornaments	religious 11.8	fascinating 9.8	aged 7.8	dimensions 7.8	colourful 5.9
25. Outside Wall	unique 12.5	attractive 10.4	dimensions 10.4	fascinating 8.3	decorative 6.3
26. Pathway	dimensions 15.2	unusual 12.1	fascinating 9.1	unique 9.1	aged 6.1
27. Placard/Plate/Sign	unique 11.3	dimensions 10.4	attractive 9.6	fascinating 8.7	traditional 8.7
28. Public Infrastructure	ordinary 14.7	dimensions 10.3	colourful 7.4	decorative 7.4	fascinating 7.4
29. Religious Artefact	quantity 9.5	colourful 9.5	mysterious 7.1	religious 7.1	traditional 7.1
30. Roof	unique 11.4	traditional 8.5	fascinating 7.4	dimensions 7.4	attractive 6.8
31. Shop	-	-	-	-	-
32. Staff	-	-	-	-	-
33. Stairs/Steps/Ramp	dimensions 12.0	fascinating 9.6	unique 9.6	attractive 7.2	decorative 6.0
34. Statues/Figures/Gods	unique 11.7	fascinating 10.0	attractive 9.6	decorative 7.4	dimensions 7.4

35. Vehicles	quantity 23.8	ordinary 19.0	noisy 4.3	aged 9.5	new 9.5
36. Weapon	dimensions 17.5	fascinating 15.0	respect 10.0	unique 10.0	unusual 10.0
37. Window	fascinating 16.7	colourful 10.0	decorative 10.0	unique 10.0	attractive 6.7

Note: (-) = insufficient data.

Table 9.4.27 The results of the drawn elements and themes by Asian and European respondents

No. Drawn Element	Overall 1st Theme	Asian 1st Theme	European 1st Theme
1. Altar	unique 9.7	dimensions 11.3	colourful 12.7
2. Animal	-	-	-
3. Architecture	fascinating 12.3	unique 14.3	dimensions 11.5
4. Artwork	colourful 10.7	attractive 12.0	colourful 12.5
5. Banner	fascinating 12.8	unique 25.0	attractive 9.5
6. Burnt Offering	attractive 14.6	attractive 12.7	attractive 16.1
7. Calligraphy	unique 9.0	attractive 9.6	traditional 13.6
8. Chimney	fascinating 12.7	fascinating 25.0	unique 12.0
9. Column	unique 10.7	decorative 14.7	colourful 16.3
10. Courtyard	religious 14.3	-	-
11. Ding/Pot/Cauldron	unique 9.4	unique 11.1	attractive 12.8
12. Divination	unique 17.1	unique 20.8	-
13. Donation Safe/Box	unique 11.6	fascinating 15.0	unique 18.8
14. Doorway/Archway	dimensions 15.5	dimensions 19.6	dimensions 14.0
15. Firecracker Room	unique 16.7	noisy 25.0	unique 25.0
16. Flag	colourful 13.2	attractive 11.5	colourful 18.2
17. Gate	dimensions 14.6	dimensions 20.0	attractive 17.9
18. General Public	attractive 17.6	-	attractive 22.2
19. Prayer Kneeler Rest	dimensions 30.8	-	-
20. Lantern	unique 12.7	decorative 7.8	unique 14.8
21. Musical Instruments	aged 9.8	traditional 15.4	aged 14.3
22. Nature	unique 13.6	colourful 14.3	dimensions 23.3
23. Offerings	religious 11.0	religious 21.1	unique 15.4
24. Ornaments	religious 11.8	aged 12.5	religious 16.7
25. Outside Wall	unique 12.5	dimensions 12.5	unique 18.2
26. Pathway	dimensions 15.2	-	dimensions 21.4
27. Placard/Plate/Sign	unique 11.3	unique 22.9	dimensions 15.7
28. Public Infrastructure	ordinary 14.7	ordinary 12.0	fascinating 16.0
29. Religious Artefact	quantity 9.5	offering 16.7	quantity 13.6

30. Roof	unique 11.4	unique 17.0	unique 11.7
31. Shop	-	-	-
32. Staff	-	-	-
33. Stairs/Steps/Ramp	dimensions 12.0	fame 13.0	dimensions 17.1
34. Statues/Figures/Gods	unique 11.7	unique 14.8	fascinating 10.3
35. Vehicles	quantity 23.8	-	noisy 25.0
36. Weapon	dimensions 17.5	respect 18.2	fascinating 19.0
37. Window	fascinating 16.7	-	colourful 13.6

Note: (-) = insufficient data.

Table 9.4.28 The results of drawing numbers, completion and dimensions

Composition	Frequency	%
Total of items	4996	100
Completion		
whole	4464	89.4
part	496	9.9
mixture	36	0.7
Total	4996	100
Dimensions		
2D	3607	72.2
3D	1308	26.2
mixture	81	1.6
Total	4996	100

Table 9.4.29 The results of drawing size, proportion and impression

Composition	Frequency	%
Size		
medium	2207	44.2
small	1878	37.6
large	753	15.1
mixture	158	3.2
Total	4996	100
Proportionate		
yes	3918	78.4
no	1078	21.6
Total	4996	100
Impression		
abstract	3775	75.6
realistic	1221	24.4
Total	4996	100

Table 9.4.30 The results of cropped images and use of calligraphic impressions

Composition	Frequency	%
Crop		
no	4821	96.5
yes	175	3.5
Total	4996	100
Calligraphy		
no	4394	88.0
yes	602	12.0
Total	4996	100

View - viewer to object

Fig. 9.4.4 Results of object's drawn a with non-directional perspective

Fig. 9.4.5 Results of object's drawn a with directional perspective

Location on the page

Figure 9.4.6 Drawn results of the nine grid locations

3.6%	7.2%	4.5%
5.1%	16.4%	3.4%
3.2%	4.7%	2.7%

Figure 9.4.7 Drawn results of the three horizontal locations

10.9%
17.2%
6.5%

Figure 9.4.8 Drawn results of the three vertical locations

2.0%	3.6%	0.7%
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The majority of the page 0.8% and mixture 7.5%.

Table 9.4.31 The results of pencil usage in chinese temple/shrine drawings

Pencil Usage	Frequency	%
Pencil Used		
yes	4610	93.0
no	386	7.0
Total	4996	100
Pencil Pressure		
mixture	1850	37.0
hard	1205	24.2
normal	1166	23.3
none	390	7.8
soft	385	7.7
Total	4996	100
Pencil Line Quality		
mixture	1605	32.1
medium	1450	29.0
thin	1069	21.4
thick	487	9.8
none	385	7.7
Total	4996	100
Pencil Marks		
liner	3809	76.2
mixture	773	15.6
none	385	7.7
pattern	19	0.3
texture	10	0.2
Total	4996	100
Pencil Tone		
none	4502	90.1
shaded	320	6.4
solid	90	1.8
mixture	84	1.7
Total	4996	100

Pencil Shadow		
no	4959	99.2
yes	37	0.8
Total	4996	100

Table 9.4.32 The results of colour pencil usage in Chinese temple/shrine drawings

Colour Pencil Usage	Frequency	%
Colour Pencils Used		
yes	2658	53.2
no	2338	46.8
Total	4996	100
Colour Pressure		
none	2338	46.8
mixture	1457	29.2
hard	567	11.3
normal	460	9.2
soft	174	3.5
Total	4996	100
Colour Line Quality		
none	2338	46.8
mixture	968	19.4
thick	902	18.1
medium	696	13.9
thin	92	1.8
Total	4996	100
Colour Marks		
none	2338	46.8
liner	1558	31.2
mixture	780	15.6
solid	286	5.7
dots	24	0.4
pattern	6	0.2
texture	4	0.1
Total	4996	100

Colour Tone		
none	2726	54.5
shaded	851	17.1
mixture	840	16.8
solid	552	11.0
gradation	27	0.6
Total	4996	100

Colour Shadow		
no	4978	99.6
yes	18	0.4
Total	4996	100

Table 9.4.33 The results of colours used in Chinese temple/shrine drawings

Colour Used in Drawings	Frequency	%
Colours		
white	1038	33.7
red	477	15.5
yellow	349	11.3
brown	301	9.8
black	294	9.6
green	166	5.4
orange	149	4.8
flesh	120	3.9
blue	107	3.5
pink	49	1.6
purple	26	0.9
Total	3076	100

Figure 9.4.9a The image results for the altar at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Altar										
COMPOSITION										
View Frequency (3.3%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (44.4%)	Red (13.5%)	Brown (12.7%)	Black (8.1%)	Orange (5.8%)	Yellow (5.1%)	Green (3.5%)	Purple (2.7%)	Pink (2.0%)	Flesh (2.0%)	Blue (0.2%)
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (9.7%)	2 nd Theme Attractive (9.1%)	3 rd Theme Colourful (8.6%)	4 th Theme Dimensions (8.0%)	5 th Theme Religious (8.0%)						

Figure 9.4.9b Drawn examples of the altar image at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing

Drawn Examples (All Respondents)

Altar

Examples

JTS581006001A

SPH581101023A

PDJ581107017B

Figure 9.4.10a The image results for calligraphy at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Calligraphy										
COMPOSITION										
View NA										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
Black (33.3%)	Red (26.2%)	Yellow (19.0%)	Purple (7.1%)	White (7.1%)	Pink (4.8%)	Brown (2.4%)				
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (9.0%)	2 nd Theme Decorative (8.5%)	3 rd Theme Dimensions (8.5%)	4 th Theme Attractive (7.4%)	5 th Theme Fascinating (7.4%)						

Figure 9.4.10b Drawn examples of calligraphy at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

<p>Drawn Examples (All Respondents)</p> <p>Calligraphy</p>		<p>Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing</p>
<p>Examples</p>		
<p>A hand-drawn sketch of a colorful shrine entrance. It features a large gate with a green roof and red pillars. There are flags, a person on a scooter, and a bench in the foreground. The gate has Chinese characters on it.</p>		
<p>KTU581020006A</p>	<p>HNK581017009B</p>	<p>SPH581016004A</p>

Figure 9.4.11a The image results for the columns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Column										
COMPOSITION										
View Association (9.8%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (34.1%)	Red (20.2%)	Yellow (11.6%)	Brown (9.3%)	Green (7.0%)	Black (7.0%)	Orange (3.1%)	Flesh (3.1%)	Pink (2.4%)	Blue (1.5%)	Purple (0.8%)
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (10.7%)	2 nd Theme Colourful (9.7%)	3 rd Theme Fascinating (8.7%)	4 th Theme Decorative (7.8%)	5 th Theme Religious (7.8%)						

Figure 9.4.11b Drawn examples of columns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

<p>Drawn Examples (All Respondents)</p> <p>Column</p>		<p>Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing</p>
<p>Examples</p>		
<p>SRN581009007B</p>	<p>HNK581010001A</p>	<p>HNK581017006A</p>

Figure 9.4.12a The image results for the ding/pot/cauldron at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Ding/Pot/Cauldron										
COMPOSITION										
View Association (1.0%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (33.3%)	Brown (18.5%)	Black (14.5%)	Yellow (8.7%)	Red (7.6%)	Orange (6.2%)	Flesh (5.4%)	Blue (2.2%)	Green (1.4%)	Pink (1.4%)	Purple (0.7%)
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (9.4%)	2 nd Theme Dimensions (9.4%)	3 rd Theme Religious (8.2%)	4 th Theme Colourful (6.6%)	5 th Theme Traditional (6.6%)						

Figure 9.4.12b Drawn examples of the ding/pot/cauldron at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

<p>Drawn Examples (All Respondents)</p> <p>Ding/Pot/Cauldron</p>		<p>Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing</p>
<p>Examples</p>		
<p>SPH581031018B</p>	<p>HNK581017014B</p>	<p>SRN581021011B</p>

Figure 9.4.13a The image results for the objects of divination at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Divination										
COMPOSITION										
View	Size		Location			Crop		Calligraphy		
Front Above (43.8%)	Small (56.3%)		Centre (37.5%)			None		Association (7.1%)		
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (38.9%)	Brown (19.4%)	Red (13.9%)	Yellow (8.3%)	Blue (5.6%)	Black (5.6%)	Green (2.8%)	Orange (2.8%)	Flesh (2.8%)		
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme		2 nd Theme			3 rd Theme		4 th Theme		5 th Theme	
Unique (17.1%)		Dimensions (14.3%)			Decorative (8.6%)		Religious (8.6%)		Respect (8.6%)	

Figure 9.4.13b Drawn examples of objects of divination at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

<p>Drawn Examples (All Respondents)</p> <p>Divination</p>		<p>Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing</p>
<p>Examples</p>		
<p>SPH581016015B</p>	<p>SPH581016007B</p>	<p>PDJ581019007B</p>

Figure 9.4.14a The image results for the donation safe/box at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Donation Safe/Box										
COMPOSITION										
View Association (22.5%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (44.5%)	Brown (13.3%)	Black (11.1%)	Red (8.9%)	Blue (6.7%)	Green (4.5%)	Flesh (4.5%)	Yellow (2.2%)	Orange (2.2%)	Purple (2.2%)	
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (11.6%)	2 nd Theme Fascinating (9.3%)	3 rd Theme Attractive (7.0%)	4 th Theme Fame (7.0%)	5 th Theme Dimensions (7.0%)						

Figure 9.4.14b Drawn examples of donation safe/box at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing

Drawn Examples (All Respondents)

Donation Safe/Box

Examples

KTU581020004B

PDJ581103009B

SPH581031019B

Figure 9.4.15a The image results for the firecracker room at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Firecracker Room										
COMPOSITION										
View Frequency (16.7%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (27.3%)	Red (18.2%)	Black (18.2%)	Yellow (13.6%)	Green (9.1%)	Flesh (9.1%)	Blue (4.5%)				
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (16.7%)	2 nd Theme Colourful (11.1%)	3 rd Theme Noisy (11.1%)	4 th Theme Aged (5.6%)	5 th Theme Ascending (5.6%)						

Figure 9.4.15b Drawn examples of the firecracker room at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing

Drawn Examples (All Respondents)

Firecracker Room

Examples

SRN581007001A

SRN581022013B

PDJ581003001A

Figure 9.4.16a The image results for the lanterns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Lantern										
COMPOSITION										
View Association (15.7%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
Red (32.5%)	White (31.1%)	Yellow (16.1%)	Orange (7.1%)	Black (5.7%)	Pink (2.6%)	Brown (2.3%)	Purple (1.3%)	Flesh (1.1%)		
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (12.7%)	2 nd Theme Religious (11.1%)	3 rd Theme Colourful (10.3%)	4 th Theme Dimensions (7.1%)	5 th Theme Decorative (5.6%)						

Figure 9.4.16b Drawn examples of lanterns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

<p>Drawn Examples (All Respondents)</p> <p>Lantern</p>		<p>Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing</p>
<p>Examples</p>		
<p>BNW581013005B</p>	<p>KTU581008001B</p>	<p>BNW581023019A</p>

Figure 9.4.17a The image results for nature around the Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Nature										
COMPOSITION										
View	Size		Location			Crop		Calligraphy		
Front (90.8%)	Medium (60.0%)		Across the Top (24.6%)			Frequency (4.9%)		None		
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
Green (30.9%)	White (30.4%)	Brown (15.3%)	Blue (12.2%)	Yellow (3.0%)	Red (2.1%)	Orange (2.1%)	Pink (2.1%)	Black (2.0%)		
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme		2 nd Theme		3 rd Theme			4 th Theme		5 th Theme	
Unique (13.6%)		Dimensions (12.3%)		Attractive (8.6%)			Fascinating (8.6%)		Decorative (6.2%)	

Figure 9.4.17b Drawn examples of nature around the Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawn Examples (All Respondents)		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Nature		
Examples		
JTS581006002A	SPH581005002A	SPH581101024A

Figure 9.4.18a The image results for the outside wall at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Outside Wall										
COMPOSITION										
View Frequency (16.2%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
 White (30.4%)	 Pink (2.2%)									
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1st Theme Unique (12.5%)	2nd Theme Attractive (10.4%)	3rd Theme Dimensions (10.4%)	4th Theme Fascinating (8.3%)	5th Theme Decorative (6.3%)						

Figure 9.4.18a Drawn examples of the outside wall at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing

Drawn Examples (All Respondents)

Outside Wall

Examples

HNK581024020A

PDJ581107018A

SPH581016009A

Figure 9.4.19a The image results for the placards/plates/signs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Placard/Plate/Sign										
COMPOSITION										
View Association (67.4%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (31.8%)	Red (22.7%)	Yellow (11.8%)	Black (10.0%)	Orange (9.1%)	Brown (9.1%)	Flesh (1.8%)	Green (0.9%)	Blue (0.9%)	Purple (0.9%)	Pink (0.9%)
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (11.3%)	2 nd Theme Dimensions (10.4%)	3 rd Theme Attractive (9.6%)	4 th Theme Fascinating (8.7%)	5 th Theme Traditional (8.7%)						

Figure 9.4.19b Drawn examples of placards/plates/signs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawn Examples (All Respondents) Placard/Plate/Sign		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Examples		
<p>A hand-drawn sketch of a temple facade. The structure features a sign above the entrance and two red lanterns hanging on either side. The drawing uses red and orange colors on a white background.</p>		
<p>HNK581017008A</p>	<p>BNW581018009A</p>	<p>PDJ581003002A</p>

Figure 9.4.20a The image results for the roof at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Roof										
COMPOSITION										
View Frequency (21.3%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (30.0%)	Red (22.1%)	Green (13.8%)	Yellow (12.0%)	Orange (8.3%)	Brown (6.0%)	Flesh (3.2%)	Black (2.3%)	Blue (0.9%)	Pink (0.9%)	Purple (0.4%)
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (11.4%)	2 nd Theme Traditional (8.5%)	3 rd Theme Fascinating (7.4%)	4 th Theme Dimensions (7.4%)	5 th Theme Attractive (6.8%)						

Figure 9.4.20b Drawn examples of the roof at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawn Examples (All Respondents)		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Roof		
Examples		
SRN581025017B	SPH581016008A	SRN581021008A

Figure 9.4.21a The image results for the statues/figures/gods at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (All Respondents)										
Statues/Figures/Gods										
COMPOSITION										
View Frequency (3.0%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (32.7%)	Yellow (13.8%)	Black (10.7%)	Red (8.3%)	Brown (8.3%)	Green (7.3%)	Flesh (7.0%)	Orange (4.6%)	Blue (4.3%)	Pink (2.4%)	Purple (0.6%)
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (11.7%)	2 nd Theme Fascinating (10.0%)	3 rd Theme Attractive (9.6%)	4 th Theme Decorative (7.4%)	5 th Theme Dimensions (7.4%)						

Figure 9.4.21b Drawn examples of statues/figures/gods at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by overall respondents

Drawn Examples (All Respondents) Statues/Figures/Gods		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Examples		
JTS581015017B	HNK581010002B	PDJ581003004B

Figure 9.4.22a The image results for the Chinese temples and shrines architecture in Phuket by Asian respondents

Figure 9.4.22b Drawn examples of chinese temples/shrines architecture in Phuket by Asian respondents

<p>Drawn Examples (Asian Respondents)</p> <p>Architecture</p>		<p>Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing</p>
<p>Examples</p>		
<p>HNK581017013A</p>	<p>JTS581014008A</p>	<p>JTS581014010A</p>

Figure 9.4.23a The image results for the banners at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (Asian Respondents)										
Banner										
COMPOSITION										
View Type (50.0%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (31.9%)	Red (21.3%)	Yellow (21.3%)	Orange (21.3%)	Green (10.6%)	Blue (10.6%)	Purple (10.6%)	Brown (10.6%)	Black (10.6%)		
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (25.0%)	2 nd Theme Fascinating (25.0%)	3 rd Theme (Aged 12.5%)	4 th Theme Attractive (12.5%)	5 th Theme Colourful (12.5%)						

Figure 9.4.23b Drawn examples of banners at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawn Examples (Asian Respondents)		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Banner		
Examples		
KTU581008003A	KTU581020008A	PDJ581106013A

Figure 9.4.24a The image results for the ding/pot/cauldron at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (Asian Respondents)										
Ding/Pot/Cauldron										
COMPOSITION										
View Type (2.2%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (30.8%)	Brown (18.3%)	Black (14.4%)	Yellow (8.6%)	Red (7.7%)	Flesh (7.7%)	Orange (6.7%)	Blue (1.9%)	Pink (1.9%)	Green (1.9%)	
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (11.1%)	2 nd Theme Dimensions (11.1%)	3 rd Theme Traditional (9.1%)	4 th Theme Religious (7.1%)	5 th Theme Fascinating (6.1%)						

Figure 9.4.24b Drawn examples of ding/pot/cauldron at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawn Examples (Asian Respondents) Ding/Pot/Cauldron		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Examples		
<p>A drawing of a red shrine with a red roof. Two people are sitting on a red platform inside the shrine. A cauldron is on the ground in front of the shrine.</p>		
BNW581018014B	JTS581006003B	PDJ581003004A

Figure 9.4.25a The image results for the objects of divination at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (Asian Respondents)										
Divination										
COMPOSITION										
View Type (10.0%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (37.5%)	Brown (25.0%)	Red (12.5%)	Yellow (8.3%)	Green (4.2%)	Blue (4.2%)	Orange (4.2%)	Black (4.2%)			
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (20.8%)	2 nd Theme Dimensions (12.5%)	3 rd Theme Religious (12.5%)	4 th Theme Decorative (8.3%)	5 th Theme Mysterious (8.3%)						

Figure 9.4.25b Drawn examples of objects of divination at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawn Examples (Asian Respondents)		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Divination		
Examples		
BNW581023021B	HNK581017015A	SPH581016016B

Figure 9.4.26a The image results for the placards/plates/signs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (Asian Respondents)										
Placard/Plate/Sign										
COMPOSITION										
View	Size	Location	Crop	Calligraphy						
Front (95.0%)	Medium (55.0%)	Centre (40.0%)	None	Type (82.1%)						
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (28.8%)	Red (25.0%)	Black (15.4%)	Yellow (9.6%)	Brown (9.6%)	Orange (7.7%)	Blue (1.9%)	Flesh (1.9%)			
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (22.9%)	2 nd Theme Attractive (10.4%)	3 rd Theme Colourful (8.3%)	4 th Theme Fascinating (8.3%)	5 th Theme Religious (8.3%)						

Figure 9.4.26b Drawn examples of placards/plates/signs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawn Examples (Asian Respondents) Placard/Plate/Sign		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Examples		
<p>SRN581009006A</p>	<p>KTU581008002B</p>	<p>JTS581014006A</p>

Figure 9.4.27a The image results for the roof at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (Asian Respondents)										
Roof										
COMPOSITION										
View Cropped (26.5%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (35.3%)	Red (19.6%)	Yellow (11.8%)	Brown (9.8%)	Green (5.9%)	Flesh (5.9%)	Blue (3.9%)	Orange (3.9%)	Black (3.9%)		
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (17.0%)	2 nd Theme Dimensions (10.6%)	3 rd Theme Colourful (8.5%)	4 th Theme Traditional (8.5%)	5 th Theme Aged (6.4%)						

Figure 9.4.27b Drawn examples of roofs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawn Examples (Asian Respondents)		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Roof		
Examples		
BNW581012002A	HNK581024019A	SRN581025022A

Figure 9.4.28a The image results for the statues/figures/gods at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (Asian Respondents)										
Statues/Figures/Gods										
COMPOSITION										
View Cropped (1.9%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (27.2%)	Black (13.6%)	Red (9.7%)	Yellow (9.7%)	Brown (9.7%)	Flesh (8.8%)	Green (7.8%)	Blue (4.9%)	Orange (3.9%)	Pink (3.9%)	Purple (1.0%)
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (14.8%)	2 nd Theme Attractive (11.5%)	3 rd Theme Decorative (11.5%)	4 th Theme Dimensions (9.8%)	5 th Theme Fascinating (8.2%)						

Figure 9.4.28b Drawn Examples of Statues/Figures/Gods at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by Asian respondents

Drawn Examples (Asian Respondents) Statues/Figures/Gods		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Examples		
BNW581012004B	BNW581018007B	JTS581014008B

Figure 9.4.29a The image results for the chimney at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (European Respondents)										
Chimney										
COMPOSITION										
View Type (13.3%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (28.6%)	Red (25.0%)	Yellow (21.4%)	Green (7.1%)	Orange (7.1%)	Black (7.1%)	Flesh (3.6%)				
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (12.0%)	2 nd Theme Aged (8.0%)	3 rd Theme Fame (8.0%)	4 th Theme Fascinating (8.0%)	5 th Theme Respect (8.0%)						

Figure 9.4.29b Drawn examples of chimneys at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawn Examples (European Respondents) Chimney		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Examples		
BNW581013005A	SRN581025019A	BNW581012003A

Figure 9.4.30a The image results for the donation safe/box at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (European Respondents)										
Donation Safe/Box										
COMPOSITION										
View Type (25.0%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (38.1%)	Black (19.1%)	Red (9.5%)	Blue (9.5%)	Brown (9.5%)	Green (4.8%)	Yellow (4.8%)	Purple (4.8%)			
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (18.8%)	2 nd Theme Attractive (12.5%)	3 rd Theme Decorative (12.5%)	4 th Theme Traditional (12.5%)	5 th Theme Commercial (6.3%)						

Figure 9.4.30b. Drawn examples of donation safe/box at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawn Examples (European Respondents) Donation Safe/Box		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Examples		
<p>HNK581017007B</p>	<p>KTU581020014B</p>	<p>SPH581016013B</p>

Figure 9.4.31a The image results for the firecracker room at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (European Respondents)										
Firecracker Room										
COMPOSITION										
View Cropped (16.7%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (30.0%)	Red (20.0%)	Green (20.0%)	Yellow (10.0%)	Flesh (10.0%)	Black (10.0%)					
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (25.0%)	2 nd Theme Aged (12.5%)	3 rd Theme Ascending (12.5%)	4 th Theme Confusing (12.5%)	5 th Theme Dimensions (12.5%)						

Figure 9.4.31b Drawn examples of the firecracker room at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawn Examples (European Respondents)		Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing
Firecracker Room		
Examples		
<p>A hand-drawn sketch of a firecracker room. It features a table with a chair and a small shrine. To the right, there is a lion's head and a lion's body. The room is decorated with various items, including a small table with a chair and a small shrine. A banner with Chinese characters is hanging from the top. The word 'Diogo' is written near the top right, and 'col.' is written near the bottom right.</p>		
<p>SRN581025021A</p>	<p>SRN581007001A</p>	<p>SRN581025022B</p>

Figure 9.4.32a The image results for the lanterns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (European Respondents)										
Lantern										
COMPOSITION										
View Type (7.1%)										
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
Red (33.4%)	White (31.6%)	Yellow (15.0%)	Pink (5.0%)	Black (5.0%)	Orange (3.4%)	Purple (3.4%)	Brown (3.4%)			
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (14.8%)	2 nd Theme Religious (11.1%)	3 rd Theme Colourful (9.3%)	4 th Theme Dimensions (7.4%)	5 th Theme Decorative (5.6%)						

Figure 9.4.32b Drawn examples of lanterns at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

<p>Drawn Examples (European Respondents)</p> <p>Lantern</p>		<p>Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing</p>
<p>Examples</p>		
<p>A hand-drawn sketch of a shrine. A table with a circular symbol on its front is the central focus. Above the table, a row of seven pink lanterns hangs from the ceiling. On either side of the table, a figure with a circular head and radiating lines is drawn. To the right of the table, a blue rectangular object, possibly a box or a small shrine, is shown.</p>		
<p>PDJ581103010B</p>	<p>BNW581018009B</p>	<p>SPH581016014B</p>

Figure 9.4.33a The image results for the offerings at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (European Respondents)										
Offerings										
COMPOSITION										
View None	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (42.9%)	Yellow (25.0%)	Flesh (14.3%)	Green (10.7%)	Red (3.6%)	Brown (3.6%)					
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (15.4%)	2 nd Theme Colourful (7.7%)	3 rd Theme Offering (7.7%)	4 th Theme Religious (7.7%)	5 th Theme Spiritual (7.7%)						

Figure 9.4.33b Drawn examples of offerings at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

<p>Drawn Examples (European Respondents)</p> <p>Offerings</p>		<p>Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing</p>
<p>Examples</p>		
<p>HNK581024018B</p>	<p>KTU581020007B</p>	<p>JTS581015018B</p>

Figure 9.4.34a The image results for the outside wall at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (European Respondents)										
Outside Wall										
COMPOSITION										
View Cropped (10.5%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (29.1%)	Red (12.5%)	Brown (12.5%)	Yellow (8.3%)	Blue (8.3%)	Orange (8.3%)	Green (4.2%)	Purple (4.2%)	Pink (4.2%)	Flesh (4.2%)	Black (4.2%)
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (18.2%)	2 nd Theme Attractive (13.6%)	3 rd Theme Dimensions (13.6%)	4 th Theme Aged (9.1%)	5 th Theme Quantity (9.1%)						

Figure 9.4.34b Drawn examples of outside wall at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing

Drawn Examples (European Respondents)

Outside Wall

Examples

SPH581016010A

SPH581101022A

SPH581016011A

Figure 9.4.35a The image results for the roof at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing										
Image Results (European Respondents)										
Roof										
COMPOSITION										
View Cropped (16.4%)	Calligraphy None									
COLOURS										
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th	9 th	10 th	11 th
White (25.0%)	Red (21.5%)	Green (17.3%)	Yellow (9.5%)	Orange (8.6%)	Blue (7.7%)	Brown (3.5%)	Flesh (3.5%)	Black (2.6%)	Pink (0.8%)	
FEELINGS & IMPRESSIONS										
1 st Theme Unique (11.7%)	2 nd Theme Quantity (9.6%)	3 rd Theme Traditional (9.6%)	4 th Theme Dimensions (8.5%)	5 th Theme Fascinating (8.5%)						

Figure 9.4.35b Drawn examples of roofs at Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket by European respondents

<p>Drawn Examples (European Respondents)</p> <p>Roof</p>		<p>Drawing Analysis Model for Tourism Marketing</p>
<p>Examples</p>		
<p>A hand-drawn sketch of a temple entrance. A wide green roof with a red border is supported by two dark pillars. A set of yellow steps leads up to a platform where a blue figure is seated in a meditative pose. Two small black figures stand on the platform to the right.</p>		
<p>HNK581017014A</p>	<p>PDJ581107019A</p>	<p>KTU581008001A</p>

Table 9.4.34 Recommending Chinese temples in Phuket to others

Category	Frequency	%
Recommend Others to Visit		
Yes	149	97.4
No	4	2.6
Total	153	100
How They Would Recommend		
Word of mouth	144	60.3
Internet	91	38.1
None	4	1.7
Total	239	100
Recommend to Whom		
Friends and family	113	58.5
Specific group of people	28	14.5
Anyone interested	22	11.4
Website followers	10	5.2
Like-minded people	9	4.7
Everyone	7	3.6
None	4	2.1
Total	193	100

Table 9.4.35 Reasons for recommending Chinese temples in Phuket

Theme	Frequency	%
Recommend		
It is cultural	36	15.7
It is fascinating	36	15.7
It is attractive	32	14.0
It is unique	23	10.0
the Vegetarian Festival	19	8.3
It is religious	18	7.9
It is mysterious	15	6.6
It is small	12	5.2
It is worthwhile	11	4.8
the location	10	4.4
It is peaceful	7	3.1
It is educational	4	1.7
Not Recommend		
didn't understand the rituals	1	0.4
it is unorganised inside	1	0.4
only if walking past it	1	0.4
it was too small	1	0.4
not much to see	1	0.4
same as other temples	1	0.4
Total	229	100.0

Table 9.4.36 Future admission fee at Chinese temples in Phuket

Category	Frequency	%
Entrance Fee		
No	93	60.8
Yes	60	39.2
Total	153	100
Entrance Fee Amount (THB)		
0	93	60.8
1 – 50	38	24.8
51 – 100	15	9.8
101 – 150	7	4.6
Total	153	100

Table 9.4.37. Recommendations for promotional images of Chinese temples in Phuket

Theme	Frequency	%
Recommend		
statues/figures/gods	81	25.8
religious ornaments	63	20.1
building	58	18.5
activities	41	13.1
building feature	28	8.9
artwork	19	6.1
ornaments	16	5.1
information	3	0.9
offerings	3	.09
nature	1	0.3
not sure	1	0.3
Total	314	100.0

Table 9.4.38. Recommendations for promotional activities at Chinese temples in Phuket

Theme	Frequency	%
Recommend		
education/learning	113	36.2
praying	46	14.7
looking around	41	13.1
guided tour	33	10.6
taking photos	24	7.7
festival	13	4.2
making an offering	11	3.5
meditating	9	2.9
relaxing	6	1.9
eating	5	1.6
not sure	5	1.6
workshops	4	1.3
selling souvenir	1	0.3
fund raising activities	1	0.3
Total	312	100.0

Table 9.4.39. Recommendations for temple managers at Chinese temples in Phuket

Theme	Frequency	%
Recommend		
marketing/promotion	146	38.4
education/learning	129	33.9
tour	54	14.2
management	21	5.5
events/activities	14	3.7
food	8	2.1
infrastructure	7	1.8
public transport	1	0.3
Total	380	100.0

APPENDIX

9.5 Interview Questions

Interview Questions 1 – Local Expert

What function do Chinese temples play in Phuket?

What activities take place at Chinese temples?

How is Taoist culture important to Phuket?

What you think about Chinese temples and shrines being used as cultural tourism attractions?

What you think of tourists visiting Chinese temples and shrines?

What is the image being promoted of Chinese temples and shrines in Phuket?

What is the image being promoted of the Vegetarian Festival in Phuket?

Do you feel Chinese culture should be promoted in Phuket? Why and how?

Has the function of Chinese temples in Phuket changed? If yes, why and how?

Do the temples for the Vegetarian Festival stay the same or rotate every year? If rotate, please explain how or why this happens?

Interview Questions 2 – Tour Guides

How important are Chinese temples as an attraction in Phuket?

From where in the world is the demand for Chinese temples images and attractions coming from?

How did you respond or how do you respond to this demand?

What is the impression of Western tourists regarding Chinese temples?

What do they expect and what demands do Western tourists have from the Chinese temples attractions?

What promotional materials are you familiar with that are used to attract tourists to Chinese temples?

What are the dissatisfactions of local people regarding Chinese temples attractions and how do you respond to these dissatisfactions?

What are the latest plans for Chinese temples?

Interview Questions 3 – Tourists

ID									
Site:	_____								
Date:	_____								
Time:	_____								
Atmosphere:	_____								

Master of Business Administration in Hospitality and Tourism Management Prince of Songkla University, Phuket Campus

INTRODUCTION

My name is Inderpal Virdee. I am studying for a Master Degree in Business Administration in Hospitality and Tourism Management. I am collecting data for my thesis on **“Exploring the Image of Chinese Temples as a Cultural Tourist Attraction in Phuket Using Photographic Analysis Technique”**.

AIMS

This research aims to understand why and how international tourists perceive Chinese Temples and Shrines images as visitor attractions.

INTERVIEW LENGTH

This interview will last about 30 minutes.

RESULTS

The findings of this research will contribute to a greater understanding of visitors’ motivations as well as providing useful information for Chinese temple/shrine management and the creation of marketing campaigns for visitor attractions in general.

CONFIDENTIALITY

All respondents will remain anonymous in this research and all of your personal information as well as the contents of the interview will be kept with strictest confidence and not passed onto any third party.

INTERVIEW INSTRUCTIONS

There are no “right” or “wrong” answers. Please say what you think.
Please answer all the questions in full, with as much detail as you can.

IMAGE - SPOKEN

1	What image(s) come into your mind first, when you think about a Chinese temple/shrine? Why?
2	What are the distinctive features of Chinese temples/shrines in Phuket?
3	What was your first impression/feeling when you entered into this Chinese temple/shrine?

IMAGE – DRAWN (A)

4	Can you please draw a picture of the Chinese temple/shrine as a whole?
5	Can you describe what you have drawn? Please explain any details, and say what interests you about what you have drawn.

©	Image ID:											A

The creator of the drawing retains copyright of the image.

Creator Name:	Creator Signature:	Creation Date:
Email:		
The creator agrees to the use of this image in not-for-profit and/or international academic publications in relation to this study only.	YES ()	NO ()
I, the creator, agree to give the author of this study (Mr. Inderpal Virdee) full copyright permission to act on the creator's behalf in any future publication of this image outside of this study. If "no", written permission will be sought from the creator.	YES ()	NO ()

Important agreement notes:

- 1) Only the "Image ID" along with the drawing will be displayed in publications printed or electronic media.
- 2) No details of the creator's name, signature or email will be released in any publication.
- 3) The creator and/or third parties associated with the creator agree that any potential negative interpretations of this image outside of this study is beyond the control of the author (Mr. Inderpal Virdee) and therefore the author cannot and will not be held liable, nor face any legal prosecution in any court of law. By signing your name you confirm that you have understood and agreed to the terms and conditions of the important agreement notes.

IMAGE – DRAWN (B)

6	Can you draw or photograph any details of this Chinese temple/shrine?
7	Can you please describe what you have drawn or photographed?

©	Image ID:														B
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The creator of the drawing retains copyright of the image.

Creator Name:	Creator Signature:	Creation Date:
Email:		
The creator agrees to the use of this image in not for profit and/or international academic publications in relation to this study only.	YES ()	NO ()
I, the creator, agree to give the author of this study (Mr. Inderpal Virdee) full copyright permission to act on the creator's behalf in any future publication of this image outside of this study. If "no", written permission will be sought from the creator.	YES ()	NO ()

Important agreement notes:

- 1) Only the "Image ID" along with the drawing will be displayed in publications printed or electronic media.
- 2) No details of the creator's name, signature or email will be released in any publication.
- 3) The creator and/or third parties associated to the creator agree that any potential negative interpretations of this image outside of this study is beyond the control of the author (Mr. Inderpal Virdee) and therefore the author cannot and will not be held liable, nor face any legal prosecution in any court of law. By signing your name you confirm that you have understood and agreed to the terms and conditions of the important agreement notes.

THE COMPONENTS OF DESTINATION IMAGE

8	Please complete the following sentences in your own words?	
8A	The Chinese temple or shrine is	
8B	The layout of the temple is	
8C	The space is	
8D	The area around the temple is	
8E	The view from the outside is	
8F	The view from the inside is	
8G	The architecture is	
8H	The decorations are	
8I	The staff or keepers are	
8J	The climate is	
8K	The feeling I get at this location is	
8L	The smell is	
8M	The environment is	
8N	The sounds are	
8O	The atmosphere is	
8P	The activities are	
8Q	The religion is	
8R	The culture is	
8S	The experience is	

ACTIVITIES

9	What did you do in the Chinese temple? (<i>You can tick more than one.</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pray <input type="checkbox"/> Take photos <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Offerings <input type="checkbox"/> Look around Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Buy a souvenir <input type="checkbox"/> Get your fortune told <input type="checkbox"/> Ask advice <input type="checkbox"/> Ring the bell
---	---	--	---

CULTURAL PROMOTION

10	What images or pictures would you use to promote Chinese temples in Phuket? Why?	
11	What activities at the Chinese temple would appeal to you the most? Why?	
12	If you were the Chinese temple manager, how would you promote Chinese temples and shrines as cultural tourist attractions?	

INFORMATION ABOUT THE SITE

13	Which influenced you the most when deciding to visit a Chinese temple in Phuket?	<input type="checkbox"/> Newspaper/Magazine <input type="checkbox"/> TV <input type="checkbox"/> Internet Other (please specify): _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Guidebook <input type="checkbox"/> Word of mouth <input type="checkbox"/> Walking past											
14	What do you think about the information available to you at the Chinese temple?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td>Excellent</td> <td>Good</td> <td>Fair</td> <td>Poor</td> <td>V Poor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>-1-</td> <td>-2-</td> <td>-3-</td> <td>-4-</td> <td>-5-</td> </tr> </table>			Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	V Poor	-1-	-2-	-3-	-4-	-5-
Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	V Poor										
-1-	-2-	-3-	-4-	-5-										

RECOMMENDATION

15	What were your expectations before visiting the Chinese temple?											
16	How satisfied were with the way the Chinese temple is organised?	<table style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td>Very satisfied</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Very dissatisfied</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> <td>5</td> </tr> </table>	Very satisfied				Very dissatisfied	1	2	3	4	5
Very satisfied				Very dissatisfied								
1	2	3	4	5								
17	Would you recommend others to visit this temple?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Why?										
18	How would you recommend it?											
19	To whom would you recommend it?											
20	Would you like to make any other comments?											

DEMOGRAPHICS

21	What is your gender?	<input type="checkbox"/> Female	<input type="checkbox"/> Male
22	What is your age?	<input type="checkbox"/> 13–19 <input type="checkbox"/> 20–39	<input type="checkbox"/> 40–64 <input type="checkbox"/> 65+
23	What is your highest level of education?	<input type="checkbox"/> No Education <input type="checkbox"/> High School <input type="checkbox"/> College Level	<input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor's <input type="checkbox"/> Master's <input type="checkbox"/> Doctorate
24	What is your approximate income level (in US dollars) per month?	<input type="checkbox"/> \$1000 and below <input type="checkbox"/> \$1001–3000 <input type="checkbox"/> \$3001–5000 <input type="checkbox"/> \$5001–10,000 <input type="checkbox"/> \$10,000 and above	
25	What is your marital status?	<input type="checkbox"/> Single <input type="checkbox"/> Divorced	<input type="checkbox"/> Married <input type="checkbox"/> Widowed
26	What is your nationality?		
27	What is your religious belief?	<input type="checkbox"/> Buddhist <input type="checkbox"/> Christian <input type="checkbox"/> Jewish <input type="checkbox"/> Taoist <input type="checkbox"/> Spiritual	<input type="checkbox"/> Hindu <input type="checkbox"/> Muslim <input type="checkbox"/> Sikh <input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Agnostic Other: _____
28	Are you on holiday?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No If no, why are you in Phuket?: _____
29	How long are you in Phuket for?	days? _____	
30	What type of tourist would you consider yourself as?	<input type="checkbox"/> Leisure <input type="checkbox"/> Cultural <input type="checkbox"/> Backpacker	<input type="checkbox"/> Spiritual <input type="checkbox"/> Religious <input type="checkbox"/> Explorer Other: _____
31	Is this your first visit to a Chinese temple in Phuket?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
32	Did you intentionally plan on coming to this temple?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
33	What time did you visit?	<input type="checkbox"/> Morning – 06:00-12:00 <input type="checkbox"/> Afternoon – 12:01-18:00 <input type="checkbox"/> Evening – 18:01-00:00	
34	How much time did you spend at the temple/shrine?	<input type="checkbox"/> Less than 30 minutes <input type="checkbox"/> About 31 – 60 minutes <input type="checkbox"/> About 61 – 90 minutes <input type="checkbox"/> More than 91 minutes	
35	Did you visit this temple/shrine?	<input type="checkbox"/> Alone <input type="checkbox"/> With a friend(s) <input type="checkbox"/> With family member(s) <input type="checkbox"/> With a tour group <input type="checkbox"/> With a personal tour guide	

36	Why did you visit this Chinese temple/shrine?	
37	How much money (in Thai Baht) did you spend at this Chinese temple/shrine?	<input type="checkbox"/> Nothing <input type="checkbox"/> 201 – 300 <input type="checkbox"/> 1 – 100 <input type="checkbox"/> 301 – 400 <input type="checkbox"/> 101 – 200 <input type="checkbox"/> 401 or more
38	What did you buy at this Chinese temple/shrine?	Please specify:
39	Did you make a donation?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
40	Would you be willing to pay an entrance fee to visit this Chinese temple/shrine?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
41	How much entrance fee (in Thai Baht) would you pay to visit this Chinese temple/shrine?	<input type="checkbox"/> 0 – 50 <input type="checkbox"/> 151 – 200 <input type="checkbox"/> 51 – 100 <input type="checkbox"/> 201 – 250 <input type="checkbox"/> 101 – 150 <input type="checkbox"/> 251 or more
42	How many Chinese temple/shrines in Phuket have you visited?	Please specify: _____

Thank you for your participation!

9.6 (306) Projective Drawings of Chinese Temples and Shrine in Phuket

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VITAE

Name Mr. Inderpal Singh Virdee

Student ID 5730120021

Educational Attainment

Degree	Name of Institution	Year of Graduation
Bachelor of Arts	Central Saint Martin's College of Art & Design, London Institute, London, UK	1998

Scholarship Awards during Enrolment

None

Work

2013 – Present: Lecturer at Prince of Songkla University, Phuket Campus, Thailand

2013 – 2008: Communication Manager at LanguageCorps Asia, Pattaya, Thailand & Phnom Penh, Cambodia

List of Publications and Proceedings

Virdee, I. & Phakdee-auksorn, P. (2017). Exploring Destination Image Using a Projective Approach:

Chinese Temples and Shrines in Phuket, Thailand. *Journal of International Studies, Prince of Songkla University, Vol. 7(2)*.

Virdee, I. (2017). Photographic Tourism Research: Literature Review. Unpublished manuscript.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319271391_Photographic_Tourism_Research_Literature_Review

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